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X-ray radiation transport in GPU accelerated Particle In Cell plasma simulations

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Abstract

Ultra-high-intensity laser pulse interactions with solid density targets are of central importance for modern accelerator physics, Inertial Confinement Fusion (ICF) and astrophysics. In order to meet the requirements of real-world applications, a deeper understanding of the underlying plasma dynamics, including plasma instabilities and acceleration mechanisms, is needed. X-ray radiation plays a substantial role in plasma physics, either as an integral part of a physical system itself or as a useful diagnostic, hence it should be included in computational models. This thesis aims to introduce X-ray radiation transport to the Particle In Cell simulation software **PICongPU**. The key outcomes of this work are a Monte Carlo, particle-based, online, and in-situ solution to X-ray radiation modelling (enabling, among others, SAXS and polarimetry synthetic experiments), as well as an analytical formulation for multiple-order, coherent X-ray scattering within this model. Moreover, the thesis includes three-dimensional simulations of laser-matter interactions together with Faraday Rotation and SAXS calculation.

Zusammenfassung

Die Wechselwirkung von Ultrahochintensität-Laserpulsen mit Festkörper-Targets ist von der zentralen Bedeutung für die moderne Beschleunigerphysik, Trägheitsfusion und Astrophysik. Um den Anforderungen der praktischen Anwendungen gerecht zu werden, ist ein tieferes Verständnis der zugrundeliegenden Plasmadynamik, einschließlich Plasmainstabilitäten und Beschleunigungsmechanismen, erforderlich. Röntgenstrahlung spielt eine wesentliche Rolle in der Plasmaphysik, entweder als ein integraler Aspekt eines physikalischen Systems selbst oder als ein nützliches diagnostisches Instrument, daher sollte sie in Berechnungsmodellen berücksichtigt werden. Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es, den Röntgenstrahlungstransport in die Particle In Cell Simulationssoftware **PICongPU** zu implementieren. Die Hauptergebnisse dieser Arbeit sind: eine Monte-Carlo, teilchenbasierte, online und in-situ Lösung zur Berechnung des Strahlungstransports (die u.a. synthetische SAXS- und Polarimetrie-Experimente ermöglicht), sowohl als auch eine analytische Formulierung für die kohärente Röntgenmehrfachstreuung innerhalb dieses Modells. Darüber hinaus, umfasst es dreidimensionale Simulationen von Laser-Materie-Wechselwirkungen zusammen mit einer Berechnung von SAXS und Faraday-Rotation.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

Ultra High Intensity (UHI) lasers can be used to create highly energetic particle bunches. Giga-, recently even peta-, watt laser systems are able to create very strong electric fields, in order of $\text{MV}\mu\text{m}^{-1}$, when interacting with matter. Such fields can accelerate electrons and ions on much shorter distances as in conventional accelerators. Therefore, Laser Particle Acceleration (LPA) may play an essential role in accelerator miniaturization and development of tabletop systems. Such laser matter interactions and the resulting radiation come with possible applications in modern radiotherapy[1–5], fusion[6–8], and astrophysics[9–13].

The main goal in the LPA research field is to optimize the acceleration processes and keep reaching higher and higher particle energies¹, as well as higher bunch charges (particle counts). But, it is also extremely important to understand how one can stabilize[18] the acceleration and achieve high reproducibility². From the perspective of the many possible applications it is necessary to be able to provide bunches with certain parameters in a reasonably reliable manner. This is especially relevant in medical applications where the delivered dose and particle energy need to be precisely controlled.

Making progress towards these goals requires constant deepening of our understanding of the various plasma dynamics behind the acceleration process. Developing new, more thorough theoretical descriptions is only possible with a sufficient feedback from experiments, which is provided by experimental diagnostics. Because of a high complexity of physical systems in question, the theoretical work in the field of UHI laser matter interactions is almost always accompanied by numerical modelling[6] (see chapter 3). Consequently, also the diagnostics need to be simulated; and most plasma simulations can predict several experimentally measurable quantities such as particle energy spectra, but by far not all of them.

Some experimental diagnostics are based on either probing with electromagnetic radiation in the X-ray part of the spectrum or are measurements of such radiation emitted by the plasma itself. This kind of diagnostics are the main motivation for the work included in this thesis that is the development of a radiation transport module for the plasma simulation software PIConGPU[19, 20]. When it comes to X-ray probing this work is mostly relevant for ion acceleration experiments (see 2.1), and such diagnostics as the Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)[21–23], Grazing-Incidence SAXS (GSAXS)[24], Resonant SAXS (RSAXS)[25, 26], Phase Contrast Imaging (PCI)[27], and polarimetry[28–30]. These can provide insights into electron density distribution, but also magnetic fields (polarimetry), charge state specific ion density (RSAXS), and potentially electron temperature (GSAXS)[31].

These probing methods are motivated among other things by the large interest in plasma instabilities, such as the Rayleigh-Taylor[32–35] instability or one of the Weibel-like[36–45] instabilities. These

¹Current record values are 8 GeV for electrons[14] and 96 MeV for ions[15–17].

²A recent study[5] has demonstrated a stable delivery of 60 MeV ion bunches.

add to the complexity of the plasma dynamics, and are significantly influencing the acceleration process. They are manifesting themselves with small, down to nano meter scale, periodic structures in density and fields. Such formations can be, e.g., a sinus like modulation of the front surface or a build up of filaments in the bulk. Studies have shown imprints of such filaments in proton signatures[46, 47] coming from opaque plasmas³, but until now no direct experimental proof of their existence was provided. X-ray probing may deliver such evidence and enable a qualitative and quantitative analysis of these phenomena. The sub nm wavelengths allow for spectral frequency domain analysis of these structures with coherent X-ray diffraction imaging (SAXS and related methods). While, the ultra short character of XFEL pulses enables resolving the femtosecond scale dynamics.

There are experiments measuring X-ray emission, e.g. K-shell emission [48, 49], that could benefit from radiation transport modelling as well. Besides, the modelling could find application in simulating isochoric X-ray heating and could also improve standalone plasma simulations by including the reabsorption of the emitted radiation.

1.2. Thesis overview

One could summarize radiation transport as combined description of propagation, scattering, absorption and emission (see section 2.3.1). The computational features developed within the context of this thesis focus on the free propagation and the scattering part, with a special focus on X-ray probing in SAXS, and Faraday Rotation related polarimetry. However, this work creates a computational framework, which one can build upon to introduce absorption and emission in further code development.

This work fits into a context of some already existing software solutions. SAXS first order scattering can be calculated, via a Fourier transform, e.g, with GAPD[50] in post-processing, or with its partial in-situ implementation within PICongGPU — the XrayScattering plugin. It is important to note that neither of the two are radiation transport tools and are only capable of calculating scattering within the kinematic diffraction theory. Another post-processing based tool for SAXS is parataxis[51], a Monte-Carlo, density based X-ray scattering simulation framework for GPUs. My work is substantially its in-situ implementation and its further development towards a complete radiation transport solution. At this point, it is also worth mentioning [52] that already partially introduced X-ray emission into PICongGPU, namely synchrotron radiation and bremsstrahlung.

The next chapter will establish some theoretical background as well as mention some experimental methods related to this work. Chapter 3 will talk about plasma simulations, and it will introduce the Particle In Cell algorithm and its realization in PICongGPU. Ch. 4 deals with some of the design decisions that had to be made for the new module. In 5, I derive a theory behind the particle based modelling of coherent scattering and postulate some necessary corrections in the original algorithm from [51]. Finally, ch. 6 describes the very details of the new implementation. Chapter 7 discusses tests, while ch. 8 presents results of plasma simulations. The thesis ends with conclusions and outlook in ch. 9.

³Opaque to radiation in optical range therefore requiring X-rays for probing. See section 2.1.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Laser ion acceleration

As already mentioned, the topic of this master thesis are simulations of X-ray radiation transport in the context of laser ion acceleration. It is important to understand this physical context. Hence, before looking at the radiation transport itself, we shall start with this brief introduction to the field.

The main idea behind laser particle acceleration is to use a high intensity pulsed laser system to first ionize target material and then create very strong electromagnetic fields that can accelerate charged particles to, potentially, very high energies on extremely short distances. The accelerated particles can be either electrons or ions, and can either originate from the bulk of the irradiated sample itself or from contaminants on its surface.

It is reasonable to differentiate between the fields of ion and electron laser acceleration. Electron acceleration is usually achieved with the Laser Wakefield Acceleration mechanism in optically under-dense materials (e.g. gasses). On the other hand, most ion acceleration mechanisms require over critical or, at least, near critical densities; These can be achieved with solid targets like metal and plastic foils, or frozen hydrogen jets.

But what does it mean and why is this distinction relevant? A critical density is a free electron density n_c for that a plasma becomes opaque to electromagnetic radiation of a particular wavelength:

$$n_c(\omega) = \frac{\epsilon_0 m_e}{e^2} \omega^2 . \quad (2.1)$$

When speaking about a critical density within the context of laser acceleration, one means, if not stated otherwise, the n_c of the driving UHI laser. In this context, under- or over-dense means to have an electron density either below or above n_c .

Solid density plasmas can not be probed with radiation in the optical part of the electromagnetic spectrum, so one needs to use probes with smaller wavelengths, like X-rays. X-ray sources with beam parameters needed for such probing experiments are not easily available and currently require moving experiments to large scale XFEL facilities. Probing in electron acceleration experiments using gas targets is usually done with optical probes. Radiation transport in optical regime can be introduced into plasma simulations similarly to how the driving laser has been already included. This is not possible (see section 4.1) for shorter wavelengths. This thesis is dealing with concepts to include radiation transport in particle-in-cell simulations (see sec. 8) in order to model such short probes. A radiation transport module capable of simulating e.g. small angle scattering or Faraday Rotation (see sections 2.3.3 and 2.5) is developed. This new module is mostly relevant for X-ray radiation and solid density targets. With that, at least in the context of synthetic probing experiments, this work is rather related to ion acceleration.

The ion acceleration by means of laser matter interactions is a highly complex and diverse physical process. Depending on various experimental parameters, the acceleration can be driven by different

acceleration mechanisms and usually multiple mechanisms will contribute at the same time. In here, we are going to briefly describe the probably most well understood and established mechanism – the Target Normal Sheath Acceleration.

In the TNSA scenario (fig. 2.1) a target, usually a flat thin foil, is at first ionized by a laser at its front surface. (In some experiments the target may be already partially pre-ionized by a preceding laser pulse.) Since $n_e > n_c$, the laser can not propagate into the foil. And so, a large part of the radiation is being reflected, but some of it can be absorbed. Similarly to how there are many acceleration schemes, there exist a variety of different physical phenomena that can be responsible for this absorption. In general, the energy is transferred into the electron population while the heavier ions remain, at first, mostly uninfluenced. What is relevant for TNSA is that a part of the electrons can be accelerated towards the targets rear side to relativistic velocities. Some electrons will not be slowed down enough, on their way through the target, to stay in the foil and will overshoot beyond the foil boundary. This creates a charge separation which leads to an electrostatic field. This field contributes, in at least three ways, to the acceleration process. Firstly, it is strong enough to cause field ionization at the back of the foil. Secondly, it exerts a force on ions in this region so that the absorbed laser energy is being partially transferred to the ions. And finally, it will force the electrons that did not reach energies high enough to completely free themselves from the foil to move back to the front, where they can once again absorb laser energy. A part of the electron population will keep recirculating in this manner, through the target, and will keep transferring energy from the laser at the front to the ions in the back. At some point, some ions will reach energies high enough to leave the foil. Such ions will mix with electrons and escape the target as a charge neutral electron-ion cloud. These highly energetic ions can be then separated from the electrons and traversed to possibly another experimental set-up or a proton(ion) therapy station.

We see in eq. (2.1) that n_c is proportional to m_e , so as more and more electrons reach relativistic energies the n_c grows with $\langle\gamma\rangle$, the average gamma factor. In some parameter ranges this can allow the laser to partially propagate into the target, what significantly enhances laser absorption; and, leads to higher ion energies. This mechanism is called relativistically enhanced TNSA[53].

Another possible scheme is the Radiation Pressure Acceleration (RPA)[54]. In that scenario, the radiation pressure creates an inward bend in the target surface due to the hole-boring mechanism, which can occur at high enough laser intensities ($I\lambda_L > 1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ W cm}^{-2} \mu\text{m}^2$)[55]. The ions reflect on the curved surface and are accelerated towards the back of the target. If a foil is thin enough, the radiation pressure can actually push the complete target in a so-called light-sail mode[56]. This can lead to very high particle energies, but it is hard to realize experimentally.

2.2. Plasma instabilities

Laser-plasma interactions are in usual much more complex than the simplistic TNSA explanation from the previous section. As already briefly mentioned in the motivation, one can expect, in such interactions, transversal modulations in densities and fields; these are in general a manifestation of plasma instabilities.

These could be, for example, surface plasmons[57–59] originating in a three-wave decay from longitudinal density oscillations with the laser frequency ω_L and the double frequency $2\omega_L$ (driven respectively by the laser electric and magnetic field). Plasmons are particularly interesting since they can seed the Rayleigh-Taylor instability[58]; a mechanism that is widely accepted as an explanation for plasma surface rippling (observed in simulations[33, 34]). A plasma Rayleigh-Taylor instability occurs on sharp density profile and is not expected to dominate an interaction with significantly

Figure 2.1.: Schematics of the TNSA mechanism.

pre-expanded targets (with electron density dropping below n_c on a relatively long scale).

In pre-expanded foils one would rather expect some kind of Weibel-like instability. The original Weibel[60] instability was postulated for plasmas with an anisotropic electron velocity distribution, as in having different longitudinal and transverse temperatures; and, was derived from Boltzmann distributions. A bit simpler explanation was provided later by Fried[36, 61]. It goes as follows:

An initial magnetic field fluctuation $\mathbf{B} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}B_z \cos(ky)$ bends paths of electrons that move either along the x or the y direction in such a way that they form regions with opposite currents (separated by a half of the fluctuation wavelength). The currents originating from the electrons moving along x are enhancing the fluctuation field, while the currents coming from the electron movement in y direction are opposing the initial B-field. When the average velocities along x and y are identical, the contributions cancel out, but in a presence of an anisotropy the fluctuation will grow. Now, this explanation works also perfectly for two counter-propagating electron populations; for that reason this instability is sometimes also called a two-stream instability.

In laser-plasma interactions such B-field and density filamentation emerge due to the counter-streaming (recirculating) relativistic electrons. More on classification and growth rates of such two-stream instabilities, in the context of electron transport, can be found in [37–41]. Furthermore, chapter 8 presents particle-in-cell simulations that show this kind of filamentation for pre-expanded targets.

2.3. Radiation transport

2.3.1. Radiation transport equation

The radiation transport equation describes the transport of EM radiation in matter.

$$\left[\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \hat{\mathbf{s}} \cdot \nabla \right] I + (\mu_a + \mu_s) I - \mu_s \int_{\Delta E} \int_{4\pi} I \cdot P(\hat{\mathbf{s}}', \hat{\mathbf{s}}, \nu, \nu') d\Omega' d\nu' = \eta(\nu) + S(\nu) \quad (2.2)$$

It has the mathematical structure of a Boltzman equation. It is possible to write this equation for different radiation related quantities. This particular form is written for a so-called spectral radiance (or specific intensity) $I(\mathbf{r}, \nu, \hat{\mathbf{s}}, t)$. So that $I dA d\nu dt d\Omega$ is the energy emitted within a frequency band $d\nu$ at ν from a infinitesimal area dA at a given point \mathbf{r} in space within dt at a time t into a solid angle $d\Omega$ around certain direction $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$.

The first non-differential part is the extinction term. It includes the total loss of intensity due to absorption and scattering. μ_a and μ_s are respectively the absorption and scattering coefficients. These losses are opposed by the scattering from another direction $\hat{\mathbf{s}}'$ towards $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ (scattering in) as well as local emission of new radiation η . When the scattering is inelastic, one also needs to consider scattering between different frequencies and integrate over ν' within some ΔE . An external source of radiation can be also included, as an additional source term S . The $P(\hat{\mathbf{s}}, \hat{\mathbf{s}}')$ function under the integral is the so-called scattering kernel, or in other words, the probability for a transition from $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ towards $\hat{\mathbf{s}}'$. Often, the scattering process has a rotational symmetry and P will only depend on the angle between $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{s}}'$. In that case, the kernel can be identified as the differential scattering cross-section $\left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \Omega} \right)$ divided by μ_s . Eq. (2.2) can be further extended to include changes in polarization in terms of scattering between different polarization states. Such type of scattering will be briefly discussed in section 2.3.3.

When it comes to emission and absorption, these processes are directly related to the atomic (de)excitations of ions in the plasma, hence these quantities depend on a local distribution of occupied atomic states, while the atomic levels as well as the related transmission rates depend on an ionization state. In a such highly dynamical system like an ultra-high intensity laser matter interaction, one can not always expect the ionization state distribution to reach an equilibrium, at least on the relevant time scales. Because of that, a calculation of local emission and absorption coefficients becomes a quite challenging task. As already mentioned, this aspect of radiation transport will not be extensively discussed in this thesis. Instead, the next section directly dives into the details of X-ray scattering.

2.3.2. Scattering

Scattering on a free electron - Compton scattering

The relevant scatterers for radiation in the X-ray range are the electrons. The scattering on free electrons is in general the inelastic Compton scattering.¹ It was described and experimentally verified by Compton[62] in 1923, a proper theoretical derivation from the QED theory was published, for the first time, by Klein and Nishina in 1929 [63]. And so, the angular scattering cross-section for

¹The scattering is inelastic regarding only the photon energy. When the complete two body system (photon and electron) is considered the scattering is actually elastic and the energy and momentum are conserved.

Compton scattering is described by the Klein Nishina formula:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{1}{4} r_e^2 \cdot P(E_\gamma, \theta)^2 \left[P(E_\gamma, \theta) + P(E_\gamma, \theta)^{-1} - 2 + 4 (\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}')^2 \right]. \quad (2.3)$$

Here, $r_e = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 m_e c^2}$ is the classical electron radius, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}'$ are the initial and final polarization vectors;

$$P(E_\gamma, \theta) = \frac{E'_\gamma}{E_\gamma} = \frac{m_e c^2}{m_e c^2 + E_\gamma (1 - \cos \theta)} \quad (2.4)$$

is the ratio of the photon energies before and after the scattering. This change in photon energy is equivalent to a wavelength shift of

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda_C (1 - \cos \theta) = 2\lambda_C \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\theta\right), \quad (2.5)$$

where $\lambda_C = \frac{h}{m_e c}$ is the Compton wavelength of an electron, and $\theta = \angle(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}')$ is the scattering angle.

The inelasticity $1 - P(E_\gamma, \theta)$ decreases with smaller photon energies, hence for long enough wavelengths ($E_\gamma \ll m_e c^2 \approx 511 \text{keV}$) it can be approximated by the fully elastic Thomson scattering; this approximation is also valid for small scattering angles θ . Eq. (2.3) reduces in that case to the Thomson angular distribution

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = r_0^2 |\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}'|^2, \quad (2.6)$$

which can be also found in a purely classical derivation from the dipole radiation of an electron oscillating in the electric field of the incoming wave[64].

Let us have a further look at the dot product in (2.6). For that purpose, we define a pair of base polarization vectors in the plane orthogonal to the initial wave vector \mathbf{k} such that the first one $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_1$ lies in the scattering plane (the plane containing \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{k}') and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_2$ is orthogonal to $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_1$. $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_1, \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_2$ are analogously defined for \mathbf{k}' , see fig. 2.2.

Figure 2.2.: Base polarization vectors definition. The angle between $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_1$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_1$ is the same as the scattering angle θ . The two remaining polarization unit vectors $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_2$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_2$ are identical and are perpendicular to the shown scattering plane.

Now, we can compute the dot product for each pair of such base polarization vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_1 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_1 &= \cos \theta \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_1 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_2 &= 0 \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_2 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_1 &= 0 \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_2 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}'_2 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

We will now use these to simplify the cross-section. In a situation where the final polarization state is not being observed, one can simply sum over the two final states $\hat{\epsilon}'_{1,2}$. So for a defined initial linear polarization $\epsilon = \cos \varphi \hat{\epsilon}_1 + \sin \varphi \hat{\epsilon}_2$ the cross-section becomes

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = r_0^2 (\sin^2 \varphi + \cos^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi) . \quad (2.7)$$

If the primary source of radiation is unpolarized one needs to also average over the two initial orthogonal states². That results in:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{1}{2} r_0^2 (1 + \cos^2 \theta) . \quad (2.8)$$

Fortunately, for the purpose of SAXS, where the observed scattering angle is very small, one can approximate $\cos \theta$ with 1. Eq. (2.7) and (2.8) both become

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = r_0^2 . \quad (2.9)$$

The angular cross-section is now constant and independent of the scattering angle.

Integrating eq. (2.8) over the whole 4π unit sphere gives us the total Thomson cross-section

$$\sigma_T = \frac{8\pi}{3} r_e^2 \approx 0.665 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^2 . \quad (2.10)$$

It is also important to note that the phase of the scattered wave is shifted by π [64]. This becomes relevant for multiple coherent scattering.

Scattering on multiple electrons

The last section described scattering on a single free electron, but what is the scattered intensity from a distribution of particles? Let us first consider two electrons. One at the origin and the other one at \mathbf{r} . We are interested in combined scattered radiation from both of the particles on an arbitrary but particular point on a detector. We are working here within the far field approximation, that is the detector and the source are far enough from the sample so that one can approximate the outgoing and incoming radiation as plane waves. This also means that we can treat rays scattered at the same angle at different points in the sample, but reaching the same spot on the detector, as parallel.

The incoming wave reaching the electron at the origin is $-\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ ahead in phase as when it reaches the second particle, as one can see in 2.3. $-\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ is just the distance the wavefront travels between the particles over wavelength times 2π . The scattered wave accumulates additional $\mathbf{k}' \cdot \mathbf{r}$ in phase until its wavefront reaches the second electron. This makes the total phase difference between the two paths

$$\Delta\phi = \phi_1 - \phi_0 = \mathbf{k}\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{k}'\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r} . \quad (2.11)$$

$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'$ is the so-called scattering vector. In a case of an elastic scattering ($k = k'$)

$$|\mathbf{Q}| = 2|\mathbf{k}| \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\theta\right) , \quad (2.12)$$

²An unpolarized beam with photons polarized in all directions is equivalent to a mixed quantum mechanical state with half of the photons polarized along $\hat{\epsilon}_1$ and the other half along $\hat{\epsilon}_2$, since both ensembles have the same density matrix $\rho = \frac{1}{2}I$. A somehow more formal argument together with a derivation of eq. (2.8) can be found, for example, in [65, pp. 355-369] .

Figure 2.3.: The figure shows scattering on two points in space and illustrates how the phase difference between rays scattered at the two points is equal to $-\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{k}' \cdot \mathbf{r}$.

θ is again the scattering angle $\angle(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}')$ ³.

The total amplitude on the detector is just the sum of the two and equal

$$A(\mathbf{Q}) = A_e e^{i\varphi_0} + A_e e^{i\varphi_0} e^{i\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r}} , \quad (2.13)$$

with A_e - scattered amplitude from one electron, φ_0 - a constant phase including the propagation towards and from $\mathbf{r} = 0$ as well as a phase jump. From now on φ_0 is ignored since it can be always set to zero by a proper choice of coordinates.

The case of two electrons can be of course generalized to an arbitrary scatterer number

$$A(\mathbf{Q}) = A_e \sum_i e^{i\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r}_i} . \quad (2.14)$$

It is also possible to describe scatterer distribution by its number density and turn the sum in to a volume integral

$$A(\mathbf{Q}) = A_e \int_V n_e(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r}} dV . \quad (2.15)$$

This integral, $\int_V n_e(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r}} dV$ is just a Fourier transform of the electron density. It is often denoted by $S(\mathbf{Q})$ and called a structure factor. The fact that the far field amplitude for first order scattering (1st Born approximation) is a Fourier transform of a scattering potential is not unique to scattering on free electrons, but is a general founding from the scattering theory.

For Thomson scattering $A_e = E_{\text{out}} = -\frac{r_e}{d} e^{ikr} |\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}'| E_{\text{inc}}$ [64] so that the scattering intensity ($|A|^2$) at the detector in a distance d becomes

$$I(\mathbf{Q}) = I_{\text{in}} \frac{r_e^2}{d^2} P(\mathbf{Q}) \cdot S(\mathbf{Q})^2 , \quad (2.16)$$

where I_{in} is the incoming intensity and $P(\mathbf{Q}) = |\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}'|^2$ is the polarization factor. As already discussed, for small angle scattering P can be set to 1.

³Note, often in this context the scattering angle is defined as 2θ .

Scattering on ions

There are not only free electrons in a plasma but also atoms. When not completely ionized, these atoms have bound electrons that can scatter light similarly to the free particles. We look at first at a scattering from a single ion. It can be calculated by integrating over electron number density in the ion electron cloud just like in the case of a free electron distribution in a sample.

$$f^0(\mathbf{Q}) = \int_{\text{ion}} n_e(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r}} dV \quad (2.17)$$

When speaking about scattering from a single scatterer, in this case an ion, one usually calls this function a form factor rather than a structure factor. For small angle scattering, that is for $\mathbf{Q} \rightarrow 0$, f^0 is constant and equal Γ , the number of bound electrons.

The superscript zero in f^0 suggests existence of some corrections to the atomic (ionic) form factor. In fact, we were ignoring up until now that these electrons are bound. The full form factor looks like this:

$$f(\mathbf{Q}) = f^0(\mathbf{Q}) + f'(E_{\text{ph}}) + i f''(E_{\text{ph}}) . \quad (2.18)$$

The first correction f accounts for the fact that the bound electrons, especially in the lower shells, will have a smaller contribution to the scattering than the free ones. This effect depends on the ratio of the photon energy and the binding energy. For photon energies large in comparison to the binding energies the electrons can be treated as free and f' becomes zero. The second correction $i f''$ is imaginary, and it relates to the photo-absorption around resonant E_{ph} .

Now, the joint scattering amplitude from a distribution of ions is, analogously to the case of free electrons, equal to

$$A_{\text{ions}}(\mathbf{Q}) = A_i \int_V n_i(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{r}} dV = A_i S_{\text{ion}} , \quad (2.19)$$

where

$$A_i = A_e \cdot f_{\text{ion}}(\mathbf{Q}) . \quad (2.20)$$

Finally, the intensity from scattering on both ions and electrons can be expressed as follows[22]

$$I(\mathbf{Q}) = I_{\text{in}} \frac{r_e^2}{d^2} P(\mathbf{Q}) \cdot (S_{\text{free}}(\mathbf{Q}) f_{\text{free}} + S_{\text{ion}}(\mathbf{Q}) f_{\text{ion}}(\mathbf{Q}))^2 , \quad (2.21)$$

where f_{free} is the form factor of a free electron that is just 1.

It is worth noting at this point that when writing about collective scattering from multiple scatterers we were describing fully coherent scattering. But, the scattering described in the radiation transport equation is assumed to be incoherent. This becomes obvious when one realizes that integrating (2.2) corresponds to summing intensities and not amplitudes. One can still use it together with (2.3) to model scattering of incoherent radiation, like the one originating from emission within the sample. However, the analytical formulation needs to be modified to properly describe coherence. These changes will be introduced in chapter 5.

2.3.3. Faraday Rotation

Optical rotation is a rotation of the polarization plane of a linearly polarized light passing through a circularly birefringent medium (see fig. 2.4). A classical example of such medium is a glucose solution (sugar syrup). It turns out, also plasmas, at least in a presence of strong magnetic fields,

can show this behaviour as well. This follows from the left- and right-handed circular components of an electro-magnetic wave having a slightly different dispersion relation in a plasma. This was discussed in much more detail in my Bachelor thesis [30] and in [66, 67]. The total rotation for radiation following a path S is

$$\theta = \frac{e}{2m_e c} \int_S \frac{n_e}{n_c(\omega)} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{l} . \quad (2.22)$$

Here, $n_c(\omega)$ is the critical density for the probing X-ray frequency, \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field. The dot product with the path element means that only the parallel field component contributes to the rotation.

Such optical rotation that is proportional to the magnetic field component in the propagation direction is called Faraday Rotation. There exists a similar effect that is related to the perpendicular B-field component – namely the Cotton–Mouton effect. Instead of rotating the linear polarization it turns it elliptical. According to [29] for relevant X-ray energies and the expected magnetic field strengths the Cotton–Mouton effect is several magnitudes smaller than the Faraday rotation, so it can be neglected.

When electrons reach relativistic energies the rotation is reduced by a relativistic correction factor α . If one replaces n_c , in (2.22), with the relativistic critical density $\langle \gamma \rangle n_c$ and the electron mass m_e with $\langle \gamma \rangle m_e$, one gets $\theta_{\text{warm}} = \alpha \theta_{\text{cold}} = \langle \gamma \rangle^{-2} \theta_{\text{cold}}$. Here, $\langle \gamma \rangle$ is the average Lorentz factor of the electron distribution. This is the most straightforward choice of α ; In general the actual correction will depend on the electron velocity distribution [29].

Figure 2.4.: Illustration of the Faraday Rotation in a circularly birefringent medium.

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2.4. X-ray radiation sources

The oldest source of laboratory produced X-rays are X-ray tubes, which produce the characteristic Bremsstrahlung radiation spectrum. A much more modern source are synchrotrons. In these, electrons are forced on a circular path by magnets so that they emit radiation, collimated around their propagation direction, due to the constant change of their velocity vector.

This mechanism can be utilized much more efficiently by forcing accelerated (e.g. in a synchrotron ring) electrons on a sinusoidal path in between two layers of magnets, arranged with alternating polarity (see fig. 2.5). A device with such magnet placement is called an undulator. Furthermore, the electron velocity can be matched with the undulator period so that the radiation emitted by a particular electron at each turning point is in phase. With that, photons originating from one particle add up coherently, hence possibly achieved intensities can be higher than from a simple synchrotron source.

Still, the total radiation coming from all electrons is not coherent since there is no correlation between electron positions (The incoming electrons are randomly distributed within an electron cloud). This can be changed with particle bunching. If the electrons were concentrated in small bunches($\ll \lambda_{X\text{-ray}}$) and separated by $\lambda_{X\text{-ray}}$, radiation from all bunches would be in coherence. Exactly such bunch structure can spontaneously form in the undulator as a result of an interaction between the electrons and the emerging (at the moment still incoherent) radiation; this process is called Self Amplified Stimulated Emission (SASE). A radiation source utilizing this bunching principle is known as an X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL).

SASE for X-ray wavelengths requires very high electron densities in the incoming particle pulse. These can not be achieved with synchrotrons, but can be delivered by linear accelerators (LINACs). To be able to bring the electrons to high enough velocities, these LINACs need to be multiple km long. Building such large facilities is not an easy undertaking and takes a long time to finish, so there is only a handful of them in the world. The first XFEL working in the hard X-ray regime was the LCLS in California, USA (with the new LCLS-II extension under construction); then came SACLA in Harima Science Garden City, Japan; the newest addition is the recently commissioned European XFEL in Hamburg, Germany⁴.

The coherence is not the only advantage of XFELs, but also the very short pulse durations (down to a few fs), large range of available photon energies(0.26 keV to 25 keV), high repetition rates (up to 27 kHz), and high brilliance; a quantity describing source quality based on its intensity (ca. $10 \cdot 10^{12}$ photons per pulse), source size, relative bandwidth, and divergence. The values in brackets are given just for orientation and are valid for the EuXFEL[68].

Figure 2.5.: An undulator consists of a periodic dipole magnet structure. The static magnetic field is alternating along its length with a wavelength λ_u . Electrons in a beam traversing the periodic structure are forced to oscillate and radiate.

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⁴In Hamburg, there is also the FLASH FEL, but it can only reach soft X-ray energies (< 200 eV).

2.5. Experimental methods

One of the potential applications of such radiation transport module, as the one described in this thesis, are synthetic probing experiments. This section will briefly introduce two such probing diagnostics from the experimental perspective. These are the two experiments that will play a role in this work, but these are not the only ones that could be possibly modelled (see 1).

2.5.1. Small Angle X-Ray Scattering

SAXS is a well established experimental method outside the field of plasma physics. Usually, it is applied to obtain size and shape distribution of a certain type of particles[64]. The idea of applying SAXS to plasmas is rather new[21], but researchers were already able to show some promising results with structured targets[23]. This method uses coherent x-ray radiation of an XFEL to observe coherent scattering on an electron distribution in a target (see section 2.3.2).

At least at the first glance, the experimental set-up looks quite simple. The X-ray pulse is shot at a target, and photon detector is placed behind it on the X-ray axis. The detector distance is such that it allows for detection in the small scattering angle range of interest with a sufficient resolution. The necessary range and resolution depend on the kind of spatial features that one want to be able to see in the scattering image. The scattering angle is also limited by the loss of coherence due to the Compton shift (see eq. (2.5)).

The primary, not scattered, radiation can be caught by a beam stop or just reduced in intensity with a filter. Alternatively, with a bit more complicated experimental arrangement, it is possible to simultaneously use the unscattered light in a transmission based diagnostic, such as Phase Contrast Imaging.

Figure 2.6.: Schematics of a Small Angle X-ray Scattering experiment.

2.5.2. X-ray polarimetry

In a polarimetry experiment one measures a polarization of an initially linearly polarized X-ray pulse after passing through an optically active target. In the laser ion acceleration related polarimetry experiments the observed changes in polarization are mostly a simple rotation of the polarization plane, due to the Faraday Effect introduced in section 2.3.3.

In an experiment, the target is followed, on the beam propagation axis, by an analyser. The intensity of linearly polarized light passing through an analyser (polarizer) is determined by the Malus Law

$$I = I_0 \cos^2(\alpha) , \quad (2.23)$$

with α the angle between the initial polarization plane and the analyser orientation. Due to absorption and scattering the intensity before the analyser I_0 can change after passing through the sample. Hence, I_0 is measured simultaneously to the intensity behind the analyser, on a reference detector.

To properly resolve the target, and the structure within it, the image on a detector needs to be enlarged. This is realized with a set of focusing X-ray lenses (CRLs), placed in front of the the sample.

Figure 2.7.: Schematics of an X-ray polarimetry experiment.

3. Methods

3.1. Introduction

An analytical description of a plasma is usually realized either with a magnetohydrodynamical model or in a kinetic model. In the magnetohydrodynamical description the plasma particles, in most cases ions and free electrons, are treated as a fluid, or rather fluids when the different particle species are treated individually.

What differentiates magnetohydrodynamics from the common hydrodynamics, is that the fluid can be electrically charged, so it gives rise to EM-fields. Of course, in return these fields influence the non-neutral fluid. As one would expect, this model, incorporating both electro- and hydrodynamics, is governed by a combination of the Maxwell's and Navier–Stokes equations. Such description is used in many plasma simulation codes, such as `FLASH`[69].

As any other physical model the fluid description of plasmas is based on some assumptions and consequently it can not be reliably used in all plasma regimes. From the perspective of a laser plasma physicist, the main limitation of the fluid model is the requirement of a local thermal equilibrium. Such models expect particle species to have a nearly Maxwellian momentum distribution and a well-defined temperature. In the ultra-high intensity regime, on time scales relevant when describing interactions with such radiation, there is not enough time for the particle distributions to reach a local thermodynamical equilibrium. The low collisional frequency in hot plasmas (see e.g. section 5.5 on collisionless absorption in [55]) also contributes to this non-thermality of the modelled system since collisions between particles are the main thermalization driver.

Without well-defined temperatures one reaches towards the kinematical description. Here, the system is described in the phase space by a distribution of states. This means the particle velocity distributions are known and self-consistently modelled. There is no need for them to be Maxwellian. In the simplest case, the single particle velocity distribution evolution is governed by the Vlasov equation[6, 55]

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{x}} + q \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{\mathbf{v}}{c} \times \mathbf{B} \right) \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{p}} = 0 . \quad (3.1)$$

This is just a Boltzmann equation for particles in a Lorentz force field and without the collision term. In fact, this description neglects short range interactions (collisions) between particles and only includes long range ($>$ Debye length) phenomena. When the plasma can't be considered collisionless, the Vlasov-Fokker-Plack equation can be used instead.

It is possible to simulate systems by numerical solving of (3.1)[6], but such simulations are highly resource demanding and restricted to smaller systems in lower dimensions. The Particle in Cell algorithm[55] on the other hand, can significantly reduce the computational demand and allows, nowadays, for large three-dimensional set-ups with a considerable box size.

3.2. Particle in Cell algorithm

In a Particle In Cell simulation the EM-fields \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are defined on a discrete grid of points, which divides the simulation box into cells. The particle distribution $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p})$ is sampled with so called macro-particles. Each such macro-particle takes up a finite volume in the (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}) phase space and represents a portion of the underlying distribution. These particles carry attributes such as weighting w_i , charge q_i , mass m_i , position \mathbf{r}_i , and momentum \mathbf{p} . Here, the weighting is the number of physical particles represented by a macro-particle.

On each simulation time step, the EM-fields are updated by a direct integration of the Maxwell's equations over Δt (time step duration). For that purpose, grid values of the other two fields in the Maxwell's equations, that are charge and current densities, need to be computed from the neighbouring macro-particles [55]:

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_i w_i q_i S(|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i|) \quad (3.2)$$

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_i w_i q_i \mathbf{v}_i S(|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i|) . \quad (3.3)$$

Each particle contribution is weighted by w_i and a shape function S which depends on the particle distance to the evaluation point. The exact form of S can differ from simulation to simulation. After that, particles velocities and positions are updated according to the Lorentz force. To calculate the force for each particle the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} fields are interpolated from the grid points to the particle position. The repetitive execution of these steps on each time step is often summarized in the so-called PIC loop (see fig. 3.1).

Figure 3.1.: PIC loop

With this iterative approach it is possible to determine $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$, $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r})$, and $f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p})$ at any time for which the algorithm converges (usually $< 1\text{ps}$). f is available at first as macro particle data from which fields such as the particle number density, charge density, energy density, charge current etc. can be obtained just like in (3.2).

3.3. PIConGPU

PIConGPU is a free, open source Particle In Cell simulation software. It is written in modern `c++` and is currently using the `c++14` standard. With some help of meta programming techniques, `c++` templates, and compile time calculations the code can take a full advantage of compiler optimization while remaining highly flexible and applicable in many scenarios. Thanks to the parallelization abstraction library `alpaka` it can run on both GPUs and CPUs. As many gpu oriented software solutions it can run with `cuda` on nvidia products, and thanks to HIP support build in `alpaka` it can also run on AMD, or intel graphic cards.

Parallelization over CPU cores, both when running on CPUs only and while running CPU side operations in a GPU based setup, is done with the `openMP` library. When running on multiple computational nodes, e.g. on an HPC system, the inter-node communication is realized with MPI (Message Passing Interface).

The combination of MPI and one of the `alpaka` backends (`cuda`, `HIP`, `openMP`, ...) creates a parallelization hierarchy, which for GPUs extends further down into GPU blocks, wraps, and threads. In the following we will describe this structure for a GPU set-up, since the code is primarily developed with a GPU system in mind.

On the top level are host and device pairs. Each GPU is a device, and it is accompanied by a CPU host — It doesn't have to be a full CPU socket, just one or more threads constituting an MPI rank. Each of these pairs has a part of the simulation spatial domain assigned to itself. It holds all field and particle data from that region and performs all local operations. Some of these operations may either require to read or write data from, or to, the neighbouring domains. This is for example the case when a particle moves between domains of two different devices. For that reason, each GPU has some memory reserved to mirror a small part of the adjacent domains. This divides the cells stored on one GPU into three parts. In the centre is the so-called core, this is the part that is only stored on this GPU. It is encased by border, this is the part of the local domain which is mirrored on the neighbouring GPUs. The domain edge is covered by guard, this is the region that mirrors the adjacent borders — See fig. 3.3.

The next level consists of supercells. These are groupings of cells, which correspond to GPU blocks. Usually, a supercell would have $8 \times 8 \times 4 = 256$ cells in 3D or $16 \times 16 = 256$ cells in 2D. In most cases, a GPU block can run 256 threads in parallel, so the supercell size is optimized for block-wise parallelization over cells.

The division into supercells is also relevant for particle data storage. Particles, or rather particle attributes, are stored in containers called frames, each such frame can hold up to the supercell size of particles. A frame always contains only particles from one supercell. For each supercell and each particle species there exists a linked list of such frames. This allows for an easy and efficient parallelization over all particles in a given supercell — frame by frame. See fig. 3.2 for an overview of the GPU side hierarchy.

Something that is going to be relevant for the description of the implementation details in chapter 6 is how one is setting simulation parameters in PIConGPU. To fully leverage the `c++` optimization and save some computational time a significant part of a simulation set-up is defined in a set of so called `param` files. These are normal `c++` header files that are part of the source code, but are meant to be modified by a user. Consequently, the software needs to be recompiled every time a `param` file is changed. The remaining configuration is done via command line parameters, these are usually defined in a single `.cfg` configuration file.

Figure 3.2.: Parallelization on device with `alpaka`. The highest level in `alpaka` hierarchy is grid. The grid elements in `PIConGPU` are devices (GPUs). On the next level are blocks, each block corresponds to a supercell. Finally, each block consists of threads that are sequentially processing elements. In the case of `PIConGPU` the elements are usually either cells or particles.

Figure 3.3.: This figure shows the distribution of simulation cells between devices on an example of a GPU positioned in the down left corner of the total domain. The three zones — core, border and guard — illustrate how a part of each GPU domain is mirrored on an adjacent device. The guards on the sides without a neighbour are used for enforcing boundary conditions. Please note, this figure has a solely illustrative purpose and so the number of supercells in each domain, and cells in a supercell, is highly underestimated.

Another important concepts are kernels, virtual threads and virtual blocks. A virtual thread is a concept that allows running the same code on different architectures. Usually parallel operations will be called with 256 (supercell size) virtual threads per block and the code will be written in such a way that each virtual thread is processing one element, in parallel to the other virtual threads. Now, an actual compute system does not have to have this exact number of actual parallel threads per block available. In that case, the virtual threads would be evenly spread among the physical threads, so some threads would have to sequentially compute operations meant for more than one virtual thread. Virtual blocks work analogously. When there are e.g. more supercells to process than actual computational blocks, some virtual blocks will be executed sequentially. A kernel is a functor executed by physical threads. It implements a parallel procedure, typically it defines how tasks should be distributed among virtual threads within a virtual block.

4. Results

This section discusses the overall design of the new module. In this work the radiation transport is implemented in-situ as a particle based Monte Carlo algorithm. Here, a few approaches are presented and compared, including some we decided against.

4.1. Modelling radiation transport

4.1.1. Possible approaches

One possible way to include X-ray radiation in a Particle In Cell simulation would be to directly use the PIC algorithm. The radiation would just become a part of the simulation native fields which should be correctly propagated with the already present Maxwell solver. This is in fact how the optical laser is introduced. Unfortunately, resolution of a usual simulation is not high enough to resolve the small X-ray wavelengths. Typically, a probing beam in a SAXS experiment has photon energies around 8 keV. That corresponds to a 0.15 nm wavelength while common simulation cell sizes are somewhere between 1 and 100 nm.

Another possibility would be to use a wave-like representation. In that case, one could store the amplitude and phase as a complex field, with one value per cell, and use a Fourier wave-front propagation[64] to correctly propagate the radiation. Phenomena like scattering or absorption would need to be included in a complex valued refractive index $n = n' + in''$. It would need to be locally calculated for each cell, based on the local plasma parameters.

The third option is the particle picture. There are many radiation transport codes using this approach. The idea is to sample the intensity in eq. (2.2) with macro particles, just like the standard PIC algorithm is sampling particle densities while following the Vlasov equation. Scattering, absorption, and emission of radiation are introduced as random events. Particles are modified, deleted or created with a certain probability originating from well known cross-sections, e.g. (2.6). This is essentially a Monte Carlo simulation. Examples of such radiation transport codes are FLUKA[70], Geant4[71], MCNPX[72], PENELOPE[73]. More on this topic can be found in [74, 75].

We want to be able, in some scenarios, to simulate coherent effects. Unfortunately, these are not covered by eq. (2.2) and the standard Monte Carlo radiation transport algorithms. The post-processing tool `parataxis` is meant primarily for calculation of SAXS images, and it utilizes the particle approach. It does it by extending the standard algorithm by giving the macro photons an additional phase attribute. It turns out, this is not sufficient to properly simulate coherent multiple scattering. The algorithm needs, therefore, some further modifications, these are thoroughly discussed in chapter 5.

4.1.2. Pro and contra

Obviously, directly utilizing the Maxwell solver is not possible because of the not sufficient resolution. This leaves us with the two remaining options.

One key difference between them is memory consumption. Storing amplitude and phase per simulation cell is much less demanding as storing the many macro photons. Currently, the biggest limiting factor for three-dimensional PIC simulations is the available GPU memory. So the much smaller memory footprint of the wave-like solution is a huge advantage. When modelling coherent scattering the macro particles are not only sampling the intensity (or rather the amplitude) but also all the possible classical paths a photon can take, therefore requiring much more particles. For such set-ups the difference in memory demand is especially large.

On the other hand, the wave-like approach has a significant limitation. Without saving the wave field from previous time-steps it is not possible to include backward scattering. In contrary, macro particles can be easily scattered in all directions and no information is lost from time-step to time-step. One could argue, that at around the 8 keV the backward scattering is already slightly suppressed (From (2.3) follows that $\theta = 180^\circ$ is 6% less likely as a scattering at 0°). And, in a usual probing set-up with a detector at the front a photon needs to be scattered twice by approximately 180° to be detected. Additionally, such twice backward scattered radiation may be still coherent with itself, but due to a significant Compton shift for $\theta \approx 180^\circ$ (a reduction in photon energy by 94% after two such scatterings) it is no longer coherent¹ with the primary and the forward scattered radiation. All of that makes the backward propagation less significant but not necessarily irrelevant; especially not for incoherent radiation, radiation transport, calculating interactions with the plasma (such as plasma heating, self-absorption, or photoionization). With that in mind, this remains a strong argument for the particle picture.

Another important aspect is integration with other PIConGPU features. Here, a lot speaks for the particle approach. Firstly, the relativistic emission (bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation) was already implemented with macro photons. Secondly, usage of particles makes it possible to include certain interactions with binary collision algorithms. Currently, PIConGPU developers are working on an in-situ implementation for atomic physics[76], and binary interactions between macro ions and macro photons could be a way of self-consistent modelling of absorption and photo-ionization. Another example for such integration would be an application of binary collisions to Compton scattering as demonstrated in [77].

In the end, a decision was made to implement the particle approach.

4.2. In and ex-situ implementation scenarios

There are essentially three main approaches to how one can extend a simulation with a new analysis. These are post-processing (off-line and ex-situ), streaming (on-line and ex-situ), and implemented directly in the simulation (on-line and in-situ) — see fig. 4.1.

In theory anything that doesn't need to provide any feedback to the simulation can be done externally so either in post-processing or in a streaming set-up. For example, absorption and emission should be implemented in-situ since the influence on the particle temperatures needs to be included. On the

¹This, of course, depends on the initial spectral width, but for an XFEL pulse the wavelength shift is big enough for a loss of coherence.

other hand, in a probing setup, e.g. in a SAXS or polarimetry analysis, one could consider ignoring the X-ray influence on plasma.

An off-line ex-situ analysis would be simply impractical due to the amount of data such calculation may require. High temporal and spatial resolutions, necessary due to the usually very small scale and fast dynamics of the probed features, for multiple fields ($n_e, n_i, T_e, T_i, \vec{B}, \dots$), would often result in unmanageable output sizes. So the only practical alternative to in-situ is streaming.

We still decided to implement all the components in-situ. One reason for that is the possibility of combining the various aspects of radiation transport in order to, hopefully, provide more realistic predictions for the experiments. Another thing to consider are future extensions that would require an in-situ implementation, one example could be inelastic scattering in a SAXS set-up.

Figure 4.1.: Schematic representation of different analysis implementation scenarios. An analysis can be performed externally, either in post-processing or online in a streaming configuration. Post-processing requires storing data, possibly large amounts of it. When streaming, data is processed online and transferred e.g. over a local network. The third scenario is an in-situ implementation where the analysis is directly implemented in the simulation software and is using the same resources.

5. Analytical formulation for modelling coherent radiation

5.1. Introduction

Macro particles in PIC simulations are used to sample species phase space, which evolution is governed by some form of the Boltzmann equation (e.g. the Vlasov equation (3.1) for electrons and ions, or the radiation transport equation (2.2) for photons). The RTE doesn't incorporate coherence effects. The macro photons in `PICongPU` introduced in [52] originate in incoherent emission, so this was not a problem until now, but this new module is also meant for coherent scattering calculation. To correctly simulate, e.g. SAXS scattering patterns, we must extend this standard description.

One possible solution to coherent radiation representation in particle picture was introduced in [51] and implemented in the off-line tool `parataxis`. There, the macro photons became an additional phase attribute which is used to calculate the total phase $k \int_S ds$ accumulated along the path followed by a macro particle. The detector accumulates a complex value

$$w e^{ik \int_S ds} \quad (5.1)$$

for each macro particle (with weighting w) hitting a detector cell. Originally the macro photon weighting was initialized according to the photon density (in the incoming X-ray pulse), and the scattering was based on the scattering cross-section for photons, the Thomson scattering cross-section. It can be shown that this will result in a wrong scattering intensity. Scattering on a two-dimensional scatterer distribution, for example on a double-slit, can be described by the following formula[22]:

$$\frac{N(\mathbf{Q}, t)}{\Delta\Omega} = \frac{N_0}{A} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) |\mathcal{F}_{2D}[\sqrt{g_\perp} \tilde{n}]|^2, \quad (5.2)$$

with N_0 – number of photons in the incoming beam, A – irradiated area, $\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)$ – the angular scattering cross-section, g_\perp – photon distribution over the beam transversal cross-section (e.g. Gaussian), \tilde{n} – the areal scatterer density. With w initialized proportional to g_\perp and when using $\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)$ for macro particle scattering the detector value squared would be equal to

$$\left[\frac{N_0}{A} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) (\mathbf{Q}) \right]^2 \left| \mathcal{F}_{2D}[\langle g_\perp \tilde{n} \rangle_{\tau_R}] \right|^2. \quad (5.3)$$

Equations (5.3) and (5.2) may be similar, but there are two major differences: All the factors except for $|\mathcal{F}|^2$ are unnecessarily squared, and the Fourier transform is performed over $g_\perp \tilde{n}$ instead of $\sqrt{g_\perp} \tilde{n}$. It should be $\sqrt{g_\perp} \tilde{n}$ since the structure factor is a sum over scattering amplitudes that are proportional to the incident field amplitude and not intensity.

This discrepancy was not found in the validation tests in [51] as well as in the early tests for this new implementation (ch. 7) for two reasons. Firstly, in these tests the target was homogeneously

irradiated so that $g = 1$. Secondly, the scattering was calculated for angles for which $\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}$ can be considered to be constant, and therefore the only remaining difference was a constant factor, identical for all detector cells. This remained unnoticed because the results were, unfortunately, only analysed in arbitrary units. In the following we will introduce a modification to the particle distribution and scattering cross-section which will allow for correct intensity calculation.

To help differentiate between the photons (or macro photons) and the particles following the modified distributions the new species will be called amplitudons (or macro amplitudons).

5.2. Theoretical formulation including multiple scattering

5.2.1. Preliminary considerations

Before we introduce the new macro particle species and analyse the simulation algorithm, we will generalize (5.2) to account for multiple scattering and a time dependent, three-dimensional scatterer density. We start with some definitions.

The spatial distribution of photons in the incoming pulse, propagating towards the z direction, can be described by a probability density function $f(\mathbf{r}, t)$. It satisfies the normalization condition $\int_{\mathcal{V}} f(\mathbf{r}, t) dV = 1$ where \mathcal{V} is the volume covered by the pulse. More exactly:

$$\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{A}_{xy} \times [-l_{ps} + ct, ct]_z, \quad (5.4)$$

where \mathcal{A}_{xy} is the irradiated surface with area A_{ps} and l_{ps} is the pulse length. $V_{ps} = A_{ps}l_{ps}$ is the pulse volume. Further, f should be separable in a transversal and a longitudinal part so that one can write $f = f_{\perp}f_{\parallel}$. These new functions should also satisfy the usual normalization condition so that $\int_{\mathcal{A}_{xy}} f_{\perp} dA = 1$ as well as $\int_{-l_{ps}+ct}^{ct} f_{\parallel} dz = 1$. We also define a unitless function $g = V_{ps}f$ as well as $g_{\perp} = Af_{\perp}$ and $g_{\parallel} = l_{ps}f_{\parallel}$ with $g = g_{\perp}g_{\parallel}$.

The intensity is energy flux density, so that for photons with equal energy $\hbar\omega$ one can write:

$$I(\mathbf{r}, t) = \hbar\omega N_0 c f_{tot}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\hbar\omega N_0}{A_{ps}\tau_{ps}} g_{tot}(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (5.5)$$

Here the subscript *tot* stands for total radiation (initial plus scattered).

We also define a unitless amplitude

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{|E_{ref}|} E(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sqrt{\frac{I(\mathbf{r}, t)}{I_{ref}}} e^{i\arg(E)}, \quad (5.6)$$

with $I_{ref} = (\hbar\omega N_0)/(A_{ps}\tau_{ps})$ and E electric field. With that, the incoming amplitude can be written as

$$\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sqrt{g(\mathbf{r}, t)} e^{ikz}. \quad (5.7)$$

The plasma dynamics can be considered constant on the oscillation period time scales so that we can drop the $e^{i\omega t}$ term in Ψ_0 .

5.2.2. Single scattering

The total electric field that includes some initial field E_0 and radiation scattered on some potential at $\mathbf{r} = 0$ is equal:

$$E(\mathbf{r}, t) = E_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{f(\theta, \phi)}{r} e^{ikr} E_0(\mathbf{0}, t - cr) , \text{ or} \quad (5.8)$$

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \underbrace{\frac{f(\theta, \phi)}{r} e^{ikr} \Psi_0(\mathbf{0}, t - cr)}_{\Psi_{scatt}} . \quad (5.9)$$

The scattered radiation spreads away from the scatterer as a spherical wave with an angle dependent scattering amplitude $f(\theta, \phi)$. Here the potential is the electron electric potential and $f(\theta, \phi)$ is the Thomson scattering amplitude $f = -r_e |\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}'|$. For the case of the small angle scattering we can approximate $f = -r_e$. Let us consider in-phase scattering on multiple electrons in a small volume ΔV at \mathbf{r}' with scatterer density n . One can write then

$$\Psi_{scatt}(\mathbf{r}, t) = n(\mathbf{r}', t_R) \Delta V \frac{f(\theta, \phi)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} e^{ik|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}', t_R) . \quad (5.10)$$

This can be expanded into

$$\Psi_{scatt}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int dV' n(\mathbf{r}', t_R) \frac{f(\theta, \phi)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} e^{ik|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}', t_R) \quad (5.11)$$

to include scattering from the whole volume.

5.2.3. Multiple scattering

Until now, we were only considering the first scattering. For multiple scattering we can treat the scattered spherical wave, locally at the new scattering point, again as a plane wave. That allows us to reuse equation (5.11) by just replacing Ψ_0 with the previously scattered amplitude. The only problem is that $f(\theta, \phi)$ depends on the direction of the incoming radiation. This means that it depends on three scattering locations: the new one, the old one, and the one before. For time being we will assume the scattering to be completely isotropic with $f(\theta, \phi) = f = \text{const}$. With that the amplitude at the new scattering point depends only on the previous one. We arrive at an implicit equation

$$\Psi_{\text{new}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \int dV' K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') n(\mathbf{r}', t_R) \Psi_{\text{old}}(\mathbf{r}', t_R) , \quad (5.12)$$

where $K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = f \frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}$. It has an analogous form to the Lippman-Schwinger equation in the scattering theory, and so it has a similar iterative solution

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = & \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \int dV' K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') n(\mathbf{r}', t_R) \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}', t_R) \\ & + \int dV' \int dV'' K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') n(\mathbf{r}', t_R) K(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') n(\mathbf{r}'', t_R) \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'', t_R) \\ & + \dots , \end{aligned} \quad (5.13)$$

analogous to the Born series. Now in the general $f(\theta, \phi) \neq \text{const}$. case one just needs to replace $K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ with $K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') = f(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}'') \frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}$ and use $K_0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', -\infty \hat{\mathbf{z}}) = f(\mathbf{r} -$

$\mathbf{r}', \hat{\mathbf{z}}) \frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|}}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|}$ for the first scattering:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = & \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \int dV' K_0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') n(\mathbf{r}', t'_R) \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}', t'_R) \\ & + \int dV' \int dV'' K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') n(\mathbf{r}', t'_R) K_0(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') n(\mathbf{r}'', t''_R) \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'', t''_R) \\ & + \int dV' \int dV'' \int dV''' [K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') n(\mathbf{r}', t'_R) K(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'', \mathbf{r}''') n(\mathbf{r}'', t''_R) \\ & \times K_0(\mathbf{r}'', \mathbf{r}''') n(\mathbf{r}''', t'''_R) \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}''', t'''_R)] + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (5.14)$$

We can reformulate it into:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = & \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \sum_{m=1} \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 \dots \int d^3\mathbf{r}_m \prod_{i=1}^m f(\theta_i, \phi_i) \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_{R,i})}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} \\ & \times e^{ik(\sum_i |\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|)} \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) . \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

Here θ_i, ϕ_i are the scattering angles.

Since we are interested in Thomson scattering with a maximal scattering angle θ_{\max} for which the scattering is still coherent, we write $f(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') = -r_e U(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}')$ as a function of the incoming and outgoing directions \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{s}' , where $U = H(1 - \frac{\theta}{\theta_{\max}})$ the Heaviside function and $\theta = \angle(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}')$. This can be written out as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = & \Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) + \sum_{m=1} (-1)^m r_e^m \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 \dots \int d^3\mathbf{r}_m [U(\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1, \hat{\mathbf{z}}) \\ & \times \prod_{i=2}^m (U(\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_{i-1})) \prod_{i=1}^m \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_{R,i})}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} \sqrt{g(\mathbf{r}_1, t_{R,1})} e^{ik(\sum_i |\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i| + z_1)}] , \end{aligned} \quad (5.16)$$

where in the sum $\mathbf{r}_{m+1} = \mathbf{r}$ and in the $m = 1$ term the product $\prod_{i=2}^1 U = 1$.

5.2.4. From amplitude to intensity

Now to get an average intensity value we average the electric field over some coherence time τ_{coh} .

$$\Psi_{\tau_{\text{coh}}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{coh}}} \int_{t-\tau_{\text{coh}}}^t \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t') dt' \quad (5.17)$$

and

$$I_{\tau_{\text{coh}}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\hbar\omega N_0}{A_{\text{ps}} \tau_{\text{ps}}} |\Psi_{\tau_{\text{coh}}}(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 \quad (5.18)$$

5.2.5. Two dimensional case

Lastly, one can show that the equation (5.2) follows from this general formulation. We start with the $m = 1$ single scattering term from (5.15)

$$\Psi_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 f(\theta_1, \phi_1) \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1|} \sqrt{g(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1)} e^{ik(|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1| + z_1)} \quad (5.19)$$

One can rewrite the accumulated phase $e^{ik(|\mathbf{r}_D - \mathbf{r}_1| + z_1)}$ as a sum of a phase for scattering at $\mathbf{r} = 0$ and a difference between this reference path and a path with scattering at a given \mathbf{r}_i . This difference in the far field approximation is $\mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1$. That means,

$$e^{ik(|\mathbf{r}_D - \mathbf{r}_1| + z_1)} = e^{i\varphi_0} e^{i\mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1} . \quad (5.20)$$

$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}$ is the scattering vector. We also consider $Q_z = 0$ which is valid for small angle scattering in thin targets. For a two-dimensional scatterer density distribution $n(\mathbf{r}) = \tilde{n}(x, y, t)\delta(z)$ and a square pulse ($g(\mathbf{r}, t) = g_\perp(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$) Ψ_1 becomes

$$\Psi_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = e^{i\phi_0} \iint dx dy f(\theta_1, \phi_1) \frac{n(x, y, t_1)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1|} \sqrt{g_\perp}(x, y) e^{i(Q_x x + Q_y y)} . \quad (5.21)$$

In the far field limit all rays scattered from the scattering volume towards the same detector can be approximately treated as parallel so that the detector position \mathbf{r} can be identified by the corresponding scattering vector \mathbf{Q} and $f(\theta_1, \phi_1) \rightarrow f(\mathbf{Q})$ can be taken in front of the integral. Further we approximate $|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1|$ with a constant detector distance d so that

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_1(\mathbf{Q}, t) &= e^{i\phi_0} \frac{1}{d} f(\theta_1, \phi_1) \iint dx dy (\tilde{n}\sqrt{g_\perp})(x, y, t_1) e^{i(Q_x x + Q_y y)} \\ &= e^{i\phi_0} \frac{1}{d} f(\mathbf{Q}) \mathcal{F}_{2D}[\tilde{n}\sqrt{g}] . \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

We insert now Ψ_1 into (5.17). One can switch the time integral with the Fourier integral so one gets

$$\Psi_\tau(\mathbf{Q}, t) = e^{i\phi_0} \frac{1}{d} f(\mathbf{Q}) \mathcal{F}_{2D}[\langle \tilde{n}\sqrt{g} \rangle_\tau] , \quad (5.23)$$

$\langle \cdot \rangle_\tau$ denotes a time average over a detection interval τ . In the case of a two-dimensional distribution and assuming full temporal coherence $\tau = \tau_{\text{ps}}$.

Using (5.18) and $N(\mathbf{Q}, t) = A_{\text{det}} \tau I_\tau(\mathbf{Q}, t)$ we arrive at

$$N(\mathbf{Q}, t) = \frac{N_0}{A_{\text{ps}}} A_{\text{det}} \left(\frac{|f(\mathbf{Q})|}{d} \right)^2 \left| \mathcal{F}_{2D}[\langle \tilde{n}\sqrt{g} \rangle_\tau] \right|^2 \quad (5.24)$$

The solid angle covered by the detector cell $\Delta\Omega$ can be written as $\frac{A_{\text{det}} \cos(\theta)}{d^2}$. $A_{\text{det}} \cos(\theta)$ is the projected detector cell area, for small scattering angles θ $\cos(\theta) \approx 1$ so that

$$\frac{N(\mathbf{Q}, t)}{\Delta\Omega} = \frac{N_0}{A_{\text{ps}}} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) (\mathbf{Q}) \left| \mathcal{F}_{2D}[\langle \tilde{n}\sqrt{g} \rangle_\tau] \right|^2 . \quad (5.25)$$

Here we used $\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) (\theta, \phi) = |f(\theta, \phi)|^2$.

5.3. Photons and amplitudons

In this section we use the findings from the previous section to formulate probability distributions for amplitudons. The goal is to correctly sample the amplitude Ψ rather than $|\Psi|^2$.

5.3.1. Initial distribution

The initial distribution f for photons can be written as $f = \frac{|\Psi_0|^2}{V_{\text{ps}}}$. For amplitudons we choose, instead, their initial probability density $h(\mathbf{r}, t)$ to be proportional to $|\Psi_0|$:

$$\begin{aligned} h(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}}\sqrt{V_{\text{ref}}}\mathcal{N}_{\text{am}}} |\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}, t)| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}}\sqrt{V_{\text{ref}}}\mathcal{N}_{\text{am}}} \sqrt{g}(\mathbf{r}, t) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ref}}}\mathcal{N}_{\text{am}}} \sqrt{f}(\mathbf{r}, t) , \end{aligned} \quad (5.26)$$

Where $\mathcal{N}_{\text{am}} = \frac{1}{V_{\text{ps}}} \int_{\mathcal{V}} \sqrt{g}(\mathbf{r}, t) dV$ is a normalization factor. We need it since in general $\mathcal{N}_{\text{am}} \neq \frac{1}{V_{\text{ps}}} \int_{\mathcal{V}} g dV = 1$. V_{ref} is an arbitrary reference volume that can be freely chosen.

5.3.2. Angular scattering distribution

Let us consider scattering of amplitudon particles on a single electron. The scattering process is described by eq. (5.9) and $|\Psi_{\text{scatt}}(\mathbf{r}, t)| = \frac{|f(\theta, \phi)|}{r} |\Psi_0(0, t_R)|$. We are interested in the probability of scattering into some solid angle Ω_0 . This probability is equal to the ratio of the incoming and the scattered probability currents. The probability current density is just the probability density times velocity so that the current through an area ΔA is:

$$J_{\text{inc}} = c\Delta A h(0, t_R) \quad (5.27)$$

and for the scattered flux we can write

$$\begin{aligned} dJ_{\text{out}} &= c h_{\text{scatt}}(\mathbf{r}, t) dA \\ &= c \frac{|\Psi_{\text{scatt}}(\mathbf{r}, t)|}{V_{\text{ps}}\mathcal{N}_{\text{am}}} r^2 d\Omega \\ &= c h(0, t_R) \frac{|f(\theta, \phi)|}{r} r^2 d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (5.28)$$

with that we find the scattering probability

$$\begin{aligned} P_S &= \frac{J_{\text{out}}}{J_{\text{inc}}} = \frac{1}{J_{\text{inc}}} \int_{\Omega_0} \left(\frac{dJ_{\text{out}}}{d\Omega} \right) d\Omega \\ &= \frac{1}{\Delta A} r \int_{\Omega_0} |f(\theta, \phi)| d\Omega . \end{aligned} \quad (5.29)$$

From this follows the angular scattering cross-section

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{am}} = \Delta A \frac{dP_S}{d\Omega} = r |f(\theta, \phi)| , \quad (5.30)$$

as well as the total scattering cross-section

$$\sigma_{\text{tot,am}} = \int_{4\pi} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{am}} d\Omega = r \int_{4\pi} |f(\theta, \phi)| d\Omega . \quad (5.31)$$

What is unusual about σ_{am} is that it depends on the distance to the observation point \mathbf{r} (or the point of next scattering). The standard formula

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) = |f(\theta, \phi)|^2 \quad (5.32)$$

can be derived in an analogous way by starting with a probability density proportional to $|\Psi|^2$ [78].

The r dependence is problematic since there is no way to know at a moment of some scattering event where and if the particle will be scattered again. One way of incorporating this into the simulation algorithm is to calculate at first the probability for some reference distance l_0 and multiply at the next scattering or detection the particle weighting by r/l_0 . For the distance to be known at the next event it is enough to save the time step of the last event as an additional particle attribute and get r as $r = c(t - t_{\text{last}})$.

5.3.3. Summarized changes

	particles	photons	amplitudons
initial distribution		$f = \frac{1}{V_{\text{ps}}} g$	$h = \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}} V_{\text{ref}} \mathcal{N}_{\text{am}}}} \sqrt{g}$
scattering		$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{ph}} = f(\theta, \phi) ^2$	$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{am}} = l_0 f(\theta, \phi) $
		$\sigma_{\Omega} = \int_{\Omega} f(\theta, \phi) ^2$	$\sigma_{\Omega} = l_0 \int_{\Omega} f(\theta, \phi) $
# particles in pulse		N_0	$\sqrt{N_0} \mathcal{N}_{\text{am}}$

- f is the scattering amplitude $f = -r_0 |\epsilon, \epsilon'|$ for Thompson scattering (ϵ is the polarization vector) and for small angle scattering $f \approx -r_0$.
- r_{12} is the distance to the next event.
- A macro amplitudon gets an extra attribute t_{last} .
- The choice of the number of amplitudons in a pulse is such that the number density $n_{\text{am}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ref}}}} \sqrt{n_{\text{ph}}}$.
- The particle weight is multiplied by $\frac{c(t-t_{\text{last}})}{l_0}$ at each scattering event (except of the first one). On detection by $\frac{c(t-t_{\text{last}})+d}{l_0}$ with d the remaining detector distance.

5.4. Detector value in a SAXS set-up

5.4.1. Introductory considerations

Let us start with some definitions. We define $D(\mathbf{r}_D, t)$ as the complex value accumulated on a detector at a cell at \mathbf{r}_D at time t . $\Delta D(\mathbf{r}_D, t)$ is the contribution to D from one simulation time step Δt at t , or a sum over contributions from all histories (macro amplitudons) scattered towards \mathbf{r}_D and terminating within Δt at t . \mathcal{A} is the set of these histories.

Each macro amplitudon contributes a complex value $w e^{i\varphi}$, where w is the macro particle weighting,

and φ is the acquired phase shifted to some reference time t_0 . Using these definitions we can write

$$\Delta D(\mathbf{r}_D, t) = \sum_{i \in I(\mathcal{A})} \omega_i e^{i\varphi_i} . \quad (5.33)$$

Now, starting from eq. (5.33), which describes the actual summation in the code, we try to find the physical meaning behind this quantity. At the end we want to show that for fully coherent scattering up to an arbitrary scattering order the simulation is equivalent to the formulation introduced in section 5.2.

In the following, we work with the assumption that each macro amplitudon is representing the same fully coherent source. In that particular case, φ depends only on the path taken by the macro particle. Further, all macro amplitudons shall be initialized with $\mathbf{k} = k_z \mathbf{z}$. With that, the path, and so the phase φ as well, depends only on all the scattering points $\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots)$ in the target and the detector cell it hits (\mathbf{r}_D). In the following we denote $e^{i\varphi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_D)}$ with $\Phi(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{r}_D)$.

5.4.2. Phase calculation

As already discussed, the amplitudon particles carry a phase attribute so that it can be included in coherent scattering calculation. One could think of advancing the phase attribute by $\omega \Delta t$ on each time step for every particle. But, every such update would generate a slight error due to the non-exact nature of floating point operations. It turns out, this error, accumulated over many simulation steps, would easily lead to a numerical loss of coherence. This would be obviously unacceptable so that another approach was postulated[51]. Instead of performing costly and error-prone updates on each step, the phase can be calculated from a constant initial phase attribute and the simulation time step in which the particle leaves the simulation. This works as follows: At first the particles are initialized with

$$\phi_0 = kz_0 - \omega t_0 + \varphi_0 , \quad (5.34)$$

where z_0 – the initial z coordinate, t_0 – initialization time, and φ_0 is a constant phase offset (by default zero). We assumed here that the particles move initially in the positive z direction. Once the particle is about to leave the simulation at some time t_f , its phase at the detector is obtained from

$$\phi_D = -\omega t_f + kd + \phi_0 . \quad (5.35)$$

d is the distance to the detector cell from where the particle is at t_f . We insert ϕ_0 and get

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_D &= \omega(t_f - t_i) + kd + kz_0 + \varphi_0 \\ &= k(s + d + z_0) + \varphi_0 , \end{aligned} \quad (5.36)$$

where s is a distance the particle moved since the initialization. In total, $s + d + z_0$ is the distance which a ray represented by the particle travels since it enters the simulation box at $z = 0$, while pointing towards z , till it reaches some detector cell at a distance d from the particles last recorded position. $\Phi(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{r}_D) = e^{\phi_D}$.

5.4.3. General formulation

We divide the simulation box into cells such that Φ won't vary significantly between scattering positions within the cell. We call the set of all these cells \mathcal{R} , and the subset of \mathcal{A} with all the macro particles scattered (in order) in cells at $\mathbf{R}_i = (\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots)$ is denoted as \mathcal{A}_i , where \mathbf{R}_i is an element of

the set of all (partial) permutations with repetition (excluding direct repetitions, that is scattering directly into the same cell) of \mathcal{R} denoted here as $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{R})$ — see fig. 5.1. We can write

Figure 5.1.: This figure illustrates the meaning of the \mathbf{R}_i tuples. Paths B and C correspond to the same tuple $\mathbf{R} = ((0, 1), (2, 2), (3, 1))$. Path A has scattering points in the same cells but in different order, so it is represented by a different tuple $((2, 2), (0, 1), (3, 1))$, while path D has scattering points in completely different cells.

$$\Delta D(\mathbf{r}_D, t) = \sum_{i \in I(\mathcal{A})} w_i \Phi(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_D) = \sum_{\mathbf{R}_i \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{R})} \left(\Phi(\mathbf{R}_i, \mathbf{r}_D) \sum_{j \in I(\mathcal{A}_i)} w_j \right). \quad (5.37)$$

$N^i = \sum_{j \in I(\mathcal{A}_i)} w_j$ is the number of amplitudons which followed a scattering path with scattering points in cells defined by the tuple \mathbf{R}_i , and the detector cell \mathbf{r}_D ; such that they arrived at the detector within Δt at t . In other words, $N^i = j_i(\mathbf{r}_D, t) A_{\text{det}} \Delta t$, where $j_i(\mathbf{r}_D, t)$ is the particle current density (only including particles following paths described by R_i), and A_{det} is the detector cell area. We can write $J_i(\mathbf{r}_D, t) = j_i(\mathbf{r}_D, t) A_{\text{det}}$ as

$$J_i(\mathbf{r}_D, t) = j_0(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) A_{\text{cell}} P(\mathbf{r}_1 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}_D, \mathbf{R}_i). \quad (5.38)$$

Here, $j_0(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) A_{\text{cell}}$ is the incoming flux through the cell where the first scattering happens, at the retarded time t_1 . $P(\mathbf{r}_1 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}_D, \mathbf{R}_i) = P(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_D, t)$ is the probability to scatter at this cell and after that follow a path, with arrival time t , which is included in \mathbf{R}_i .

Now, let us consider scattering of a given order $m > 0$. That means, we sum, at first, only over R_i with m elements. We multiply by $(V_{\text{cell}}/V_{\text{cell}})^m$ and write

$$\frac{\Delta D_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{\Delta t} = \sum_{\mathbf{R}_i \in \mathcal{P}_m(\mathcal{R})} \left(\Phi(\mathbf{R}_i, \mathbf{r}_D) j_0(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) A_{\text{cell}} \frac{P(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D, t)}{V_{\text{cell}}^m} V_{\text{cell}}^m \right). \quad (5.39)$$

In the $V_{\text{cell}} \rightarrow 0, \Delta t \rightarrow 0$ limit this becomes:

$$\frac{dD_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} = \prod_{k=1}^m \int d^3 \mathbf{r}_k \Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D) j_0(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) p(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D, t), \quad (5.40)$$

where

$$p(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D, t) = \frac{\partial^{3m-2} P(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D, t)}{\partial z_1 \partial x_2 \partial y_2 \partial z_2 \cdots \partial x_m \partial y_m \partial z_m} \quad (5.41)$$

is a probability density with $3m - 2$ variables $(z_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots)$ and 6 parameters $(x_1, y_1, \mathbf{r}_D, t)$.

In the remaining $m = 0$ case of no scattering:

$$\frac{dD_0(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} = j_0(\mathbf{r}_d, t) A_{\text{det}} e^{ikz_D} . \quad (5.42)$$

5.4.4. Finding probability density

The next step is to find an expression for $p(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D, t)$. For that, let us consider scattering paths such that:

- Initially, the particle comes from the $-z$ direction.
- Each scattering happens within a small cubical volume element $dV_i = dx_i dy_i dz_i$. The volume elements are located at $\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m$ and oriented in such a way that one of the sides of the cube is perpendicular to the line connecting the previous point \mathbf{r}_{i-1} with the current one \mathbf{r}_i (or perpendicular to $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ for the first scattering).
- The scattering angles θ_i, ϕ_i are such that the new direction vector points towards the perpendicularly oriented surface of the volume element at z_{i+1} , with area $dV_i^{2/3}$. In case of the last scattering the angles are such that the particle hits the detector cell at \mathbf{r}_D .
- Each event happens at a corresponding retarded time t_i . Each t_i is unambiguously defined by the detector arrival time t , the speed of light c and the distances between the scattering points.

This is illustrated on an example in fig. 5.2.

Figure 5.2.: This figure shows volume elements together with a detector cell defining a certain bundle of possible scattering paths. Please, refer to the bullet points at the beginning of section 5.4.4 for a detailed explanation. Of course, points \mathbf{r}_i do not have to necessarily lay in the same plane.

The probability to be scattered while travelling a distance Δl is equal to $\Delta l/l_s$. $l_s = (n\sigma)^{-1}$ is the mean scattering path, with n – the scatterer density and σ – the scattering cross-section. If we only look at scattering into some small solid angle $\Delta\Omega_i$, σ is not the total cross-section but rather

$$\sigma(\Omega_i) = \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) d\Omega \approx \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right) \Delta\Omega_i . \quad (5.43)$$

Now, the probability to scatter around \mathbf{r}_i within dV_i at t_i just like it was defined in the bullet points above, is

$$P_i = n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_i) \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{am}} \Delta\Omega_i dV_i^{1/3}. \quad (5.44)$$

$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{am}} = |\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i| |f(\theta, \phi)|$ depends on \mathbf{r}_{i+1} . A solid angle illuminating a small surface A in a distance d is equal to the projected surface $A \cos(\alpha)$ over d^2 , with α the angle between the irradiated surface and the illumination direction. Here $\alpha = 0$ so that

$$P_i = n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_i) \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} |f(\theta_i, \phi_i)| dV_{i+1}^{2/3} dV_i^{1/3}. \quad (5.45)$$

For the first scattering we can write dz_1 instead of $dV_1^{1/3}$ since the first volume element is oriented along the x,y, and z axes and the particles move initially along z.

P_m looks a bit different since we are not scattering towards the next volume element but towards the detector cell.

$$P_m = n(\mathbf{r}_m, t_m) \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_D - \mathbf{r}_m|} |f(\theta_m, \phi_m)| A_{\text{det}} dV_m^{1/3}. \quad (5.46)$$

Here the angle α_D — see fig. 5.2 — between the line connecting \mathbf{r}_m with the detector centre and the line through \mathbf{r}_m and \mathbf{r}_D does not have to be zero. Nevertheless, for a detector in a large enough distance covering a small solid angle, as it is in a SAXS setup, α is small enough to stay within the $\cos(\alpha) \approx 1$ approximation.

The total probability when $m = 1$ is

$$P = n(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_D - \mathbf{r}_1|} |f(\theta_1, \phi_1)| A_{\text{det}} dz_1 \quad (5.47)$$

for $m = 2$

$$P = P_1 * P_2 = n(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) n(\mathbf{r}_2, t_2) \frac{|f(\theta_1, \phi_1)| |f(\theta_2, \phi_2)|}{|\mathbf{r}_D - \mathbf{r}_2| |\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1|} A_{\text{det}} dz_1 \underbrace{dV_2^{2/3} dV_2^{1/3}}_{dV_2} \quad (5.48)$$

and so for an arbitrary order one can write

$$P = P_1 \cdots P_m = \left[\prod_{i=1}^m \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_i)}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} |f(\theta_i, \phi_i)| \right] A_{\text{det}} dz_1 \prod_{j=2}^m dV_j. \quad (5.49)$$

So that finally

$$p(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D, t) = A_{\text{det}} \prod_{i=1}^m \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_i)}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} |f(\theta_i, \phi_i)|. \quad (5.50)$$

5.4.5. Final formulation

Now we can insert (5.50) into (5.40) get

$$\frac{dD_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} = A_{\text{det}} \prod_{k=1}^m \int d^3\mathbf{r}_k j_0(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1) \prod_{i=1}^m \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_i)}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} |f(\theta_i, \phi_i)| \Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D). \quad (5.51)$$

The current density j_0 is just the particle density times the speed of light:

$$j_0(\mathbf{r}, t) = cN_{\text{am}}h(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \sqrt{g}(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (5.52)$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dD_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} &= \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \prod_{k=1}^m \int d^3\mathbf{r}_k \sqrt{g(\mathbf{r}_1, t_1)} \times \\ &\quad \prod_{i=1}^m \frac{n(\mathbf{r}_i, t_i)}{|\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i|} |f(\theta_i, \phi_i)| \Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D) . \end{aligned} \quad (5.53)$$

The phase term $\Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_D)$ is, following (5.36), equal $e^{ik(\sum_i |\mathbf{r}_D - \mathbf{r}_i| + z_1)}$, where the sum in the exponent bracket is just the total travelled distance.

A comparison with equation (5.15) reveals that

$$\frac{dD_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} = \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \Psi_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t) . \quad (5.54)$$

This is also valid for $m = 0$ since

$$\frac{dD_0(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} = j_0(\mathbf{r}_d, t) A_{\text{det}} e^{ikz_D} = \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \underbrace{\sqrt{g(\mathbf{r}_d, t)} e^{ikz_D}}_{\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}_d, t)} . \quad (5.55)$$

One can simply add the contributions from all orders and get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dD(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} &= \sum_{i=0}^m \frac{dD_i(\mathbf{r}_D, t)}{dt} \\ &= \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \sum_{i=0}^m \Psi_m(\mathbf{r}_D, t) \\ &= \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \Psi(\mathbf{r}_D, t) . \end{aligned} \quad (5.56)$$

Now, we integrate over some detection time t_{det} and get

$$D(\mathbf{r}_D, t) = \frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \int_0^{t_{\text{det}}} \Psi(\mathbf{r}_D, t') dt' . \quad (5.57)$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} |D(\mathbf{r}_D, t)|^2 &= \left(\frac{c\sqrt{N_0}A_{\text{det}}}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ps}}V_{\text{ref}}}} \right)^2 \left| \int_0^{t_{\text{det}}} \Psi(\mathbf{r}_D, t') dt' \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{cA_{\text{det}}^2 t_{\text{det}}^2}{\hbar\omega V_{\text{ref}}} I_{t_{\text{det}}}(\mathbf{r}_d, t) \end{aligned} \quad (5.58)$$

and the energy accumulated over t_{det} within one detector cell (ij) at \mathbf{r}_D is

$$\mathcal{E}_{ij} = A_{\text{det}} t_{\text{det}} I_{t_{\text{det}}}(\mathbf{r}_D, t) = \frac{\hbar\omega V_{\text{ref}}}{cA_{\text{det}} t_{\text{det}}} |D(\mathbf{r}_D, t)|^2 . \quad (5.59)$$

Please note, in the implementation the division by $\frac{c(t-t_{\text{last}})+d}{l_0}$ at detection was not yet included. This is not a problem as long as we can approximate the distance $c(t-t_{\text{last}})+d$ with a one common detector distance d_0 . In that case one just needs to remember to divide the detector output by it. This will be changed before the implementation will be merged into the PICongGPU mainline.

6. Implementation details

6.1. Overview

The section below describes implementation of the developed functionality. The goal was to model radiation transport in the particle picture. For that, one needs to be able to create new particles, propagate them, modify them with a certain probability, calculate their contributions to detector values, and finally delete particles once they leave the simulation. Figure 6.1 is an example of how these different parts come together to enable a synthetic SAXS probing experiment. The propagation and deletion was already included in PIConGPU, the other components are new and will be the matter of this section.

Figure 6.1.: Small Angle X-ray Scattering synthetic experiment overview. The incoming probing XFEL beam is discretized into amplitudons that are spawned at the simulation boundary. The particles are propagated on each step and can change their direction due to scattering on electron density. At the end the amplitudons are propagated to a planar detector placed behind the simulation box.

6.2. Particle injection

We will start by discussing particle creation. In general, new particles can be either spawned in the simulation volume, due to emission, or be injected at the simulation boundaries to form an inward propagating pulse. The first case has been already partially implemented within the bremsstrahlung

and synchrotron radiation features[52]. Here, the newly developed particle injection at the boundary is presented.

The main idea is to reuse as much as possible of the already present particle creation mechanics, which is used to initialize densities in the simulation initialization phase. This is done with the `CreateDensity` class and the `KernelFillGridWithParticles` kernel. `CreateDensity` combines two functors: A density functor class defines the physical particle number density at any position in the simulation volume. A creation¹ functor class defines how the new macro particles should be positioned within a simulation cell, as well as how many macro particles should be created in each cell. Now, to use this code for injecting particles one needs to make sure that they are only spawned in an outer boundary.

For that purpose, a new creation functor interface `FreeBoundary` was introduced². It ensures that a creation functor is returning a non-zero number of new macro particles, to be created, only within the outermost supercells of the local border — see 3.3 for border definition. This is, in principle, a general interface for running any type of operations restricted to an outer boundary. `FreeBoundary` imposes the restriction only at the super-cell level, a further check in a special creation functor implementation for particle injection (`StartAttributesImpl`) narrows it down to only the outermost cells.

Let us now discuss how exactly the `CreateDensity` algorithm is used. At first, one has to mention that in this implementation the incoming beam can only initially propagate along one of the simulation coordinate axes. In other words, the beam is always at a normal incidence to one of the simulation box sides. With that simplification, the particles need to be created only in one boundary, only at one side of the box.

`CreateDensity` sets particle weightings based on the number of the new macro particles in a cell, and the physical number density given by a density functor. In a scenario where the particles are created time-step after time-step (as the beam enters a simulation) some particles may be still present in the initialization cell while new ones are being created. But, `CreateDensity` will not take into account these older particles when calculating weightings. Consequently, in such situation, the created density would be incorrect. To make sure that this will not happen, the new particles are only spawned within a $c\Delta t$ distance (Δt is the time-step duration) from the boundary (see fig 6.2). Since $c\Delta t$ is the distance photons travel within one step, the new particles will never overlap with the old ones.

The particle position and weighting are not the only attributes that need to be set. When `CreateDensity` is used at the beginning of the simulation the other attributes are only initialized with their default values. Any particle specific modifications are introduced within separate procedures that follow the density creation. In these, the program loops again over all particles, and sets e.g. non-zero momenta according to some initial species temperature. This is not really an option for particle injection. There is no easy way of determining if a given particle was just created and needs initialization or if it was already initialized. Also, the extra computational cost that comes with setting individual attributes in separate, sequentially called, kernels becomes problematic when the procedures need to be called at many time-steps. Because of that, the just mentioned `StartAttributesImpl` creation functor combines a set of sub-functors to initialize all attributes at once. Each sub-functor is responsible for setting one of them. These can be position, momentum, initial phase³, or a polarization angle. A user can choose from different sub-functors available for each attribute and parametrize them, if necessary, in `externalBeam.param`.

¹In `PICongPU` this type of functor is called position functor. I decided to call it differently to differentiate it from a position sub-functor used in this implementation.

²`FreeBoundary` was provided by a fellow developer R. Widera and was not developed by myself.

³The phase is initialized according to formula (5.34)

Figure 6.2: Particle injection at a boundary. New particles are created within a $c\Delta t$ distance from the edge.

In addition to `StartAttributesImpl`, an injection specific density functor was also introduced. This functor(`density::ProbingBeamImpl`) returns density equal to

$$n_{\text{ph}} = \frac{\Phi_{\text{ph}} \Delta t A_{\text{cell}}}{V_{\text{cell}}}, \quad (6.1)$$

where Φ_{ph} is the local photon flux density, A_{cell} is the front facing area of the cell and V_{cell} is the cell volume. This value is reduced in comparison to the physical density $c\Phi_{\text{ph}}$. With this reduction, $n_{\text{ph}}V_{\text{cell}}$ results in a correct total weighting, in the `KernelFillGridWithParticles` algorithm, for the reduced cell (with depth reduced to $c\Delta t$).

The local particle flux density Φ_{ph} at a given time and place is determined by a beam transversal profile, its temporal shape, beam propagation direction, beam transversal offset, and a beam delay. All of these are combined within an implementation already provided by the `xRayScattering` plugin (see 1.2). The beam direction is defined by a combination of the side from which the beam is entering the simulation (one can choose from propagation in the \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{y} , \mathbf{z} directions and the 3 reversed directions $(-\mathbf{x}, -\mathbf{y}, -\mathbf{z})$) and a set of yaw and pitch angles to rotate the beam from one of the 6 base orientations (see tab. 6.2). At least for now, when used with this particle injection module, these angles must be set to zero. This, combined with a beam temporal delay, and a transversal offset defines a co-moving beam coordinate system.

The `ProbingBeam` functor from the `xRayScattering` plug-in provides a coordinate transform between the simulation frame and such beam system. It also combines two functors that define beam profile and shape to determine the beam intensity (or amplitude) at any place and time in the simulation box. The value returned by the beam functor is relative, it is equal 1 at the pulse maximum. The actual particle flux density is obtained by a multiplication with a reference value `photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity`, which can be set in `externalBeam.param`.

As just mentioned, this functionality was already included in the plug-in. This implementation only extended the already existing utilities, by e.g. making some functions, previously working only on at run time, also available at compile time.

To summarize, the particles are spawned in a shallow region – $c\Delta t$ max depth – at one of the simulation boundaries. This is done by calling `CreateDensity`, specialized with parametrized `StartAttributesImpl` and `density::ProbingBeamImpl` functors, on each time-step. `PIConGPU` already has an interface for calling procedures at the beginning of each step, the

Figure 6.3.: Simplified representation of the scattering algorithm

`IterationStartPipeline`. So, to enable particle injection, a user needs to place their specialization of `CreateDensity` in that pipeline in `iterationStart.param`.

6.3. Scattering

Once a particle found its way into the simulation volume it should interact with the rest of the simulation. Such interactions are realized within a new simulation `Scattering` stage. It is called on each step for every particle species for that a scatterer was set in `speciesDefinition.param`. Such scatterer is a `c++` class that provides a full description of the desired scattering process; It includes a particle functor implementation for the actual modification of particles, a kernel that should be used for calling this functor, and a list of all required simulation fields.

6.3.1. Directional scattering functor

We will begin with directional scattering, implemented in the `ScatterFunctor` and the `ScatterParticlesKernel`. When called on a particle, the `ScatterFunctor` decides at first if a particle should be scattered by calling a condition sub-functor. If the condition is satisfied, a direction sub-functor is called that sets the new particle direction.

When a particle has a `startPhase` attribute, as it would be in a SAXS set-up, the phase is shifted at this point by π . The reason for this is the phase shift in Thomson scattering mentioned in 2.3.2 that shows up as the $(-1)^m$ factor in (5.16). If desired, the weighting can be divided at this moment by l_0 and multiplied with the distance to the last scattering point; this is one of the algorithm

modifications introduced in ch. 5. For that to happen, a user needs to parametrize their scatterer with l_0 and the particles in the species need to have the `lastEventStep` attribute.

A particle can also have an attribute counting times it was scattered. This can be useful for restricting the scattering order or separating different orders while detecting particles. If this is the case, the counter is advanced here by one.

Direction functor

Now let us discuss the two sub-functors in a bit more detail. The scattering direction functor `Random` samples two angles: an azimuth angle from $\varphi \in [0, 2\pi)$, as well as a polar angle $\theta \in [\theta_{\min}, \theta_{\max})$. These angles describe a new propagation direction in a spherical coordinate system which z axis lays along the old particle momentum. That means, the polar angle θ is the scattering angle, while φ sets the remaining degree of freedom.

The angles are sampled in such a way that in these spherical coordinates the angle pairs result in points uniformly distributed on a unit sphere; or rather a part of the sphere defined by the minimal and maximal polar angles. To achieve such uniform distribution, φ is simply uniformly sampled from $[0, 2\pi)$, while θ is obtained from a uniform variable $u \in [0, 1)$ with

$$\theta = \arccos(u(\cos(\theta_{\min}) - \cos(\theta_{\max})) + \cos(\theta_{\max})) . \quad (6.2)$$

This formula results from an application of the inversion transform sampling method to the underlying distribution function.

Once both angles are sampled, the particle momentum is rotated to the new orientation. Both, this vector rotation, and the angle sampling were taken from the direction functor implementation in `parataxis`[51].

As already mentioned in 2.3.2 such uniform distribution is sufficient for scattering with small angles θ ; as it is the case with SAXS.

Scattering condition

We know from 5.4.4 that a probability to scatter within a time-step Δt is equal to $\frac{c\Delta t}{l_s}$, where l_s is the scattering length. We also recall that $l_s = (n\sigma)^{-1}$, so the probability is proportional to the local scatterer density n . n is passed to a condition functor by the scatterer functor, the proportionality factor $a = c\Delta t\sigma$ can be calculated beforehand with

$$a = c\Delta t \cdot \sigma_{\Omega} = c\Delta t \cdot l_0 \int_{\Omega} |f(\theta, \phi)| \quad (6.3)$$

for amplitudons, or from

$$a = c\Delta t \cdot \sigma_{\Omega} = c\Delta t \cdot \int_{\Omega} |f(\theta, \phi)|^2 \quad (6.4)$$

for photons, and set in `scattering.param`. Here, Ω is the solid angle defined by the minimal and maximal values for the scattering angles φ and θ . The functor returns true with the correct probability by generating a uniformly distributed random variable u , between 0 and 1, and returning the truth value of $u < an$.

Such scattering condition can be achieved with the `ProbLinToDens` condition functor. Beside it, the implementation also provides an `Always` functor that always returns `true` and `Threshold` for scattering condition based on a scatterer density threshold. Additionally, all condition functors can impose a scattering order limit. There is also an alternative version of `ProbLinToDens` called `RandomThomson` in that the factor $c\Delta t$ is already included so that the value that needs to be set is σ_Ω and not a ; this functor was used in the simulation set-ups in ch. 8. In the end, one should decide for just one the versions and remove the other one.

Scattering kernel

The parallelization over particles is realized within the `ScatterParticlesKernel`, at least when the `ScatterFunctor` is in use. It is called on every step for all supercells within core and border, that is in the whole local domain.

Before any particles are scattered, the scatterer density is cached in the block shared memory. This allows for quicker access, and is especially beneficial when one expects multiple particles per cell. The kernel can actually be called, thanks to `c++` variadic templates, with an arbitrary number of scatterer densities, for example with both free and bound electron densities. The cached value is then just the sum of all provided fields.

As described in 3.3, each thread is a part of a block and each block corresponds to a supercell with a linked list of frames for each species. In `ScatterParticlesKernel` each virtual thread calls the scattering functor for one particle in a frame. The functor is called with the scatterer density from the particle cell. Frames are kept being processed like that until there are no more frames left, and the functor has been called for all particles from the supercell.

6.3.2. Faraday rotation

Another possible choice for a species scatterer, beside the `ScatterFunctor`, is the `FaradayRotationFunctor` that is called by the `ScatterParticlesWithBFieldKernel`. This kernel is an extended version of the `ScatterParticlesKernel`, where in addition to density also the simulation native B-field is cached in the shared memory. The `FaradayRotationFunctor` is then called on each particle, just like before, with the density value n from the particle cell, and with the B-field interpolated to the particle position.

The actual functor implementation is quite simple and does not involve any sub-functors. The `polarizationAngle` attribute is simply modified by

$$\Delta\alpha = c\Delta t \frac{e^3}{2c\varepsilon_0 m_e^2} \frac{n}{\omega^2} \mathbf{B} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{p}}{|\mathbf{p}|} . \quad (6.5)$$

Here, the angular frequency ω is calculated from the particle (photon or amplitudon) momentum \mathbf{p} . Alternatively, when a species wide wavelength flag is present, ω is pre-calculated from it at compile-time. $\Delta\alpha$ is the change in polarization accumulated over the distance a photon travels in one time-step $c\Delta t$. The equation follows from (2.22) and (2.1).

6.3.3. Providing simulation fields

CallScatterer functor

A scattering kernel is called from within the `Scattering` stage by the `CallScatterer` functor. This functor, beside for running the kernel, is responsible for delivering all simulation fields required by a given scatterer. Different scatterers may require different fields, e.g. only `FaradayRotationFunctor` needs the magnetic field. But in fact, the requirements may differ even for the same scatterer from set-up to set-up. This would be, for example, the case when one would need to combine scattering densities from different species. Also, in the future, some other implementation, e.g. thermal absorption, may need some other variables, such as a temperature.

The goal was to avoid hard-coding multiple kernel call implementations, that is writing a separate but very similar code for each and every case, while at the same time enabling maximal flexibility. This showed to be quite challenging, especially because the calculation of derived field quantities involves a lot of meta-programming so a major part of it has to be done at compile-time. In the end, calls to operations that calculate fields derived from particle data (such as number densities) were put in compile-time loops, created with a help of `std::index_sequence` and pack expansions.

After calling the kernel, the `fillAllGaps` method of the scattered species class can be called. This method removes any gaps in the particle frames. Such gaps may occur e.g. when particles are deleted. The need for this operation is defined in a scatterer class.

Combined-derived fields

In `PIConGPU` fields such as number, charge, or energy densities are calculated as a sum of weighted contributions from individual particles. But, not all quantities can be derived like this. One example would be an electron density for Faraday Rotation calculation that has been already multiplied with the relativistic correction $\langle \gamma \rangle^{-2}$. One can not simply calculate this as sum of every particle's w/γ^2 value simply because $\langle \gamma^{-2} \rangle$ is not the same as $\langle \gamma \rangle^{-2}$.

This motivated a new feature, developed as a part of this thesis, that is a combined-derived attribute. It can be used to calculate quantities that are a function of two already available simple derived attributes. A combined-derived attribute definition consists of a list of the two simple attributes, a binary operation that should be used to compute the result, and a description class that provides a name and an SI unit for the combined attribute. So for example, a `RelativisticDensity` attribute that calculates the just mentioned relativistically corrected density, for Faraday Rotation, is defined like follows:

```
1   using RelativisticDensity = CombinedDeriveAttribute<
2       particleToGrid::derivedAttributes::Density,
3       particleToGrid::derivedAttributes::EnergyDensity,
4       RelativisticDensityOperation,
5       RelativisticDensityDescription>;
```

where the `RelativisticDensityOperation` functor calculates $n \langle \gamma \rangle^{-2}$, with $\langle \gamma \rangle$ obtained from the

number density n and the energy density ε with

$$\langle \gamma \rangle = \frac{1}{mc^2} \frac{\varepsilon}{n} + 1 . \quad (6.6)$$

With this feature there is no need to implement a relativistic correction directly in the Faraday Rotation functor. Such derived attributes can be used in the same way as the simple attributes anywhere in the code, e.g. they can be included in the simulation output as easily as any of the previously available fields.

6.3.4. Particle splitting

There are many methods of variance reduction in Monte Carlo radiation transport simulations[74]. One of them is particle splitting. On each event, such as scattering, a particle may be split into a certain number of new particles, and the event outcome, such as scattering angle, is individually determined for each one of them. This allows us to concentrate the computational resources on sampling the spherical wave coming from each scattering point, rather than on the positions of such points.

A particle splitting algorithm was introduced with the `SplitScatterer` and the `SplitAndScatterParticles` kernel. This implementation builds up on the `ScattererFunctor` and its kernel. The new scatterer does not provide its functionality in a single call operator, as it is usual with `c++` functors, instead it scatters it among a few methods with the following signatures:

```
SplitScatterer
├─ bool scatteringCondition(particle, density)
├─ bool splittingCondition(particle)
├─ void scatterSingle(particle)
├─ void split(id, sourceParticle, newParticle)
└─ void afterSplit(sourceParticle)
```

After caching the density data as usual the kernel loops over all particles that are present in a supercell. For each particle it calls the `scatteringCondition` method of the scatterer functor to decide if the particle should be scattered or not. Then, if this is the case, the splitting condition method is called. If the particle needs to be scattered, but it is not supposed to be split, `scatterSingle`, which is in principle just the normal scattering operator from the `ScatterFunctor`, is called for the particle. If, on the other hand, `splittingCondition` returns `true`, the particle is marked for splitting. All particles in `PICongPU` have the `multiMask` attribute that is used for marking particles. The kernel makes a use of it and sets it to 50, an arbitrary value that is not used in any other context. Furthermore, at this moment a variable that counts the number of particles to split is advanced by one. Each thread has its own counter to avoid racing conditions and at the end of the particle loop this individual thread counters are reduced on a single shared counter by an atomic add operation.

Now, once the number of particle to split is known, the master thread⁴ creates (if there is not enough place in the last frame) enough new frames to accommodate for the new particles. The number of required new slots is just the number of particles to split times the number of new particles created on each split (N_{new}), which is a template argument of the `SplitScatter` and can be set in `scattering.param`.

⁴The thread with index 0, which is used for operations that are not run in parallel.

Everything until now was, in a sense, just a preparation for the actual splitting. Now, the kernel loops once again over all particles. A thread that happens to be processing a marked particle will follow the following steps: At first, the mark is removed, as it is not needed any more. To proceed, the kernel needs to know at what position in the particle storage it is supposed to save the new particles coming from this particular split. Because of that, each marked particle is assigned an index (`memoryDestinationBlock`) by advancing, with an atomic add operation, a `countSplittedParticles` counter in the shared memory. With that, the position in memory for each of the new N_{new} particles is known and `SplitScatterer::split` is called for each of the new particles.

In `split` the weighting of the new particle is set to the value from the source particle divided by $N_{\text{new}} + 1$ since with a creation of N_{new} new particles one is splitting the old particle into $N_{\text{new}} + 1$. Then, all the other attributes are copied from the source to the new particle. After that, `scatterSingle` is called on the new particle. At the end, if a particle has a `generation` attribute, it is advanced by one. (This attribute can be used e.g. to limit splitting to a certain generation while letting the scattering order unrestricted)

Finally, after `split` has been called on all N_{new} child particles, the `afterSplit` method is applied to the source particle. In there, it is scattered with `scatterSingle` and its weighting is also divided by $N_{\text{new}} + 1$.

The kernel ends, once all old particles have been checked for the `multiMask=50` mark and split if needed.

6.4. Detection

6.4.1. PhotonDetector plugin

The particle detection was introduced as a new PIconGPU `photonDetector` plug-in. The plug-in system provides additional functionalities, such as the simulation I/O interface, that can be enabled, and to a large extent configured, via run-time command line options.

The detector is a species specific extension. That means, it can be individually turned on and off for each of the simulated particle species. Once a particle from a species with an active detector leaves the simulation, a ray-tracing algorithm checks if it will reach any of the detector cells. If this is the case, some value that can be derived from the particle attributes is accumulated in the detector cell, by one of the available policies.

`photonDetector` is a planar detector and so it complements the already present spherical calorimeter plug-in. For now, it can be only placed, in some distance, parallel to one of the box sides, in such a way that the middle of the detector lays directly in front of the simulation box centre. However, support for arbitrary placements and orientations could be added later by extending the ray-tracing algorithm.

The detector data can be written to disk, or streamed to another application, at any time during the simulation. This I/O functionality was implemented, in the `PhotonDetectorWriter` class, using the `openPMD-api`[79]. This API is a library that enables parallel data handling (data following the openPMD naming and meta-data scheme) with such backends as ADIOS, HDF5 and JSON. After writing data, detector values are zeroed to avoid unnecessary numerical errors, which can occur

when small values are added to large numbers.

The table 6.1 shows all the plug-in run-time options, and an example compile-time configuration is shown in listing 6.2. It is possible to define a list of such compile-time set-ups in `photonDetector.param` and the `PICongPU` plug-in controller will create individual plug-ins for each of the provided configurations (see listing 6.1). Besides, `photonDetector` is a so-called multi plug-in. For such extensions it is possible to enable multiple instances, with different run-time options, at the same time. With that, one can run simulations with multiple detectors that can have any combination of the run and compile-time options.

```
1 struct NonSpecializedPhotonDetector
2 {
3     template<typename T_DetectorConfig, typename T_Species>
4     struct apply
5     {
6         using type = plugins::multi::Master<
7             plugins::photonDetector::PhotonDetector<
8                 T_DetectorConfig, T_Species >>;
9     };
10 };
11
12 template<typename T_Config>
13 struct AssignDetectorConfig : bmpl::apply2<NonSpecializedPhotonDetector, T_Config,
14     ↪ bmpl::_1>
15 {
16 };
17 using UnspecializedSpeciesPhotonDetectorPlugins = typename bmpl::
18 transform<plugins::photonDetector::SeqAllDetectorConfigs,
19     ↪ AssignDetectorConfig<bmpl::_1>>::type;
```

Listing 6.1: Generation of partially specialized photon detector plug-ins in `PluginController` from a list of configurations, with the use of the meta-programming library `boost::mpl`. The full specialization including the particle species class is done later together with the remaining species plug-ins.

6.4.2. Particle detection

A part of the plug-in is a detector implementation class `PhotonDetectorImpl`, adopted from `parataxis`. It provides detector storage, on both device and host side, and a particle functor `DetectParticle` used in the `DetectParticles` kernel. This kernel is called on each iteration in the guard region at the outer simulation boundary for particles of the plug-in species. The only situation in `PICongPU` when a particle can find itself in guard is when it's either moving to the next gpu or it is leaving the simulation. So it is enough for the `DetectParticles` kernel to simply loop over all particles in the region. The kernel calls on each particle the `DetectParticle` functor, provided by `PhotonDetectorImpl`. This functor checks if the particle, with its current position and momentum, will hit the detector and, if so, which cell. This check is done by the ray tracing functor `GetTargetCellIdx`.

Table 6.1.: All available `photonDetector` plug-in run-time parameters.

setting	description
<code>period</code>	Defines time-steps at which the plug-in is enabled ¹ .
<code>size.x</code>	Detector size in x direction ² , in cells.
<code>size.y</code>	Detector size in y direction ² , in cells.
<code>placement</code>	Simulation box side behind which the detector is placed. Valid values are: <code>x-</code> , <code>x+</code> , <code>y</code> , <code>y+</code> , <code>z-</code> , <code>z+</code> . ³
<code>outputDir</code>	Subdirectory name for storing the detector output.
<code>fileName</code>	Output file name prefix.
<code>infix</code>	<code>openPMD-api</code> file name infix. Determines if iterations are stored in separate files or not, and how the files are numbered.
<code>ext</code>	<code>openPMD-api</code> file name extension that determines the used backend.
<code>json</code>	Advanced (backend) configuration for <code>openPMD-api</code> in JSON format.

¹ In the `PICongPU` period notation.

² In the detector coordinate system.

³ For example `'x-'` is a placement on the x axis in front of the box, when looking towards the positive x direction. While, `'x+'` would be on the same axis but behind the box.

Figure 6.4.: Simplified representation of the detection algorithm

```

1 struct PhotonDetectorConfig
2 {
3     /* Accumulation policy
4      * Policy that defines how the detector handles incoming particles
5      * Possible values:
6      * - particleHandlers::CountParticles
7      * - particleHandlers::CountMacroParticles
8      * - particleHandlers::AddWaveParticles
9      * - particleHandlers::AmplitudeWithPolarization
10     */
11     using AccumulationPolicy = particleHandlers::AddWaveParticles;
12
13     // Only accumulate particle satisfying this particle filter:
14     using ParticleFilter = particles::filter::Scattered;
15
16     /**
17      * Distance between the detector and the simulation edge.
18      * Unit: meter
19     */
20     static constexpr float_64 distance = 5.0;
21     /**
22      * Width and height of each detector cell
23      * Unit: meter
24     */
25     static constexpr float_64 cellWidth = 200 * 1.0e-6;
26     static constexpr float_64 cellHeight = 200 * 1.0e-6;
27
28     // configuration name used in a plug-in prefix
29     static std::string getName()
30     {
31         return "AddWaveParticlesCfg";
32     }
33 };
34 constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig::distance;
35 constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig::cellWidth;
36 constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig::cellHeight;

```

Listing 6.2: An example for a `photonDetector` compile-time configuration.

Ray tracing

At first the particle momentum, cell index and in-cell position are translated into the detector coordinate system. This system is oriented just like a beam system (from `xrayScattering`) for a beam propagating directly at the detector. That means, the z component is pointing from the simulation at the detector, while the x and y axes are in the detector plane. This is supposed to be a right-hand system and that is why, with this choice of z , x is the vertical and not the horizontal axis — see fig. 6.5, also see tab. 6.2 for the relations between beam coordinate systems and the simulation system. This coordinate system equivalence makes it possible to reuse, for these transformations, routines from the `xrayScattering` plug-in, and the particle injection implementation.

If the particle's z momentum component (in the beam system) is above zero, and so the particle moves towards the hemisphere with the detector in it, the detector cell index is calculated. At first

Figure 6.5.: Detector coordinates

as

$$\begin{aligned} i_x &= \text{atan2}(p_x, p_z) / \Delta\theta_x \\ i_y &= \text{atan2}(p_y, p_z) / \Delta\theta_y . \end{aligned} \quad (6.7)$$

Here, it is assumed that each detector cell covers the same angular range of

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\theta_x &= \text{atan}\left(\frac{\Delta x}{d}\right) \\ \Delta\theta_y &= \text{atan}\left(\frac{\Delta y}{d}\right) , \end{aligned} \quad (6.8)$$

where Δx and Δy are respectively the detector cell height and width, and d is the detector distance. This assumption is valid only when the detector distance is large enough, like it is in a SAXS set-up, or when $\mathbf{p} = p_z$. The later would be a case, e.g., in a polarimetry set-up, at least as long as Faraday Rotation was not combined with directional scattering.

After that, the index is offset by particle position

$$\begin{aligned} i_x &= i_x + \left(i_{\text{sim},x} - \frac{s_x}{2}\right) \cdot \Delta x_{\text{sim}} \\ i_y &= i_y + \left(i_{\text{sim},y} - \frac{s_y}{2}\right) \cdot \Delta y_{\text{sim}} . \end{aligned} \quad (6.9)$$

Here, \mathbf{i}_{sim} is the simulation cell index in the detector coordinates, \mathbf{s} is the simulation box size in cells, and Δx_{sim} and Δy_{sim} are the simulation cell dimensions. Just like it was already done in `parataxis`, the last addition is performed with stripping the integral part of \mathbf{i} beforehand, and adding it afterwards. This helps to avoid a floating point addition error that can occur when the angle based contribution is much larger as the one coming from particle position.

At the end, \mathbf{i} is rounded down to an integer value and shifted by the half of the detector size (so that $\mathbf{i} = (0, 0)$ lays in the centre). If the index is within the detector bounds, the `DetectParticle` will follow by calling the chosen accumulation functor for this particle, and the just determined detector cell.

6.4.3. Accumulation policies

A contribution to a detector cell value from a particle that was found to hit this cell by the ray tracing algorithm is determined by an accumulation policy. So far there are 4 policies

available: `AddWaveParticles` meant for SAXS set-ups, `AmplitudeWithPolarization` for polarimetry, `CountParticles` for simply summing the weighting of particles reaching a given cell and `CountMacroparticles` for counting macro particles. The last two are quite self-explanatory, so the remaining part of this section discusses only the other two.

AddWaveParticles

This policy follows the formula 5.33 to add complex amplitudes of incoming amplitudons. One assumes here that all amplitudons have the same linear polarization hence the amplitude is not a vector but simply a complex number. Like already mentioned in ch. 5 the amplitude magnitude is just the particle weighting, and the particle phase is calculated according to formula 5.35. The initial phase ϕ_0 is a particle attribute and can be directly accessed, it was assigned to the particle at its initialization. The $-\omega t_f$ term is either pre-calculated at every simulation step, when a species has the common `wavelength` flag, or it is calculated individually for each particle, when a species is not set to be monochromatic.

The calculation of the kd term is a bit less straight-forward. It follows the technique developed in [51] that minimizes the numerical uncertainties by calculating the phase as an offset to the phase accumulated along a reference ray (with length d_{ref}) connecting the middle of the outer simulation boundary with the centre of the detector cell. The figure 6.6 shows that the difference Δd between the two rays — the reference ray and the one starting at the particle position — is equal to the projection of the particle position offset vector $\Delta \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0$ on the reference beam direction $\hat{\mathbf{l}}_{\text{ref}}$. So that

$$kd = kd_{\text{ref}} + k\Delta d = kd_{\text{ref}} + k(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{l}}_{\text{ref}}. \quad (6.10)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{l}}_{\text{ref}}$ is calculated as $\mathbf{l}_{\text{ref}}/|\mathbf{l}_{\text{ref}}|$, with $\mathbf{l}_{\text{ref}} = (\tan(i_x \Delta \theta_x), \tan(i_y \Delta \theta_y), 1)$. This is again only valid for a detector in a far enough distance.

Figure 6.6.: Calculating phase with a reference ray. Δd is the difference in distance to the detector cell from the particle position and from the centre of the simulation nearest outer boundary.

For now, the kd_{ref} term was left out from the computation. It was not included in the `parataxis`

implementation on the grounds that it is just a constant phase offset per cell that can be calculated at later times, if necessary; and, as long as one is interested in the squared value — intensity — the constant phase offset will cancel itself out anyway. The problem with that, is that the `PIConGPU` implementation should also work for polychromatic radiation. In such a case k , and so kd_{ref} , needs to be calculated individually for each particle. This means that `AddWavesParticles` is not yet fully ready for polychromatic set-ups; however, this can be easily changed.

AmplitudeWithPolarization

This accumulation policy is meant for polarimetry simulations. Obviously, one can here no longer assume that all incoming particles will be identically polarized; for that reason, the detector value is now a vector with two amplitude components. On the other hand, in a simple polarimetry set-up where all particles come from the same source and are just transmitted along a straight line one can assume that all of them are in phase. Because of that, with this policy the phase calculation is left out and the amplitude components are stored as plain real numbers. This saves some computational complexity and memory usage. For some more elaborate set-ups, e.g. combining Faraday Rotation with directional scattering, one would need a more general solution that would combine the features from `AmplitudeWithPolarization` and `AddWaveParticles`.

The amplitude magnitude A is, also here, the particle weighting w . It is projected on the x and y axis to give the individual components:

$$\begin{aligned} A_x &= w \sin(\alpha) \\ A_y &= w \cos(\alpha) \end{aligned} \tag{6.11}$$

Here, the angle α is just the particle `polarizationAngle` attribute so that it is implicitly assumed that for `polarizationAngle = 0` the radiation is polarized in the detector y direction — see fig.6.7. This is only o.k. as long as the detector coordinate system is oriented in the same way as the beam system that was used on the initialization. This is certainly the case for such simple, purely transmissive, polarimetry set-ups. Nevertheless, also this part of the implementation still needs to be generalized. The simplest way to do that would be to replace `polarizationAngle` with a polarization vector $\vec{\epsilon}$, but this would mean storing two float values more per particle. Since $|\vec{\epsilon}| = 1$ is known, one could also think about storing just two components together with the sign of the third one.

Figure 6.7.: Polarization angle at a detector

Table 6.2.: Relation between different beam (or detector) coordinate systems and the simulation coordinates, listed for all six possible **Side** choices for particle injection and the six equivalent detector placements.

Side	detector placement	beam(detector) system	simulation system
XSide	x+	x	-z
		y	y
		z	x
XRSide	x-	x	-z
		y	-y
		z	-x
YSide	y+	x	-z
		y	-x
		z	y
YRSide	y-	x	-z
		y	x
		z	-y
ZSide	z+	x	-y
		y	x
		z	z
ZRSide	z-	x	-y
		y	-x
		z	-z

7. Tests

7.1. Double-slit

To verify the functionality related to coherent diffraction a test simulation with a double-slit like density profile was performed. To be more exact, the used density profile was an inverted double-slit aperture; that means, in the whole volume expect for two strips in the middle the electron density was set to zero. The reasoning behind it, is that radiation in a diffraction experiment would come only from the two slits and so one wants the particles to only scatter in this region; and not from everywhere else.

This density was realized in a 128x64x64 cells simulation box with the two stripes in the middle, separated by 11 cells, 3 cells wide and 5 cells deep; the cell side length was 4 nm — see fig. 7.6. The density is made up of +1 cooper ions and the corresponding free electrons, though this could be realized with any other species mix that would result in the same electron density distribution.

The probing beam had a constant transversal and temporal form (a plane wave), and it propagated along the z axis; the wavelength was set via the species flag, identical for all particles, to $\lambda = 0.1$ nm. In the first set-up, 216 macro amplitudons were spawned in each boundary cell at every iteration; in the second simulation it were 18, but the particles were split in 12 on a scattering event. In both set-ups, the scattering condition was a density > 0 threshold so that all particles that reach one of the slits were immediately scattered. The scattering was limited to the first order, hence all particles were scattered within the first layer of the non-zero density cells.

This gives, for the simulation without splitting, $128 \cdot 64 \cdot 216 = 1769472$ new particles at each time step. After the first amplitudons reach the other side of the simulation box, there is an equal amount of them leaving on the other side. So, the total amount of probing particles in the simulation will reach and stay at around $128 \cdot 64 \cdot 111 \cdot 216 = 196411392 = 2.0 \cdot 10^8$, here 111 is the amount of time-steps that a particle moving with the speed of light needs to cross the 64 cell deep simulation box. As one can see from fig. 7.4, this estimated number agrees with the one obtained from the simulation output; the number of total particles in the split set-up is accordingly smaller.

An `AddWaveParticles` detector was placed behind the simulation box, in a 5m distance, in the particle propagation direction. The 1024x1024 cells large detector, with 200 μm wide and 200 μm high cells, resulted in a maximal detected scattering angle of approximately 0.028 rad. The maximum angle in the scattering direction functor was set to 0.03 rad, just slightly higher than the detection limit.

The detector was only accumulating scattered particles so that the not scattered amplitudons, the one passing next to the slits, were ignored. Considering just the set-up geometry, around 60% of the scattered particles should hit the detector. That results, for the first set-up, in approximately = $128 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 216 \cdot 0.6 = 1 \cdot 10^5$ amplitudons accumulated on the whole detector per time step. Since $12 \cdot 18$ is again 216, one expects approximately the same number for the second simulation. And in fact, this value agrees with what was measured with a `CountMacroParticles` detector in both

simulations.

The complex valued detector output was squared and normalized (divided by the average value of three cells from the middle of the $\theta_x = 0$ line). The fig. 7.1 shows the detector images from both set-ups after 1000, 10'000, and 60'000 steps. The average number of detected macro particles per detector cell was (83 ± 18) after 1000, (927 ± 60) after 10'000, and (5613 ± 152) after 60'000 steps; these values turned out to be the same in both set-ups.

Fig. 7.2 and 7.3 show, for the first and second simulation, detector line-outs on the detector y-axis. These values were compared with the expected double-slit intensity[80] calculated from

$$I(\theta) = I_0 \cos(\pi(d/\lambda) \sin \theta) \operatorname{sinc}((b/\lambda) \sin \theta) , \quad (7.1)$$

where I_0 is the intensity for $\theta = 0$, $d = 11 \cdot 4 \text{ nm}$ is the slit distance, $b = 3 \cdot 4 \text{ nm}$ is the slit width, and sinc is the normalized version of the sinc function.

As one can see from these figures, and the calculated mean squared error shown in figure 7.5, the simulated intensity is clearly converging against the expected theoretical value. With that, the first simulation successfully reproduced a similar test case from [51]. Comparing the two set-ups, it can be seen that the newly introduced particle splitting algorithm leads to the same results while requiring much less computational resources. In summary, this results show that this implementation can be successfully used to calculate coherent scattering, at least up to the first scattering order.

7.2. Faraday Rotation

In addition to the just presented double-slit set-ups, another set of test simulations was run to verify the Faraday Rotation related part of the implementation. In these simulations, a plane wave particle beam, with $\lambda = 0.1 \text{ nm}$, was propagated in a straight line through a temporally constant but spatially inhomogeneous distribution of electron density and magnetic field. The probing species had the `FaradayRotationFunc`tor enabled as their scatterer.

The density was equal to $1 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-3}$ multiplied by a sum of four gaussians

$$g(\mathbf{x}, \vec{\mu}, \vec{\sigma}) = \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(x_1 - \mu_1)^2}{\sigma_1^2} + \frac{(x_2 - \mu_2)^2}{\sigma_2^2} + \frac{(x_3 - \mu_3)^2}{\sigma_3^2} \right) \right] \quad (7.2)$$

with $\vec{\mu}_1 = (10, 30, 230)$, $\vec{\mu}_2 = (30, 60, 120)$, $\vec{\mu}_3 = (49, 78, 68)$, $\vec{\mu}_4 = (32, 64, 128)$ and $\vec{\sigma}_1 = (10, 50, 120)$, $\vec{\sigma}_2 = (20, 70, 60)$, $\vec{\sigma}_3 = (45, 23, 44)$, $\vec{\sigma}_4 = (15, 15, 15)$. The $\vec{\mu}$ and $\vec{\sigma}$ values are given in simulation cells. The magnetic field, on the other hand, was equal to $\mathbf{B} = (2B_0, B_0, (1/2)B_0)$, with $B_0 = (a - 1) \cdot 1 \cdot 10^9 \text{ T}$. Here, a is also a sum of gaussians with $\vec{\mu}_1 = (35, 90, 40)$, $\vec{\mu}_2 = (48, 80, 10)$, $\vec{\mu}_3 = (12, 120, 23)$, $\vec{\mu}_4 = (32, 64, 128)$ and $\vec{\sigma}_1 = (50, 14, 250)$, $\vec{\sigma}_2 = (84, 90, 65)$, $\vec{\sigma}_3 = (24, 178, 99)$, $\vec{\sigma}_4 = (15, 15, 15)$.

The particles propagated along the z axis, and were caught on a polarimetry detector placed behind the simulation volume. The detector cell size and the number of cells were chosen to exactly match the cells at the simulation rear side so that the transmitted intensity is measured with the simulation resolution. The initial value of `polarizationAngle` was zero for all particles; therefore, the polarization angle rotation could be obtained from the measured amplitude components by $\alpha = \operatorname{atan} 2(A_x, A_y)$.

Figure 7.1.: Relative intensity from the double-slit test simulations. On the left side are the results from the simulation without particle splitting. The right-hand side shows the results from a particle splitting set-up. The values directly above the images are the mean number of already accumulated macro particles per detector cell.

double slit intensity on the $\theta_x^{det} = 0$ row. I_0 is averaged over 3 middle cells, no split

Figure 7.2.: The figure shows an intensity line-out, from the double-slit simulation without splitting, at the detector $\theta_x = 0$ line. The values are normalized by the average value of three cells from the centre of the line-out. The solid line shows the expected theoretical values.

double slit intensity on the $\theta_x^{det} = 0$ row. I_0 is averaged over 3 middle cells, split

Figure 7.3.: The figure shows an intensity line-out, from the double-slit simulation with splitting, at the detector $\theta_x = 0$ line. The values are normalized by the average value of three cells from the centre of the line-out. The solid line shows the expected theoretical values.

Figure 7.4.: The total number of amplitudons in the simulation box at a given time-step for both double-slit test set-ups.

Reference values were calculated in python by integrating the formula (2.22). The fig. 7.7 shows, next to each other, the results from both PICongGPU and the python script; the absolute value of the relative error between the two can be found in fig. 7.9a.

A simulation with the same density profile but a constant magnetic field, equal to $1 \cdot 10^9$ T, was run as well; the results can be seen in fig. 7.8 and fig. 7.9b. In addition, the same set-up was run with a homogenous density $1 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and a homogenous $1 \cdot 10^{29}$ T magnetic field; in that case, the calculated rotation was approximately equal to $1.34594 \cdot 10^{-4}$ rad with a maximal relative error of $9 \cdot 10^{-9}$ rad.

The relative error in 7.9a and 7.9b is at some points quite high, this can be most likely explained by some small differences in sampling, field calculation, and (in the case of the magnetic field in PICongGPU) also interpolation. In some parts of the output from the first run, the uncertainty (in fig.

Figure 7.5.: The mean squared error for the values along the $\theta_x = 0$ line-out, The x axis is the mean number of accumulated macro particles per detector cell, from both double-slit test set-ups.

Figure 7.6.: Density profile from double-slit tests

7.9a) becomes very large, but this happens only in the region where the result changes its sign and one can expect high relative errors for near zero values. In total, these tests do not give any reason to suspect an error in the implementation. Especially when looking at the quite exact result in the homogenous case, one can quite confidently state that the Faraday Rotation calculation works as expected.

Figure 7.7.: Faraday Rotation in-situ test. Static, non-homogenous density and magnetic field resulting in a Faraday Rotation.

Figure 7.8.: Faraday Rotation in-situ test. Static, non-homogenous density and a constant magnetic field resulting in a Faraday Rotation.

Figure 7.9.: Relative error (absolute value) in the Faraday Rotation in-situ tests.

8. Particle In Cell Simulations

8.1. Aluminium foil simulation with Faraday Rotation calculation

As I started working on my thesis, before I began to work on the radiation transport module, a three-dimensional aluminium foil simulation with visible electron density and magnetic field filamentation was run. The simulation was a part of preparations for ongoing XFEL polarimetry experiments. The simulation output was used to calculate Faraday Rotation in post-processing, similarly to how it was done in my bachelor thesis[30]. This section will describe the set-up of this simulation, and some aspects of the simulation outcome.

8.1.1. Simulation set-up

We will start by listing a few simulation parameters. The simulation box was 1344 x 1760 x 1334 cells large, with a cell size of $\Delta x = 7.142857$ nm; this translates to around 12.6 μm in the laser propagation direction (simulation y-axis) and 9.6 μm in both transversal directions. Two constraints played a role in the choice of this Δx value. Firstly, the simulation grid resolution had to be good enough to properly resolve the electron plasma wavelength

$$\lambda_p = \sqrt{\frac{n_e e^2}{m_e \epsilon_0}}. \quad (8.1)$$

With the maximal electron density estimated by three times the free electron density of fully ionized aluminium and minimum three cells per plasma wavelength one gets the first condition $\Delta x \lesssim 7.3$ nm. The second constraint was that the simulation box transversal size should be divisible by the laser wavelength ($\lambda_L = 800$ nm); this helps to avoid unwanted artefacts that may come from the choice of periodic boundary conditions. In principle, with such a large simulation volume it should be possible to use absorbing boundary conditions; but, test runs with a Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) field absorber lead to significant field artefacts at the simulation boundary, so a decision was made to use the periodic option instead. Today, PICongPU offers some more settings that could have helped with such artefacts, but these were not available at the time. One should note here, that in the laser propagation direction (y) the PMLs are still used.

The aluminium foil was 5 μm thick and stretched from $y=4$ μm to $y=9$ μm . In front of it was an exponentially decaying pre-plasma with a 150 nm scale length; the pre-plasma was cut-off at a 1050 nm distance from the foil surface, shortly after the density dropped under the laser critical density. Such pre-plasma is supposed to model pre-expansion caused by laser intensity preceding the simulated main pulse. The scale-length choice was based on a series of two-dimensional test simulations, with an aim to optimize for maximal build up of in-bulk filaments. This density distribution was initialized with one ion particle per simulation cell. The choice of such, very low, resolution was dictated by the size of the used computational system; a simulation with a higher number of particles per cell would not fit in the memory of the available GPUs.

The pump laser strength was set to

$$a_0 = \left(\frac{2e^2 \lambda_L I}{\pi m_e^2 c^5} \right)^{1/2} = 35 \quad , \text{ with } I - \text{ the peak intensity.}$$

The laser was introduced as a 30 fs long Gaussian pulse; transversally a Gaussian beam with a 3 μm beam waist (FWHM), and its focal spot at the foil front surface (4 μm). The laser intensity started at 60 fs before the pulse maximum and disappeared 60 fs after it. The laser was linearly polarized along the z-axis.

The aluminium ions were initialized in a pre-ionized 3+ charge state. This initial ionization state was estimated by a python tool provided in the `PICongGPU` documentation. Fig. 8.1 shows that the expected dominating ionization state for the used laser pulse at -60 fs is the chosen 3+ state, according to both the ADK[81] and BSI (Barrier Suppression Ionization) models.

8.1.2. Writing simulation output

The simulation output was meant to be used in a Faraday Rotation calculation. As we know from section 2.3.3, this requires at least the magnetic field and the electron density. In here, a relativistic correction factor $\langle \gamma \rangle^{-2}$ should also be included. Average γ depends on electron temperature, so one also needs to save the electron kinetic energy density. One can not expect all electrons to have the same temperature, hence the electron density and energy were written separately for three electron subpopulations: cold electrons with $\gamma < 1.5$, warm electrons with $1.5 \leq \gamma < 4$, and a hot electron population with γ above 4. In addition to this, the bound electron density of the aluminium ions was saved too; so, that these electrons can be also included in the total electron density.

The fields need to be written out at such a period that oscillations at the plasma frequency can still be resolved. It can be shown that, due to how the simulation-step duration relates to the simulation cell size¹, one needs to write the output at around every 2 simulation steps if one wants to achieve the same amount of samples per a plasma oscillation period as how many cells fit in a plasma wavelength[30]. The data needs to be written for as long as a probing pulse needs to cross and completely leave the simulation box. The total output size for an already very short 4 fs long pulse was estimated to 132 TiB.

This is simply an unmanageable amount of data for just one simulation. Because of that, the output was reduced by pixel binning. Field data were averaged over cubes with a side length of two simulation cells what resulted in an output size reduction by a factor of $2^3 = 8$. This particle binning could not be achieved directly in `PICongGPU` as the software does not provide such functionality. Hence, a new python tool `field-reduce`[82] was developed that uses the `openPMD-api` and `mpi4py` to bin simulation output, in parallel. At first the tool was meant to be used in a streaming set-up so that the unreduced output would not have to be written to disk at all. Unfortunately, this approach failed due to some configuration limitations, present at the time, at the local HPC cluster `hemera`. Because of that, the simulation run was split in 9 parts, and `field-reduce` was used to process the data after every such simulation part has run. Both, the temporary, and the final output were saved with the ADIOS2 `openPMD` backend, and with a `blosc zstd` compression enabled.

¹restricted by the CFL condition

Figure 8.1.: Expected ionization state occupancy for the laser envelope and intensity used in the aluminium set-up. The first plot at the top shows the state occupancy based on the ADK field ionization model, the plot below shows the transmission rates from the same model, the last plot shows the occupancy according to the BSI model.

8.1.3. Faraday Rotation calculation

The simulation output showed, as anticipated, some visible filamentation in both electron density and magnetic fields, as well as ambipolar fields at the both target surfaces; this can be seen in figs. 8.2 to 8.5, 8.6 and 8.7.

As a probing pulse propagates through a plasma, the Faraday Rotation effect is being integrated over time and space. Because the magnetic field changes its sign from a filament to filament, it is plausible that contributions to the polarization change from filaments with opposite field signs may cancel each other out. This consideration leads to a question if such structures are going to be visible in a polarimetry experiment. This set-up was an attempt to calculate X-ray Faraday Rotation from a full size, three-dimensional PIC simulation with a laser-plasma interaction to help answer this question. Until now such calculations were either done with two-dimensional simulations[28] under an assumption of a (half-way) cylindrical symmetry or from small three-dimensional set-ups[30] that only modelled ca. 1.6 μm of plasma in the transversal direction, and could not fit the whole laser focus.

The rotation angle was calculated using the python tool `fdrot` developed in my bachelor thesis[30], with a few minor changes. The old tool was averaging the rotation angle as a weighted average over the probing pulse. Clearly, one can not simply average the angle, but should rather average intensity or amplitude instead. Here, the calculation was done in the following way: The probing beam was divided into Δx long sections and the rotation angle was calculated individually, as two-dimensional arrays, for each section. Then, these rotation angle maps were transformed into intensity behind an analyser set at a 90° angle to the initial polarization

$$I_{ixy} = \sin(\alpha_{ixy})^2 . \quad (8.2)$$

These intensities were weighted by the relative probing pulse intensities w_i , satisfying $\sum_i w_i = 1$, and summed to

$$I_{xy} = \sum_i I_{ixy} . \quad (8.3)$$

Finally, the rotation angle was obtained from

$$\alpha_{xy} = \arcsin(\sqrt{I_{xy}}) . \quad (8.4)$$

There are two problems with this calculation method. Firstly, the choice of the analyser, set at the right angle, leads to an ambiguity in the rotation sign. So, α calculated like this will be always positive, regardless of that if the magnetic field component along the propagation direction was positive or negative. Secondly, one should be summing amplitudes rather than intensities. This can be motivated, by the fact that a typical analyser is also a spectral filter, so the radiation behind it is highly monochromatic and should be summed coherently.

It was planed to rerun this analysis and calculate the angle similarly to how it was done in 7.2. That is, by calculating the two amplitude components A_x, A_y , for each pulse slice, and summing over these amplitudes instead of intensities. Unfortunately, the simulation output was permanently corrupted during a storage system outage, therefore this new analysis could not be performed.

Figure 8.9 shows the result of the analysis for two propagation directions (along simulation x and z axes). The rotation was obtained from the total electron density including the bound electrons (though these didn't contribute much as almost all ions were already fully ionized, see fig. 8.7). An average gamma value was calculated, for each cell, individually for all three populations from

the number and energy densities. It was used to multiply the densities of the cold, warm and hot populations by $\langle \gamma \rangle^{-2}$.

The results were calculated for an 2 fs Lorentzian pulse (Cauchy distribution) at 6 keV, cut 2 fs before and after the pulse maximum. The pulse entered the simulation volume with an approximately 120 fs long delay and reached the centre of the simulation volume at around 138 fs; for reference, the pump laser arrived at the foil surface at around 73 fs.

In total, these results show that the filament structures are still visible in the two-dimensional rotation maps. Still, it is not clear if the rotation is large enough to be detected with polarization purities currently delivered by XFEL sources. In the end, one should treat this simulation outcome with some caution, especially due to the very low resolution (in terms of the number of particles per cell), the use of periodic boundary conditions, and the absence of binary collisions.

8.2. In-situ SAXS and Faraday Rotation

Once the implementation presented in chapter 6 was completed, and tested as described in chapter 7, in-situ SAXS and polarimetry probing simulations were run. This section will start with a description of the new simulation set-up, and the chosen XFEL probing beam. Then, the rest of this section will handle the results from the two synthetic experiments.

8.2.1. New simulation set-up

Foil and laser

At first, the simulation set-up used for the in-situ probing was supposed to be the same as the one in the aluminium foil simulation described in the previous section. Unfortunately, with the addition of the probing particles the old configuration did not fit on the locally available GPU nodes. Reducing the computational requirements for the aluminium simulation turned out to be also not possible because the simulation was already running with the lowest reasonable resolution; e.g. the number of macro ions per cell was already 1 and obviously could not be further reduced. Therefore, the set-up was changed.

Now, the foil was no longer made out of aluminium; the new material was formvar ($C_8O_2H_{14}$), a plastic with a density equal to $1.23 \cdot 10^6 \text{ gm}^{-3}$, even lower than aluminium with $2.7 \cdot 10^6 \text{ gm}^{-3}$. Together with the lower Z-number of the molecule constituents, it resulted in a much lower electron density. This made it possible to change the simulation cell size from approximately 7 nm to exactly 10 nm. Additionally, the foil thickness was reduced to 2 μm to further lower the number of initialized macro-particles.

The new simulations were run with 960 cells in the both transversal directions (x, and z), resulting in the same 9.6 μm box width. In the laser propagation direction, the box did not have to be that long any more since the foil was much thinner. The new longitudinal box size was 1008 cells ($\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$).

To avoid having to initialize at least 3 macro ions per cell, each for every element, the carbon and oxygen atoms were both represented by one particle type. This combined species had the charge and ionization levels of carbon, and a mass equal to $m_{CO} = (8/10)m_C + (2/10)m_O \approx 12.8 \text{ u}$. Carbon ions were initialized in a 4+ state; this pre-ionization state was determined using the same python tool

Figure 8.2.: B-field from the aluminium set-up. On the left B_z averaged over x . On the right B_x averaged over z . From top to bottom the figures show the fields at 120.0 fs, 134.20 fs, and 154.72 fs.

Figure 8.3.: B-field from the aluminium set-up. On the left B_z slice in the middle of the x direction, at 134.20 fs. On the right B_x slice in the middle of the z direction, at 134.20 fs. The values were first averaged in the z (or x) direction over 6 cells around the slice point, then a $\sigma = 0.8$ Gaussian filter was applied 3 times to smooth the data.

Figure 8.4.: B-field from the aluminium set-up. B-field from an iteration at 134.20 fs, sliced at $y=4.1 \mu\text{m}$ (just behind the front surface), zoomed in at the laser focus. On the left B_z , on the right B_x . Values were averaged in the y direction over 6 cells around the slice point, then $\sigma = 0.8$ Gaussian filter was applied 3 times.

Figure 8.5.: Free electron density from the aluminium set-up, at 134.20 fs. On the left n_e slice in the middle of the z direction. On the right n_e slice in the middle of the x direction.

Figure 8.6.: Free electron density from the aluminium set-up, at 134.20 fs. On the left n_e slice in the middle of the z direction. On the right n_e slice in the middle of the x direction.

Figure 8.7: Bound electron density, from the aluminium set-up, averaged over x at 134.20 fs.

Figure 8.8.: Free electron density from the aluminium set-up. n_e from an iteration at 134.20 fs, sliced at $y=4.1 \mu\text{m}$ (just behind the front surface), zoomed in at the laser focus. Data was smoothed with a $\sigma = 0.5$ Gaussian filter.

Figure 8.9.: Faraday Rotation with relativistic correction, for an analyser at 90° , after summing the effect from all electron populations. On the left accumulated over the x direction, on the right over the z direction.

that was used for the aluminium set-up. The proton number was set to its physical value, while the density of the combined species was set so that the total fully ionized electron density was the one of formvar (regardless of the missing bound electrons from oxygen). The rest of the set-up, including the pump laser configuration, remained unchanged.

Probing pulse

The probing beam configuration was roughly based on beam parameters from recent experiments at HiBEF. It was a 30 fs long Gaussian with a 20 μm spot size (transversally a radially symmetric Gaussian with FWHM = 20 μm), and a peak intensity resulting in $N_0 = 1 \cdot 10^{12}$ photons in the beam spot. The photon energy was fixed with the wavelength flag set to $\lambda_{\text{XFEL}} = 0.15 \text{ nm}$.

The beam was cut at 45 fs before and after the main pulse and was introduced into the simulation with a 50 fs delay. These settings resulted in the following timing for the probing pulse maximum: It entered the simulation box at 50 fs + 45 fs = 95 fs, reached the centre of the box at 95 fs + (4.8 μm)/ c = 111 fs, and left the box at 95 fs + (9.6 μm)/ c = 127 fs.

Since both of the planned synthetic diagnostics work with coherent radiation, the probing beam was initialized as amplitudons. That means, the beam profile and shape was set to a square root of the just mentioned Gaussians. The amplitudon reference flux density (`photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity`) was calculated with

$$\Phi_{\text{am}} = \frac{\sqrt{N_0}c}{\sqrt{V_{\text{ref}}}} \sqrt{f(\vec{\mathbf{0}}, (\tau_{\text{ps}}/2))} \approx 7.378 \cdot 10^{34} \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}, \quad (8.5)$$

where $V_{\text{ref}} = 1 \cdot 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ is an arbitrary reference volume, f is defined just like in ch. 5, and $f(\vec{\mathbf{0}}, (\tau_{\text{ps}}/2))$ is its value at the pulse maximum; V_{ps} used in the definition of f was the cylinder volume $\pi(10 \mu\text{m})^2 \cdot c\tau_{\text{ps}}$.

The figs. 8.10 to 8.17 show electron density and magnetic fields from the simulation output. The simulation steps included in these figures — 95.76 fs, 114.91 fs, and 134.06 fs — were the closest available to the just mentioned 95 fs, 111 fs, 127 fs. Once again, one can clearly see ambipolar magnetic fields, and filamentation in both \mathbf{B} and n_e ; somehow interesting are here the net-like structures in fig. 8.13, resembling some experimentally observed proton signatures. Noteworthy is also the visible (also in the aluminium set-up fig. 8.8) slight elongation of these bubbles along the laser polarization (z), just like predicted and modelled in [34].

But, also these simulation results should be enjoyed with some caution; the same set-up in a two-dimensional simulation with 16 macro ions per species per cell was showing filaments that were completely crossing the 2 μm thick foil while in this three-dimensional simulation, as well as in 2D runs with lower number of mppc, the filaments are only clearly visible in the front half of the foil. This is strongly suggesting that some physical phenomena remain not properly resolved.

8.2.2. SAXS

This part of the section will discuss the in-situ scattering simulations. For SAXS, the new configuration was run with 4 new macro amplitudons per a boundary cell and time step; this was the maximal number that could be set with this set-up and the available resources. The scattering was

Figure 8.10.: B-field from the formvar set-up. On the left B_z averaged over x . On the right B_x averaged over z . From top to bottom the figures show the fields at 95.76 fs, 114.91 fs, and 134.06 fs.

enabled with the split scatterer, with 256 new particles on split. The used condition functor was `RandomThomson` with the total scattering cross-section set to

$$\sigma_{\Omega} = 4\pi r_e l_0 \sin\left(\frac{\theta_{\max}}{2}\right) \approx 1.06 \cdot 10^{-26} \text{ m}^{-2}, \quad (8.6)$$

where $l_0 = 3 \text{ nm}$, and $\theta_{\max} = 0.02 \text{ rad}$ was the set maximal scattering angle. The scattering was limited to the first order. With that, the total probability to scatter within the foil was around

$$n_e \sigma_{\Omega} \cdot 9.6 \mu\text{m} \approx 4\%; \quad (8.7)$$

here, n_e is the fully ionized formvar electron density, approximately $4 \cdot 10^{29} \text{ m}^{-3}$.

The detection configuration was mostly based on the set-up from [21]. In the main simulation run, the detector was placed in a 1 m distance with 1024×1024 $40 \mu\text{m} \times 40 \mu\text{m}$ cells. This gave a $\theta_{x,\max} = \theta_{y,\max}$ of approximately 0.02 rad, which for the probing wavelength $\lambda = 0.15 \text{ nm}$ was equivalent to $q_{\max} \approx 0.86 \text{ nm}^{-1}$. In addition, two other simulations were run, both with a 1024×1024 detector in a 1 m distance but with $4 \mu\text{m}$ and $400 \mu\text{m}$ large detector cells. In these set-ups the maximum scattering angle θ_{\max} was adjusted accordingly to 0.002 rad and 0.2 rad. σ_{Ω} and so the scattering probability remained unchanged between the three runs.

An approximate range for the size of the filament structures was estimated from the n_e slices in fig. 8.13 as $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ to $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. These values correspond to an 0.3 mrad to 1.5 mrad range for the Bragg peak angle, which can be calculated from $\theta = \arcsin(\lambda_{\text{XFEL}}/S)$, with S – the structure size. Hence, if there would be some signal originating from the filament structures, one would expect it to be visible in at least one of the two detectors with the $4 \mu\text{m}$ and $40 \mu\text{m}$ large cells. Unfortunately, nothing like that could be observed. One can see, from fig. 8.19 that there was no visible signal except for a homogeneously distributed noise and a cross like structure in the centre of the detector (only really properly visible at the detector with $\theta_{\max} = 0.002 \text{ rad}$).

This cross looks very much like a two-dimensional Fourier transformation of a rectangular box. The

Figure 8.11.: B-field from the formvar set-up. On the left B_z slice in the middle of the x direction, at 114.91 fs. On the right B_x slice in the middle of the z direction, at 114.91 fs. The values were first averaged in the z (or x) direction over 6 cells around the slice point, then a $\sigma = 0.8$ Gaussian filter was applied 3 times to smooth the data.

Figure 8.12.: B-field from the formvar set-up. B-field sliced at $y=4.3\ \mu\text{m}$ (just behind the front surface), zoomed in at the laser focus. On the left B_z , on the right B_x . From top to bottom the figures show the fields at 95.76 fs, 114.91 fs, and 134.06 fs. Values were averaged in the y direction over 6 cells around the slice point, then $\sigma = 0.8$ Gaussian filter was applied 3 times.

Figure 8.13.: Free electron density from the formvar set-up. [Free electron sliced just behind the front surface, zoomed in at the laser focus. On the left figures with a slice point at $y=4.2\ \mu\text{m}$, on the right at $y=4.4\ \mu\text{m}$. From top to bottom the figures show the fields at 95.76 fs, 114.91 fs, and 134.06 fs. Data was smoothed with a $\sigma = 0.5$ Gaussian filter.

Figure 8.14.: Free electron density from the formvar set-up, at 114.91 fs. On the left n_e slice in the middle of the z direction. On the right n_e slice in the middle of the x direction.

Figure 8.15.: Free electron density from the formvar set-up, at 114.91 fs. On the left n_e slice in the middle of the z direction. On the right n_e slice in the middle of the x direction.

Figure 8.16: Bound electron density, from the formvar set-up, averaged over x at 114.91 fs.

Figure 8.17.: Free electron density averaged over x at 114.91 fs.

line-outs in fig. 8.20 show that the modulations at the detector central axes fit perfectly a signal from $9.6\ \mu\text{m}$ and $2.15\ \mu\text{m}$ wide slits. So, this signal can be fully explained by the scattering on the rectangular foil with the same dimensions ($2.15\ \mu\text{m}$ is the foil thickness plus one pre-plasma scale length).

The two figures in 8.18 show SAXS scattering intensity calculated, with a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), from the static simulation output (free electron density) at $114.91\ \text{fs}$ (probing beam in the simulation centre). The calculation was done for the same XFEL pulse. The plot at the bottom is zoomed in on the range of the smallest detector ($0.002\ \text{rad}$). Besides the signal from the foil thickness on the $q_x = 0$ axis one can also see diagonal streaks (resembling structures modelled in [22]) as well as some visible signal around ca. $q_x = \pm 0.015\ \text{nm}^{-1}$, $q_y = 0$. Once again, these extra features could not be observed in the in-situ result.

There may be many reasons for why the simulations did not result in any physically interesting scattering. Most likely, there were not enough macro amplitudons in the simulation. The total number of macro particles initialized within the $2\ \mu\text{m} \times 9.6\ \mu\text{m}$ large part of the boundary that covered the foil and over the $30\ \text{fs}$ long pulse duration can be estimated as approximately $1.2 \cdot 10^9$. With the 4% probability, and the splitting into 257 particles the total number of amplitudons scattered from within the foil, and initialized within the $30\ \text{fs}$, is more or less 10 times higher $1.2 \cdot 10^{10}$. This is not a small number, but it includes scattering from the whole foil. A number of particles that were scattered within some small structure will be much smaller and probably insufficient to properly sample the many possible classical photon paths that need to be taken into consideration.

A much better start would be a small set-up, concentrated around the laser focus. Also, just like it was done in real life experiments, one should probably begin by simulating a structured target from that one would expect a much stronger signal, e.g. something similar to the foils used in [23]. Additionally, these simulations should be accompanied by calculations done in other available tools, like `parataxis`, `GAPD`, or the `xrayScattering` plug-in. Once parameter configurations are found that work for such simpler set-ups, one can think about scaling these up to large, $\sim 10\ \mu\text{m}$, simulation volumes.

Nevertheless, this first in-situ SAXS analysis was of a rather exploratory nature, and despite its negative outcome the presence of the correct signal from the foil rectangular form, together with the test results from section 7.1, and the analytical derivation in chapter 5 suggests that the calculation is, in fact, correct. It remains only unclear, what are the actual computational requirements of such computations, and to what extent this method can be practicably applied to large and highly dynamical systems.

8.2.3. Faraday Rotation

The polarimetry configuration was much simpler. The beam was initialized with just one macro particle per boundary cell and iteration. The used scattering functor was the `FaradayRotationFunctor`. Electron densities included in the calculation were the same three populations as for the aluminium simulation, together with the bound electron density of the carbon ions (again not really contributing to the result, see fig. 8.16).

The densities of the cold, warm, and the hot electrons were already multiplied with the $\langle\gamma\rangle^{-2}$ factor, thanks to the new combined-derived attribute `RelativisticDensity`. In a second run, the three corrected n_e fields were replaced by a simple free electron density so that the second simulation was done without the relativistic correction.

Figure 8.18.: SAXS intensity obtained with an 2D FFT from a single iteration at 114.91 fs from the formvar set-up. The FFT was performed on a free electron density integrated in the propagation direction z and multiplied with the $20\ \mu\text{m}$ Gaussian profile. The absolute intensity values were calculated for the pulse used in the simulation.

Figure 8.19.: SAXS detector images from formvar simulations. Top left: simulation with $\theta_{\max} = 0.2$ rad, top right: simulation with $\theta_{\max} = 0.02$ rad, bottom left: simulation with $\theta_{\max} = 0.002$ rad, bottom right: $\theta_{\max} = 0.002$ rad zoomed in.

Figure 8.20.: Line-outs, from the simulation with $\theta_{\max} = 0.002$ rad, along the detector y (left) and x (right) axis. Zoomed in around the detector centre. The theoretical curves are expected relative intensities for a $9.6 \mu\text{m}$ slit (left) and a $2.15 \mu\text{m}$ slit (right), for the probing wavelength.

When it comes to $n_{e,\text{free}}$ in figs. 8.14 and 8.15 the distributions look very similar when looked upon from both the x and z directions; the magnetic field structures, on the other hand, differ quite significantly between the left- and right-hand side of fig. 8.10. The filaments visible in the figures with B_z averaged over z were clearly longer and much more pronounced as the ones still visible after averaging B_x over x. For that reason, the Faraday Rotation calculation was done along the simulation z axis.

In fig. 8.21 one can see the results of this calculation from both simulation runs. The filaments and the ambipolar fields are very much visible. However, the filaments are partially merged into each other and not that easily recognizable as in fig. 8.9. This can be probably explained by the much longer probing pulse (30 fs Gaussian compared to a 4 fs Lorentzian). One should be careful while comparing the results from this and the aluminium set-up since both were calculated at different photon energies, but the λ dependence is just a simple factor in 2.22, so this can be easily accounted for.

In total, the investigation (including both the aluminium, and the formavar set-ups) has shown that as long as filament structures are present in plasma they can be potentially observed with polarimetry, at least with sufficiently short probing pulses.

There is also a ca. tenfold drop in the maximum observed rotation angle visible between the uncorrected and the relativistically corrected case. The fig. 8.22 shows the quotient of the values obtained from the two runs. That, approximately, factor 10 difference holds more or less throughout the foil; it becomes significantly higher only in the expansion regions at the front and the back of the foil, where one would expect a higher ratio of hot to cold electrons.

Figure 8.21.: Faraday rotation, from the formvar set-up, accumulated over the simulation z axis. On the left without the relativistic correction and on the left with the $1/\gamma_{ave}^2$ correction. Laser comes from the left.

Figure 8.22.: Ratio of the rotation angle from the simulation without the relativistic correction over the value from the run that included the correction. The quotient was set to zero for cells where either of the two values was zero. Laser comes from the left.

9. Conclusions and Outlook

This project was undertaken to design a radiation transport solution for the Particle In Cell simulation software `PICongGPU`. Radiation transport is a rather broad umbrella-term that includes many physical phenomena, so, at first, its aspects relevant to plasma modelling were identified. What followed, was an evaluation of different possible approaches to radiation representation in the context of their applicability to modelling of the relevant phenomena.

As a result of these considerations, the aim of the remaining part of the project was set to create a Monte-Carlo, particle-based solution; it was, to a large extent, successfully accomplished. Three new, independent, `PICongGPU` modules for particle injection, detection, and scattering (including directional scattering, and Faraday Rotation) were implemented. Two main aspects of radiation transport (absorption and emission) remain to be developed, but these can be now introduced within the new, highly flexible scattering stage.

Clearly, the focus of this work was put on probing with XFEL pulses in polarimetry, SAXS and other related experiments. It was pointed out on multiple occasions that the standard radiation transport theory does not properly treat coherent sources such as the ones utilized in these experiments, hence it needed to be extended; such extension was discussed, in-depth, in chapter 5. Findings presented in that discussion raised some important theoretical issues, above all regarding multiple coherent scattering computation, that have not been addressed before. Furthermore, the discussion provides a deeper understanding of how, well known, scattering theory rudiments can be applied to analytically describe such novel experimental methods like SAXS plasma diagnostic. Finally, and most importantly, the derivation presented in that chapter confirms the usefulness of particle-based Monte-Carlo algorithms in coherent scattering calculations. What still needs to be clarified, is how the two radiation descriptions (with macro photons, and with macro amplitudons) are to be translated into each other in simulations including both: the standard radiation transport and coherent effects.

Although this work concentrated on code development, the findings presented in the previous chapter may be of relevance for the ongoing polarimetry experiments. The calculated rotation map show that filament structures, here for the first time simulated with full electron density in three-dimensions, survive a temporal and spatial integration. This study has also shown the relativistic temperature effect to cause a ca. 10 fold drop in the polarization rotation, however this value is not universal since it depends on electron temperature. Moreover, the calculated effect is comparable with values obtained with a Radon transform from a two-dimensional simulation study in [28].

The full answer to the question if such simulated rotation can be experimentally observed depends on several parameters: the XFEL beam intrinsic polarization purity; polarization resolution of the used analyser; detector characteristic, including its resolution; the total drop on intensity coming from the analyser (due to its frequency filtering nature and the relatively broad probe spectrum); as well as the absorption in the target, and in the CRLs. So, to help answer this question, follow-up studies should include a complete, source to detector, synthetic experiment.

Both simulations show instabilities similar to Raylight-Taylor instability simulated in [34]; here for the first time with full electron density. Further, the found structures are on the sub nano-meter

scale; as anticipated in [83], a study including a similar thin foil simulation, but in two-dimensions. The density filaments, similarly to the B-field filaments, are still visible after averaging over one of the transversal dimensions (see fig. 8.17); this implies that they are likely to be experimentally observable just like it was argued in [21] for two-dimensional simulations.

At this point, one should remember that the reliability of the presented results (from both the post-processing, and the in-situ analyses) is somehow limited by the low simulation resolution, dictated by the available computational resources. Because of that, these simulations should be repeated on a larger HPC system.

When it comes to SAXS in-situ analysis, considerably more work will need to be done to determine the computational requirements and practicability of this method in different scenarios. Further studies should involve, at-first, similar synthetic experiments in considerably smaller systems and, preferably, structured targets. Future research could also usefully explore how exactly SAXS could be modelled within the wave-picture approach, and clarify whether it may allow achieving useful results on considerably smaller HPC systems. Especially, it should investigate to what degree such an implementation would be scalable, and parallelizable.

A natural progression of this work is, of course, to implement absorption and emission. At first, this could be realized with externally generated (i.e. with FLYCHK[84]) look-up tables. The absorptance and emittance could be then determined from local particle-derived plasma parameters, such as temperature and density. But, this would require averaging, and assumptions to be made about the particle velocity distribution. Therefore, at some point, absorptance and emittance should be implemented using actual transmission rates and atomic state distributions calculated in-situ by the atomic physics module (currently in development).

Similarly, one could think about developing binary-collision based alternatives to the just implemented scattering module that is also based on particle-derived, average quantities. These could enable self-consistent modelling of temperature effects (such as the relativistic correction for Faraday Rotation, or the Compton shift and the resulting partial loss of coherence for SAXS) directly from individual particle momenta.

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Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit im Rahmen der Betreuung am Institut für Kern- und Teilchenphysik ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst habe und alle verwendeten Quellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Ort, Datum

Unterschrift

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A. Implemented code

Code in this appendix includes most of the new implementation. The file names show relative paths within the directory `include/picongpu/` in the PICongGPU repository. All files begin with a following licence header: that was shortened, in the files below, down to just the first line.

```
1  /* Copyrighth <year> <authors>
2  * This file is part of PICongGPU.
3  *
4  * PICongGPU is free software: you can redistribute it and/or modify
5  * it under the terms of the GNU General Public License as published by
6  * the Free Software Foundation, either version 3 of the License, or
7  * (at your option) any later version.
8  *
9  * PICongGPU is distributed in the hope that it will be useful,
10 * but WITHOUT ANY WARRANTY; without even the implied warranty of
11 * MERCHANTABILITY or FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE. See the
12 * GNU General Public License for more details.
13 *
14 * You should have received a copy of the GNU General Public License
15 * along with PICongGPU.
16 * If not, see <http://www.gnu.org/licenses/>.
17 */
```

Listing A.1: Licence header

File 1. param/scattering.param

```

1  /* Copyright 2020-2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/functors.def"
8  /* preprocessor struct generator */
9  #include <pmacc/preprocessor/struct.hpp>
10
11 namespace picongpu
12 {
13     namespace particles
14     {
15         namespace scattering
16         {
17             struct ConditionParam
18             {
19                 static constexpr float_X threshold = 0.0_X;
20             };
21             struct DirectionParam
22             {
23                 static constexpr float_X maxPolarAngle
24                     = pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value * 0.01_X;
25                 static constexpr float_X minPolarAngle
26                     = pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value * 0.00_X;
27             };
28             using ConditionFunc = condition::Threshold<ConditionParam>;
29             using DirectionFunc = direction::Random<DirectionParam>;
30
31             template<typename T_Densities>
32             using PhotonScatterer
33                 = ScatterFunc<T_Densities, ConditionFunc, DirectionFunc>;
34         } // namespace scattering
35     } // namespace particles
36 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 2. param/externalBeam.param

```

1  /* Copyright 2020-2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2  {
3  namespace plugins
4  {
5  namespace externalBeam
6  {

```

```

7  using namespace picongpu::plugins::externalBeam;
8  /* Choose from:
9  * - ZSide
10 * - YSide
11 * - XSide
12 * - ZRSide
13 * - YRSide
14 * - XRSide
15 */
16 using DbgProbingSide = picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::ZSide;
17
18 PMACC_STRUCT(
19     DbgRotationParam,
20     (PMACC_C_VALUE(
21         float_X,
22         yawAngle,
23         0._X / 180.0_X * pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value))(
24         PMACC_C_VALUE(
25             float_X,
26             pitchAngle,
27             0.0_X / 180.0_X * pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value)));
28
29 PMACC_STRUCT(
30     DbgGaussParam,
31     (PMACC_C_VALUE(float_X, sigmaX_SI, 0.0_X)) (PMACC_C_VALUE(
32         float_X,
33         sigmaY_SI,
34         0.0_X)));
35 PMACC_STRUCT(
36     DbgOffsetParam,
37     (PMACC_C_VECTOR_DIM(
38         float_32,
39         DIM2,
40         beamOffset_SI,
41         0.0_X,
42         0.0_X)) (PMACC_C_VALUE(float_X, beamDelay_SI, 0.0_X)));
43
44 // using DbgBeamProfile =
45 // externalBeam::beamProfiles::GaussianProfile<DbgGaussParam>;
46 using DbgBeamProfile = externalBeam::beamProfiles::ConstProfile;
47 using DbgBeamShape = externalBeam::beamShapes::ConstShape<>;
48
49 using DbgBeamCoordinates
50     = picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::CoordinateTransform<
51         DbgProbingSide,
52         picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::SecondaryRotation<DbgRotationParam>,
53         DbgOffsetParam>;
54 using DebugBeam = picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::
55     ProbingBeam<DbgBeamProfile, DbgBeamShape, DbgBeamCoordinates>;
56 } // namespace externalBeam
57 } // namespace plugins
58
59 namespace particles

```

```

60 {
61 namespace externalBeam
62 {
63 namespace density
64 {
65 struct ProbingBeamDensityParam
66 {
67 private:
68 static constexpr float_64 cellVolumeSI
69 = SI::CELL_HEIGHT_SI * SI::CELL_WIDTH_SI * SI::CELL_DEPTH_SI;
70
71 public:
72 using ProbingBeam = plugins::externalBeam::DebugBeam;
73 // Just a test value -> one 100000 photons per full cell
74 static constexpr float_64 photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity{
75 100000.0 / cellVolumeSI * SI::SPEED_OF_LIGHT_SI};
76 };
77 using ProbingBeamDensity = ProbingBeamImpl<ProbingBeamDensityParam>;
78 } // namespace density
79 namespace startPosition
80 {
81 struct QuietProbingBeamParam
82 {
83 using ProbingBeam = typename picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::DebugBeam;
84 /** Number of particles in each dimension initialized in a cell (in the beam
85 * coordinate system).
86 *
87 * Keep in mind that the particles are not spaced across the complete cell
88 * but rather a reduced cell. The cell dimensions along the beam x and y
89 * coordinates stay the same but along the beam z direction the cell depth is
90 * reduced to DELTA_T * SPED_OF_LIGHT.
91 *
92 * All 3 components need to be specified. In the case of a 2 dimensional
93 * simulation, the component corresponding to the picongpu z direction will
94 * be discarded later.
95 */
96 static constexpr float_X minWeighting = 0.001;
97 using numParticlesPerDimension = mCT::Int<3, 3, 1>;
98 };
99 using QuietBeam = QuietProbingBeam<QuietProbingBeamParam>;
100 } // namespace startPosition
101 namespace momentum
102 {
103 struct BeamMomentumParam
104 {
105 using ProbingBeam = typename picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::DebugBeam;
106 static constexpr float_64 photonEnergySI = 6.0 * UNITCONV_keV_to_Joule;
107 };
108 using BeamMomentum = PhotonMomentum<BeamMomentumParam>;
109 } // namespace momentum
110 namespace initPhase
111 {
112 struct Param

```

```

113 {
114 using ProbingBeam = typename picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::DebugBeam;
115 static constexpr float_64 phi0 = 0.0;
116 };
117 // using BeamPhase = FromPhotonMomentum<Param>;
118 using BeamPhase = FromSpeciesWavelength<Param>;
119 } // namespace initPhase
120 using BeamStartAttributes = StartAttributesImpl<
121 startPosition::QuietBeam,
122 momentum::BeamMomentum,
123 initPhase::BeamPhase>;
124
125 } // namespace externalBeam
126 } // namespace particles
127 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 3. param/photonDetector.param

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/accumulationPolicies.def"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace plugins
12 {
13 namespace photonDetector
14 {
15 struct PhotonDetectorConfig1
16 {
17 using AccumulationPolicy =
18 /**
19 * Policy that defines how the detector handles incoming particles
20 * Possible values @see particleHandlers
21 */
22 particleHandlers::AddWaveParticles;
23
24 using ParticleFilter = particles::filter::All;
25
26 /**
27 * Distance of the detector from the right side of the volume
28 * Unit: meter
29 */
30 static constexpr float_64 distance = 5.0;
31 /**

```

```

32  * Width and height of each detector cell
33  * Unit: meter
34  */
35  static constexpr float_64 cellWidth = 350e-6;
36  static constexpr float_64 cellHeight = 350e-6;
37
38  static const std::string getName()
39  {
40      return "Config1";
41  }
42  };
43  constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig1::distance;
44  constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig1::cellWidth;
45  constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig1::cellHeight;
46
47  struct PhotonDetectorConfig2
48  {
49      using AccumulationPolicy =
50          /**
51           * Policy that defines how the detector handles incoming particles
52           * Possible values @see particleHandlers
53           */
54          particleHandlers::CountParticles;
55
56      using ParticleFilter = particles::filter::All;
57
58      /**
59       * Distance of the detector from the right side of the volume
60       * Unit: meter
61       */
62      static constexpr float_64 distance = 5.0;
63      /**
64       * Width and height of each detector cell
65       * Unit: meter
66       */
67      static constexpr float_64 cellWidth = 350e-6;
68      static constexpr float_64 cellHeight = 350e-6;
69
70      static const std::string getName()
71      {
72          return "Config2";
73      }
74
75      // TODO: Maybe add extra params for constraints like in praxis.
76  };
77  constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig2::distance;
78  constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig2::cellWidth;
79  constexpr float_64 PhotonDetectorConfig2::cellHeight;
80
81  using SeqAllDetectorConfigs
82      = MakeSeq_t<PhotonDetectorConfig1, PhotonDetectorConfig2>;
83
84  } // namespace photonDetector

```

```

85 } // namespace plugins
86 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 4. particles/PhotonFuncutors.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include <pmacc/math/Vector.hpp>
8  #include <pmacc/traits/GetFlagType.hpp>
9  #include <pmacc/traits/Resolve.hpp>
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12     namespace particles
13     {
14         template<
15             typename T_Species,
16             bool hasWavelength = pmacc::traits::
17                 HasFlag<typename T_Species::FrameType, wavelength<>>::type::value>
18         struct GetAngFrequency
19         {
20             HDINLINE static constexpr float_X get()
21             {
22                 using FrameType = typename Species::FrameType;
23                 using WavelengthFlag = typename pmacc::traits::Resolve<
24                     typename GetFlagType<FrameType, wavelength<>>::type>::type;
25                 constexpr float_X wavelength = WavelengthFlag::getValue();
26                 return pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::doubleValue * SPEED_OF_LIGHT / wavelength;
27             }
28             using Species = T_Species;
29             HDINLINE float_X operator()() const
30             {
31                 return get();
32             }
33
34             template<typename T_Particle>
35             HDINLINE float_X operator()(const T_Particle& particle) const
36             {
37                 return get();
38             }
39         };
40
41         template<typename T_Species> struct GetAngFrequency<T_Species, false>
42         {
43             template<typename T_Particle>
44             HDINLINE float_X operator()(const T_Particle& particle) const

```

```

45 {
46     float_X weighting = particle[weighting_];
47     float_X momentum = math::abs(particle[momentum_]);
48     return momentum / HBAR / weighting * SPEED_OF_LIGHT;
49 }
50 };
51
52 /**
53  * Returns the phase for a given timestep
54  */
55 template<typename T_Species> struct GetPhaseByTimestep
56 {
57     using Species = T_Species;
58
59     HINLINE float_64
60     operator()(const uint32_t currentStep, float_64 phi_0 = 0.0) const
61     {
62         static const float_64 omega = GetAngFrequency<Species>();
63         /* phase phi = phi_0 - omega * t;
64          * Note: This MUST be calculated in double precision as single precision is
65          * inexact after -100 timesteps Double precision is enough for about 10^10
66          * timesteps More timesteps (in SP&DP) are possible, if the product is
67          * implemented as a summation with summands reduced to 2*PI */
68         static const float_64 phaseDiffPerTimestep
69         = fmod(omega * DELTA_T, 2.0 * PI);
70         // Reduce summands to range of 2*PI to avoid bit canceling
71         float_64 dPhi = math::fmod(
72             phaseDiffPerTimestep * static_cast<float_64>(currentStep),
73             2.0 * PI);
74         phi_0 = math::fmod(phi_0, 2.0 * PI);
75         float_64 result = phi_0 - dPhi;
76         // Keep in range of [0,2*PI)
77         if(result < 0)
78             result += 2.0 * PI;
79         return result;
80     }
81
82     HDINLINE float_64 operator()(
83         const uint32_t currentStep,
84         Species const& particle,
85         float_64 phi_0 = 0.0) const
86     {
87         const float_64 omega = GetAngFrequency<Species>(particle);
88         /* phase phi = phi_0 - omega * t;
89          * Note: This MUST be calculated in double precision as single precision is
90          * inexact after -100 timesteps Double precision is enough for about 10^10
91          * timesteps More timesteps (in SP&DP) are possible, if the product is
92          * implemented as a summation with summands reduced to 2*PI */
93         const float_64 phaseDiffPerTimestep
94         = math::fmod(omega * DELTA_T, 2.0 * PI);
95         // Reduce summands to range of 2*PI to avoid bit canceling
96         float_64 dPhi = math::fmod(
97             phaseDiffPerTimestep * static_cast<float_64>(currentStep),

```

```

98         2.0 * PI);
99         phi_0 = math::fmod(phi_0, 2.0 * PI);
100        float_64 result = phi_0 - dPhi;
101        // Keep in range of [0,2*PI)
102        if(result < 0)
103            result += 2.0 * PI;
104        return result;
105    }
106 };
107 } // namespace particles
108 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 5. particles/externalBeam/functors.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  // density:
6  #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/density/ProbingBeamImpl.def"
7  // momentum:
8  #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/momentum/PhotonMomentum.def"
9  // phase:
10 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/FromPhotonMomentum.def"
11 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/FromSpeciesWavelength.def"
12 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/NoPhase.def"
13 // start position:
14 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/startPosition/QuietProbingBeam.def"
15 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/startPosition/RandomProbingBeamImpl.def"
16 // polarization
17 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/polarization/NoPolarization.def"
18 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/polarization/OnePolarization.def"
19
20 // main functor:
21 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/StartAttributesImpl.def"

```

File 6. particles/externalBeam/momentum/PhotonMomentum.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  namespace picongpu

```

```

8  {
9  namespace particles
10 {
11 namespace externalBeam
12 {
13 namespace momentum
14 {
15 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct PhotonMomentum
16 {
17     private:
18     using ParamClass = T_ParamClass;
19     // Defines from which side the beam enters the simulation box.
20     using SideCfg = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam::SideCfg;
21     static constexpr float_64 photonMomentum{
22         ParamClass::photonEnergySI / UNIT_ENERGY
23         / static_cast<float_64>(SPEED_OF_LIGHT)};
24     // Photons propagate along the beam z direction
25     // Check if the beam z axis is a reversed pic axis. If so reverse direction.z
26     // before axis swap.
27     static constexpr bool reverse = SideCfg::Side::reverse[2];
28     using DirectionBeam = typename boost::mpl::
29         if_c<reverse, mCT::Int<0, 0, -1>, mCT::Int<0, 0, 1>>::type;
30     // Convert into the pic simulation system
31     using DirectionSim =
32         typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template ReverseSwap<DirectionBeam>::type;
33
34     public:
35     HINLINE PhotonMomentum(uint32_t currentStep)
36     {
37     }
38
39     /** Set particle momentum
40     *
41     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
42     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
43     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
44     * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
45     *
46     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
47     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
48     * @param particle to be manipulated
49     * @param ... unused particles
50     */
51     template<
52         typename T_Acc,
53         typename T_MetaData,
54         typename T_Particle,
55         typename... T_Args>
56     DINLINE void operator()(
57         T_Acc const& acc,
58         T_MetaData& meta,
59         T_Particle& particle,
60         T_Args&&...) const

```

```

61     {
62         float_X const macroWeighting{particle[weighting_]};
63         float3_X const direction{precisionCast<float_X>(DirectionSim::toRT())};
64         // Don't need to normalize direction here since the norm is 1.
65         float3_X const mom{
66             direction * (static_cast<float_X>(photonMomentum) * macroWeighting)};
67         particle[momentum_] = mom;
68     }
69
70     /* Empty initialization
71     *
72     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
73     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
74     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
75     *
76     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
77     */
78     template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
79     HDINLINE void init(T_MetaData const& meta)
80     {
81     }
82 };
83 // namespace momentum
84 // namespace externalBeam
85 // namespace particles
86 // namespace picongpu

```

File 7. particles/externalBeam/momentum/PhotonMomentum.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  namespace picongpu
6  {
7  namespace particles
8  {
9  namespace externalBeam
10 {
11 namespace momentum
12 {
13     /** Set initial photon momentum
14     *
15     * Sets photon momentum based on beam orientation and photon energy.
16     *
17     * @tparam T_ParamClass param class providing the beam configuration and the
18     * photon energy.
19     * Example:
20     * @code{c++}

```

```

21 *      struct BeamMomentumParam
22 *      {
23 *          using ProbingBeam = typename
24 picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::PhotonBeam;
25 *          static constexpr float_64 photonEnergySI = 6.0 *
26 UNITCONV_keV_to_Joule;
27     };
28 *      @endcode
29 */
30 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct PhotonMomentum;
31 } // namespace momentum
32 } // namespace externalBeam
33 } // namespace particles
34 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 8. particles/externalBeam/density/ProbingBeamImpl.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/ProbingBeam.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/Side.hpp"
9
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12 namespace particles
13 {
14 namespace externalBeam
15 {
16 namespace density
17 {
18 namespace detail
19 {
20 using namespace picongpu::plugins::externalBeam;
21 using namespace picongpu::SI;
22 // Get the area of the cell side that is perpendicular to the beam propagation
23 template<typename T_Side> struct GetCellAreaSI
24 {
25     static constexpr float_64 get();
26 };
27 template<> struct GetCellAreaSI<XSide>
28 {
29     static constexpr float_64 get()
30     {
31         return CELL_DEPTH_SI * CELL_HEIGHT_SI;
32     }

```

```

33     };
34 template<> struct GetCellAreaSI<YSide>
35 {
36     static constexpr float_64 get()
37     {
38         return CELL_DEPTH_SI * CELL_HEIGHT_SI;
39     }
40 };
41 template<> struct GetCellAreaSI<YSide>
42 {
43     static constexpr float_64 get()
44     {
45         return CELL_DEPTH_SI * CELL_WIDTH_SI;
46     }
47 };
48 template<> struct GetCellAreaSI<YRSide>
49 {
50     static constexpr float_64 get()
51     {
52         return CELL_DEPTH_SI * CELL_WIDTH_SI;
53     }
54 };
55 template<> struct GetCellAreaSI<ZSide>
56 {
57     static constexpr float_64 get()
58     {
59         return CELL_WIDTH_SI * CELL_HEIGHT_SI;
60     }
61 };
62 template<> struct GetCellAreaSI<ZRSide>
63 {
64     static constexpr float_64 get()
65     {
66         return CELL_WIDTH_SI * CELL_HEIGHT_SI;
67     }
68 };
69
70 } // namespace detail
71
72 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct ProbingBeamImpl : public T_ParamClass
73 {
74     using ParamClass = T_ParamClass;
75     using ProbingBeam = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam;
76     // Defines from which side the beam enters the simulation box.
77     using Side = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam::Side;
78     static constexpr float_64 photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity
79     = ParamClass::photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity_SI;
80     static constexpr bool limitInY = ParamClass::limitInY;
81     static constexpr float_32 minY = ParamClass::minY_SI / UNIT_LENGTH;
82     static constexpr float_32 maxY = ParamClass::maxY_SI / UNIT_LENGTH;
83
84     // the area of the cell side perpendicular to the propagation
85     static constexpr float_64 CELL_AREA_SI = detail::GetCellAreaSI<Side>::get();

```

```

86 static constexpr float_X PHOTONS_IN_A_CELL = static_cast<float_X>(
87     photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity * SI::DELTA_T_SI * CELL_AREA_SI);
88 // the photon density in the cell in terms of the base density
89 static constexpr float_X REFERENCE_PHOTON_DENSITY
90     = PHOTONS_IN_A_CELL / CELL_VOLUME / BASE_DENSITY;
91
92 template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
93 {
94     using type = ProbingBeamImpl<ParamClass>;
95 };
96
97 HINLINE ProbingBeamImpl(uint32_t currentStep)
98     : probingBeam_m()
99     , currentStep_m(currentStep)
100 {
101 }
102
103 /** Calculate the normalized density
104  *
105  * @param totalCellOffset total offset including all slides [in cells]
106  */
107 HINLINE float_X operator()(const DataSpace<simDim>& totalCellOffset)
108 {
109     const floatD_X globalCellPos(
110         (precisionCast<float_X>(totalCellOffset) + floatD_X::create(0.5))
111         * cellSize.shrink<simDim>());
112     // get the current position in the beam coordinate system
113     float3_X position_b
114         = probingBeam_m.coordinateTransform(currentStep_m, globalCellPos);
115     // Get the relative beam intensity from the probing beam configuration
116     float_X intensity = probingBeam_m(position_b);
117     return intensity * REFERENCE_PHOTON_DENSITY;
118 }
119
120 private:
121 PMACC_ALIGN(probingBeam_m, const ProbingBeam);
122 PMACC_ALIGN(currentStep_m, const uint32_t);
123 };
124 } // namespace density
125 } // namespace externalBeam
126 } // namespace particles
127 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 9. particles/externalBeam/density/ProbingBeamImpl.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4

```

```

5  namespace picongpu
6  {
7      namespace particles
8      {
9          namespace externalBeam
10         {
11             namespace density
12             {
13                 /* Density functor for beam particles
14                  *
15                  * @tparam T_ParamClass param class providing a beam configuration
16                  * and the photon flux that correspond to the relative beam intensity
17                  * equal 1. Example:
18                  * @code{c++}
19                  * struct ProbingBeamDensityParam
20                  * {
21                  *     using ProbingBeam = plugins::externalBeam::PhotonBeam;
22                  *     // unit is m^{-2}s^{-1}
23                  *     static constexpr float_64 photonFluxAtMaxBeamIntensity{1.0e20};
24                  * };
25                  */
26                 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct ProbingBeamImpl;
27             } // namespace density
28         } // namespace externalBeam
29     } // namespace particles
30 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 10. particles/externalBeam/polarization/NoPolarization.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  namespace picongpu
8  {
9      namespace particles
10     {
11         namespace externalBeam
12         {
13             namespace polarization
14             {
15                 struct NoPolarization
16                 {
17                     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
18                     {
19                         using type = NoPolarization;
20                     };

```

```

21 HINLINE NoPolarization(uint32_t currentStep)
22 {
23 }
24
25
26 /* Do Nothing
27 *
28 * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
29 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
30 * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
31 * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
32 * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
33 *
34 * @param acc alpaka accelerator
35 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
36 * @param particle particle to be manipulated
37 * @param ... unused particles
38 */
39 template<
40     typename T_Acc,
41     typename T_MetaData,
42     typename T_Particle,
43     typename... T_Args>
44 HINLINE void operator()(
45     T_Acc const& acc,
46     T_MetaData& meta,
47     T_Particle& particle,
48     T_Args&&...) const
49 {
50 }
51
52 /* Empty initialization
53 *
54 * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
55 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
56 * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
57 *
58 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
59 */
60 template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
61 HDINLINE void init(T_MetaData const& meta)
62 {
63 }
64 };
65 } // namespace polarization
66 } // namespace externalBeam
67 } // namespace particles
68 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 11. particles/externalBeam/polarization/OnePolarization.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 namespace picongpu
6 {
7     namespace particles
8     {
9         namespace externalBeam
10        {
11            namespace polarization
12            {
13                /** Set the particle polarization. Same vaue for a partices.
14                 *
15                 * @tparam T_Param param class. Must define the polarization value (-PI, + PI].
16                 * Example:
17                 * @code{cpp}
18                 * struct T_Param
19                 * {
20                 *     static constexpr float_X polarization{pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value
21                 * /2.0_X};
22                 * };
23                 * @endcode
24                 *
25                 */
26                template<typename T_Param> struct OnePolarization;
27
28            } // namespace polarization
29        } // namespace externalBeam
30    } // namespace particles
31 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 12. particles/externalBeam/polarization/OnePolarization.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 namespace picongpu
8 {
9     namespace particles
10    {
11        namespace externalBeam
12        {
13            namespace polarization

```

```

14 {
15 template<typename T_Param> struct OnePolarization
16 {
17     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
18     {
19         using type = OnePolarization<T_Param>;
20     };
21
22     HINLINE OnePolarization(uint32_t currentStep)
23     {
24     }
25
26     /* Do Nothing
27     *
28     * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
29     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
30     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
31     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
32     * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
33     *
34     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
35     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
36     * @param particle particle to be manipulated
37     * @param ... unused particles
38     */
39     template<
40         typename T_Acc,
41         typename T_MetaData,
42         typename T_Particle,
43         typename... T_Args>
44     DINLINE void operator()(
45         T_Acc const& acc,
46         T_MetaData& meta,
47         T_Particle& particle,
48         T_Args&&...) const
49     {
50         particle[polarizationAngle_] = T_Param::polarization;
51     }
52
53     /* Empty initialization
54     *
55     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
56     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
57     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
58     *
59     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
60     */
61     template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
62     HDINLINE void init(T_MetaData const& meta)
63     {
64     }
65 };
66 } // namespace polarization

```

```

67 } // namespace externalBeam
68 } // namespace particles
69 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 13. particles/externalBeam/polarization/NoPolarization.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 namespace picongpu
6 {
7     namespace particles
8     {
9         namespace externalBeam
10        {
11            namespace polarization
12            {
13                //! Don't set particle polarization ( if the attribute is present it remains
14                //! the default 0.0)
15                struct NoPolarization;
16
17            } // namespace polarization
18        } // namespace externalBeam
19    } // namespace particles
20 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 14. particles/externalBeam/StartAttributesImpl.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2014-2021 Rene Widera, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/NoPhase.def"
6 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/polarization/NoPolarization.def"
7 #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/generic/FreeBoundary.def"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace externalBeam
14         {
15             namespace acc
16             {

```

```

17  /** Set beam particle attributes
18  *
19  * Set the in cell position, the weighting, momentum and phase of a macro
20  * particle created as a part of an external particle beam, that is entering
21  * the simulation box.
22  *
23  * The method numberOfMacroParticles provides the number of new particles that
24  * need to be created in a cell.
25  *
26  * This Functor should be used together with a low level functor
27  * like particles::startPosition::generic::FreeBoundary that ensures that the
28  * particles are created only on the simulation external boundary.
29  *
30  * It is impossible to differentiate between newly created and already
31  * previously present particles after the KernelFillGridWithParticles has run.
32  * Hence, when particles are initialized during the simulation and not only
33  * before the 0th step (when no previous particles exist), all initial
34  * attributes need to be already set in KernelFillGridWithParticles. That's why
35  * this functor wraps around a start position functor (setting weighting,
36  * position and also providing the numberOfMacroParticles method) and combines
37  * it with other sub-functors. Each sub-functor is responsible for one
38  * additional attribute ( currently momentum and phase).
39  *
40  * All sub-functors (beside start position functor) should be default
41  * constructible and have a host-device init method (takes the low level
42  * functor as a reference parameter). The start position functor should have a
43  * constructor which takes currentStep (uint32_t) as an only parameter.
44  *
45  *
46  * @tparam T_StartPositionFunctor functor used to set particle position and
47  * weighting. It should provide a numberOfMacroParticles method.
48  * @tparam T_MomentumFunctor functor used to set particle initial momentum.
49  * @tparam T_PhaseFunctor functor used to set particle initial phase. Use
50  * initPhase::NoPhase for particles without a phase.
51  */
52  template<
53      typename T_StartPositionFunctor,
54      typename T_MomentumFunctor,
55      typename T_PhaseFunctor,
56      typename T_PolarizationFunctor,
57      typename T_Species = bmpl::_1>
58  struct StartAttributesImpl;
59
60  } // namespace acc
61
62  /** Set beam particle attributes
63  *
64  * Set the in cell position, the weighting, momentum and phase of a macro
65  * particle created as a part of an external particle beam.
66  */
67  template<
68      typename T_StartPositionFunctor,
69      typename T_MomentumFunctor,

```

```

70      typename T_PhaseFunctor = initPhase::NoPhase,
71      typename T_PolarizationFunctor = polarization::NoPolarization>
72  using StartAttributesImpl
73  = particles::startPosition::generic::FreeBoundary<acc::StartAttributesImpl<
74      T_StartPositionFunctor,
75      T_MomentumFunctor,
76      T_PhaseFunctor,
77      T_PolarizationFunctor>>;
78
79  } // namespace externalBeam
80  } // namespace particles
81  } // namespace picongpu

```

File 15. particles/externalBeam/functors.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  // density:
6  #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/density/ProbingBeamImpl.hpp"
7  // momentum:
8  #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/momentum/PhotonMomentum.hpp"
9  // phase:
10 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/FromPhotonMomentum.hpp"
11 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/FromSpeciesWavelength.hpp"
12 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/NoPhase.hpp"
13 // start position:
14 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/startPosition/QuietProbingBeam.hpp"
15 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/startPosition/RandomProbingBeamImpl.hpp"
16 // polarization
17 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/polarization/NoPolarization.hpp"
18 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/polarization/OnePolarization.hpp"
19
20 // main functor:
21 #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/StartAttributesImpl.hpp"

```

File 16. particles/externalBeam/startPosition/QuietProbingBeam.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2013-2021 Axel Huebl, Heiko Burau, Rene Widera, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6

```

```

7  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/AxisSwap.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/Side.hpp"
9
10 #include <boost/mpl/integral_c.hpp>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14     namespace particles
15     {
16         namespace externalBeam
17         {
18             namespace startPosition
19             {
20                 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct QuietProbingBeam
21                 {
22                     using ParamClass = T_ParamClass;
23                     // Defines from which side the beam enters the simulation box.
24                     using SideCfg = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam::SideCfg;
25
26                     private:
27                     // shorthand for compile-time indices conversion (between the beam and the
28                     // simulation coordinates)
29                     template<uint32_t idx>
30                     using BeamToPicIdx_t =
31                         typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template BeamToPicIdx<idx>::type;
32                     template<uint32_t idx>
33                     using PicToBeamIdx_t =
34                         typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template PicToBeamIdx<idx>::type;
35
36                     // number of particles in each direction
37                     using numParPerDimension =
38                         typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template ReverseSwap<
39                             typename T_ParamClass::numParticlesPerDimension>::type;
40
41                     /* compile-time calculation of the in-cell particle spacing. Along the beam
42                     * propagation direction ( z in the beam system) particles are created only
43                     * up to the distance that a particle travels in one time-step. Here we
44                     * assume the particles are photons and travel with the speed of light.
45                     */
46                     static constexpr float_X cellSizeCT[3]
47                         = {CELL_WIDTH, CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_DEPTH};
48                     static constexpr float_X cellDepth{cellSizeCT[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value]};
49                     static constexpr float_X spacingBeam[3]
50                         = {1.0_X, 1.0_X, DELTA_T* SPEED_OF_LIGHT / cellDepth};
51                     static constexpr float_X spacing3D_x{
52                         spacingBeam[PicToBeamIdx_t<0u>::value]
53                         / static_cast<float_X>(numParPerDimension::template at<0>::type::value)};
54                     static constexpr float_X spacing3D_y{
55                         spacingBeam[PicToBeamIdx_t<1u>::value]
56                         / static_cast<float_X>(numParPerDimension::template at<1>::type::value)};
57                     static constexpr float_X spacing3D_z{
58                         spacingBeam[PicToBeamIdx_t<2u>::value]
59                         / static_cast<float_X>(numParPerDimension::template at<2>::type::value)};
60
61                     // discard the extra dimension in case of a 2D simulation
62                     using numParShrunked =
63                         typename mCT::shrinkTo<numParPerDimension, simDim>::type;
64
65                     // This is true when the beam travels **against** one of the simulation
66                     // coordinate system unit vectors.
67                     static constexpr bool reverse = SideCfg::Side::reverse[2];
68
69                     public:
70                     HINLINE QuietProbingBeam(uint32_t currentStep) : axisSwap()
71                     {
72
73                     }
74
75                     /** Set in-cell position and weighting
76                     *
77                     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
78                     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
79                     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
80                     * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
81                     *
82                     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
83                     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
84                     * @param particle particle to be manipulated
85                     * @param ... unused particles
86                     */
87                     template<
88                         typename T_Acc,
89                         typename T_MetaData,
90                         typename T_Particle,
91                         typename... T_Args>
92                     HINLINE void operator()(
93                         T_Acc const& acc,
94                         T_MetaData& meta,
95                         T_Particle& particle,
96                         T_Args&&...)
97                     {
98                         uint32_t maxNumMacroParticles = pmacc::math::CT::volume<
99                             typename T_ParamClass::numParticlesPerDimension>::type::value;
100                         /* reset the particle position if the operator is called more times than
101                         * allowed (m_currentMacroParticles underflow protection.
102                         */
103                         if(maxNumMacroParticles <= m_currentMacroParticles)
104                             m_currentMacroParticles = maxNumMacroParticles - 1u;
105
106                         // particle spacing as a run-time float vector
107                         const float3_X spacing3D{spacing3D_x, spacing3D_y, spacing3D_z};
108                         const floatD_X spacing = spacing3D.shrink<simDim>();
109                         /* coordinate in the local in-cell lattice
110                         *
111                         * x = [0, numParsPerCell_X-1]
112                         * y = [0, numParsPerCell_Y-1]
113                         * z = [0, numParsPerCell_Z-1]
114                         */
115                         DataSpace<simDim> inCellCoordinate = DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::map(

```

```

113     numParShrunked::toRT(),
114     m_currentMacroParticles);
115
116     floatD_X inCellPosition
117     = precisionCast<float_X>(inCellCoordinate) * spacing
118     + spacing * float_X(0.5);
119
120     // Shift the coordinate along the beam propagation direction towards the
121     // external boundary if the boundary is on the end of the cell. ( The beam
122     // enters the simulation from the bottom, rear or the right side).
123     if(reverse)
124     {
125         inCellPosition[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value]
126         = 1.0_X - inCellPosition[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value];
127     }
128
129     particle[position_] = inCellPosition;
130     particle[weighting_] = m_weighting;
131
132     // decrease the number of unprocessed particles by 1
133     --m_currentMacroParticles;
134 }
135
136 /* Get the number of particles needed to be created in the simulation cell
137 *
138 * @tparam T_Particle type of the particles that should be created
139 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor sued to call the
140 * StartAttributes functor calling which call this functor.
141 *
142 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info.
143 * @param realParticlesPerCell number of new real particles in the cell in
144 * which this instance creates particles
145 *
146 * @return number of macro particles that need to be created in this cell
147 * (The operator() will be called that many times)
148 */
149 template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
150 HDINLINE uint32_t numberOfMacroParticles(
151     T_MetaData const& meta,
152     float_X const realParticlesPerCell)
153 {
154     // Check if the beam is coming from this side.
155     DataSpace<simDim> globalDomainOffset = meta.domInfo.global.offset;
156     DataSpace<DIM3> globalDomainOffsetBeamSystem
157     = axisSwap.transformCellIdx(globalDomainOffset);
158     if(globalDomainOffsetBeamSystem.z() != 0)
159         return 0u;
160
161     auto numParInCell = numParShrunked::toRT();
162
163     m_weighting = float_X(0.0);
164     uint32_t numMacroParticles

```

```

166     = pmacc::math::CT::volume<numParShrunked>::type::value;
167
168     // particle weighting if all macro particles are created
169     if(numMacroParticles > 0u)
170         m_weighting = realParticlesPerCell / float_X(numMacroParticles);
171
172     // Only create particles if weighting is not below the minimal value.
173     // Notice this is different as in the usual startPosition functor where the
174     // number of macro particles would be reduced to satisfy this condition.
175
176     if(m_weighting < T_ParamClass::minWeighting)
177         return 0u;
178     else
179     {
180         m_currentMacroParticles = numMacroParticles - 1u;
181         return numMacroParticles;
182     }
183 }
184
185 private:
186     PMACC_ALIGN(m_weighting, float_X);
187     PMACC_ALIGN(m_currentMacroParticles, uint32_t);
188     PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap, typename SideCfg::AxisSwapRT);
189 };
190
191 } // namespace startPosition
192 } // namespace externalBeam
193 } // namespace particles
194 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 17. particles/externalBeam/startPosition/QuietProbingBeam.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2014-2021 Rene Widera, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/generic/FreeBoundary.def"
6
7 namespace picongpu
8 {
9     namespace particles
10    {
11        namespace externalBeam
12        {
13            namespace startPosition
14            {
15                /** Evenly spaced postion for beam particles
16                 *
17                 * Set the in cell position and the weighting of the macro particle.

```

```

18 *
19 * @tparam T_ParamClass should define ProbingBeam type,
20 * numParticlesPerDimension vector, and minWeighting (particles won't be
21 * created in cells where weighting would be smaller than this).
22 *
23 * Example param class:
24 * @code{c++}
25 * struct QuietProbingBeamParam
26 * {
27 *     // PhotonBeam needs to be defined by a user as well.
28 *     using ProbingBeam = typename
29 * picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::PhotonBeam; using numParticlesPerDimension
30 * = mCT::Int<4, 4, 1>; static constexpr float_X minWeighting = 0.001;
31 * };
32 * @endcode
33 */
34 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct QuietProbingBeam;
35 } // namespace startPosition
36 } // namespace externalBeam
37 } // namespace particles
38 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 18. particles/externalBeam/startPosition/RandomProbingBeamImpl.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2014-2021 Rene Widera */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/generic/FreeRng.def"
8
9 #include <pmacc/random/distributions/Uniform.hpp>
10
11 #include <boost/mpl/integral_c.hpp>
12
13 namespace picongpu
14 {
15 namespace particles
16 {
17 namespace externalBeam
18 {
19 namespace startPosition
20 {
21 /** Random in cell position for beam particles
22 *
23 * The particle attribute position is assigned with a random
24 * in-cell position. This functor also sets the macro particle weighting.
25 *

```

```

26 * @tparam T_ParamClass should define ProbingBeam type, numParticlesPerCell,
27 * and minWeighting (particles won't be created in cells where weighting
28 * would be smaller than this).
29 *
30 * Example param class:
31 * @code{c++}
32 * struct QuietProbingBeamParam
33 * {
34 *     // PhotonBeam needs to be defined by a user as well.
35 *     using ProbingBeam = typename
36 * picongpu::plugins::externalBeam::PhotonBeam; static constexpr uint32_t
37 * numParticlesPerCell = 6u; static constexpr float_X minWeighting = 0.001;
38 * };
39 * @endcode
40 */
41 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct RandomProbingBeamImpl;
42 } // namespace startPosition
43 } // namespace externalBeam
44 } // namespace particles
45 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 19. particles/externalBeam/startPosition/RandomProbingBeamImpl.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2013-2021 Axel Huebl, Heiko Burau, Rene Widera, Alexander Grund */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/detail/WeightMacroParticles.hpp"
8 #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/generic/FreeRng.def"
9
10 #include <boost/mpl/integral_c.hpp>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14 namespace particles
15 {
16 namespace externalBeam
17 {
18 namespace startPosition
19 {
20 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct RandomProbingBeamImpl
21 {
22     using ParamClass = T_ParamClass;
23     // Defines from which side the beam enters the simulation box.
24     using SideCfg = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam::SideCfg;
25
26 private:

```

```

27 // shorthand for compile-time indices conversion (between the beam and the
28 // simulation coordinates)
29 template<uint32_t idx>
30 using BeamToPicIdx_t =
31     typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template BeamToPicIdx<idx>::type;
32 template<uint32_t idx>
33 using PicToBeamIdx_t =
34     typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template PicToBeamIdx<idx>::type;
35
36 /* compile-time calculation of the in-cell position range. Along the beam
37 * propagation direction ( z in the beam system) particles are created only
38 * up to the distance that a particle travels in one time-step. Here we
39 * assume the particles are photons and travel with the speed of light.
40 */
41 static constexpr float_X cellSizeCT[3]
42     = {CELL_WIDTH, CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_DEPTH};
43 static constexpr float_X cellDepth{cellSizeCT[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value]};
44 static constexpr float_X posLimBeam[3]
45     = {1.0_X, 1.0_X, DELTA_T* SPEED_OF_LIGHT / cellDepth};
46 static constexpr float_X posLimPic_x = posLimBeam[PicToBeamIdx_t<0u>::value];
47 static constexpr float_X posLimPic_y = posLimBeam[PicToBeamIdx_t<1u>::value];
48 static constexpr float_X posLimPic_z = posLimBeam[PicToBeamIdx_t<2u>::value];
49
50 // This is true when the beam travels **against** one of the simulation
51 // coordinate system unit vectors.
52 static constexpr bool reverse = SideCfg::Side::reverse[2];
53
54 public:
55 HDINLINE RandomProbingBeamImpl(uint32_t currentStep) : axisSwap()
56 {
57 }
58
59 /** Set in-cell position and weighting
60 *
61 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
62 * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
63 * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
64 * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
65 *
66 * @param acc alpaka accelerator
67 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
68 * @param particle particle to be manipulated
69 * @param ... unused particles
70 */
71 template<
72     typename T_Acc,
73     typename T_MetaData,
74     typename T_Particle,
75     typename... T_Args>
76 HDINLINE void operator()(
77     T_Acc const& acc,
78     T_MetaData& meta,
79     T_Particle& particle,

```

```

80     T_Args&&...)
81 {
82     // get the random number generator from the low level functor
83     auto rng = meta.getRngHandle()
84         .template applyDistribution<
85             pmacc::random::distributions::Uniform<float_X>>();
86     floatD_X tmpPos;
87
88     // array is not available in device code. even constexpr array.
89     const float3_X posLimPicVec{posLimPic_x, posLimPic_y, posLimPic_z};
90
91     // generate a random in-cell position for each coordinate. In the beam
92     // propagation direction the position is limited by the distance a particle
93     // can travel in one time-step.
94     for(uint32_t d = 0; d < simDim; ++d)
95         tmpPos[d] = rng(acc) * posLimPicVec[d];
96
97     // Shift the coordinate along the beam propagation direction towards the
98     // external boundary if the boundary is on the end of the cell. ( The beam
99     // enters the simulation from the bottom, rear or the right side).
100     if(reverse)
101     {
102         tmpPos[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value]
103             = 1.0_X - tmpPos[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value];
104     }
105
106     particle[position_] = tmpPos;
107     particle[weighting_] = m_weighting;
108 }
109
110 /* Get the number of particles needed to be created in the simulation cell
111 *
112 * @tparam T_Particle type of the particles that should be created
113 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor sued to call the
114 * StartAttributes functor which call this functor.
115 *
116 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
117 * @param realParticlesPerCell number of new real particles in the cell in
118 * which this instance creates particles
119 *
120 * @return number of macro particles that need to be created in this cell
121 * (The operator() will be called that many times)
122 */
123 template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
124 HDINLINE uint32_t numberOfMacroParticles(
125     T_MetaData const& meta,
126     float_X const realParticlesPerCell)
127 {
128     // Check if the beam is coming from this side.
129     DataSpace<simDim> globalDomainOffset = meta.domInfo.global.offset;
130     DataSpace<DIM3> globalDomainOffsetBeamSystem
131         = axisSwap.transformCellIdx(globalDomainOffset);
132     if(globalDomainOffsetBeamSystem.z() != 0)

```

```

133     return Ou;
134
135     // Only create particles if weighting is not below the minimal value.
136     // Notice this is different as in the usual startPosition functor where the
137     // number of macro particles would be reduced to satisfy this condition.
138     m_weighting = realParticlesPerCell / T_ParamClass::numParticlesPerCell;
139     if(m_weighting < T_ParamClass::minWeighting)
140         return Ou;
141     return T_ParamClass::numParticlesPerCell;
142 }
143
144 float_X m_weighting;
145 PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap, typename SideCfg::AxisSwapRT);
146 };
147
148 } // namespace startPosition
149 } // namespace externalBeam
150 } // namespace particles
151 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 20. particles/externalBeam/StartAttributesImpl.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2013-2021 Axel Huebl, Heiko Burau, Rene Widera, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/manipulators/IUnary.def"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/AxisSwap.hpp"
9  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/Side.hpp"
10
11 #include <boost/mpl/integral_c.hpp>
12
13 namespace picongpu
14 {
15     namespace particles
16     {
17         namespace externalBeam
18         {
19             namespace acc
20             {
21                 template<
22                     typename T_StartPositionFunctor,
23                     typename T_MomentumFunctor,
24                     typename T_PhaseFunctor,
25                     typename T_PolarizationFunctor,
26                     typename T_Species>
27                 struct StartAttributesImpl

```

```

28     {
29         // sub-functors:
30         using StartPositionFunctor = T_StartPositionFunctor;
31         using MomentumFunctor = T_MomentumFunctor;
32         using PhaseFunctor = typename bmpl::apply1<T_PhaseFunctor, T_Species>::type;
33         using PolarizationFunctor =
34             typename bmpl::apply1<T_PolarizationFunctor, T_Species>::type;
35         using Species = T_Species;
36
37     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
38     {
39         using type = StartAttributesImpl<
40             T_StartPositionFunctor,
41             T_MomentumFunctor,
42             T_PhaseFunctor,
43             T_PolarizationFunctor,
44             T_SpeciesType>;
45     };
46
47     public:
48     HINLINE StartAttributesImpl(uint32_t currentStep)
49         : startPositionFunctor(StartPositionFunctor(currentStep))
50         , momentumFunctor(MomentumFunctor(currentStep))
51         , phaseFunctor(PhaseFunctor(currentStep))
52         , polarizationFunctor(PolarizationFunctor(currentStep))
53     {
54     }
55     /** Set in-cell position, weighting, momentum, phase
56     *
57     * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
58     * @tparam T_MetaData a generic functor type which inherits from this class
59     * and calls this functor
60     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
61     * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
62     *
63     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
64     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData that calls this functor
65     * @param particle particle to be manipulated
66     * @param ... unused particles
67     */
68     template<
69         typename T_Acc,
70         typename T_MetaData,
71         typename T_Particle,
72         typename... T_Args>
73     HDINLINE void operator()(
74         T_Acc const& acc,
75         T_MetaData& meta,
76         T_Particle& particle,
77         T_Args&&...)
78     {
79         // set position and weighting
80         startPositionFunctor(acc, meta, particle);

```

```

81 // set momentum (needs weighting to be already set)
82 momentumFuncor(acc, meta, particle);
83 // this does nothing if T_PhaseFuncor =
84 // particles::externalBeam::polarization::NoPolarization.
85 polarizationFuncor(acc, meta, particle);
86 // set phase (needs position already set and may need momentum already set)
87 // this does nothing if T_PhaseFuncor =
88 // particles::externalBeam::phase::NoPhase .
89 phaseFuncor(acc, meta, particle);
90 }
91
92 /** Get the number of macro particles that should be created and initialize
93 * this funcor
94 *
95 * This is called only once before the operator is called. Hence this method
96 * is also used to initialize this funcor and the sub-funcors. There is
97 * one instance of the low level funcor for each cell in
98 * KernelFillGridWithParticles so that the initialization can depend on the
99 * cell position.
100 *
101 * @tparam T_Particle type of the particles that should be created
102 * @tparam T_MetaData a generic funcor type which inherits from this class
103 * and calls this funcor
104 *
105 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData that calls this funcor
106 * @param realParticlesPerCell number of new real particles in the cell in
107 * which this instance creates particles
108 *
109 * @return number of macro particles that need to be created in this cell
110 * (The operator() will be called that many times)
111 */
112 template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
113 HDINLINE uint32_t numberOfMacroParticles(
114     T_MetaData const& meta,
115     float_X const realParticlesPerCell)
116 {
117     // initialize sub-funcors
118     momentumFuncor.template init<T_Particle>(meta);
119     phaseFuncor.template init<T_Particle>(meta);
120     polarizationFuncor.template init<T_Particle>(meta);
121
122     // numberOfMacroParticles also initializes the start position funcor
123     const uint32_t numMacroParticles
124         = startPositionFuncor.template numberOfMacroParticles<T_Particle>(
125             meta,
126             realParticlesPerCell);
127
128     return numMacroParticles;
129 }
130
131 private:
132 PMACC_ALIGN(startPositionFuncor, StartPositionFuncor);
133 PMACC_ALIGN(momentumFuncor, MomentumFuncor);

```

```

134 PMACC_ALIGN(phaseFuncor, PhaseFuncor);
135 PMACC_ALIGN(polarizationFuncor, PolarizationFuncor);
136 };
137 } // namespace acc
138 } // namespace externalBeam
139 } // namespace particles
140 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 21. particles/externalBeam/phase/FromSpeciesWavelength.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 namespace picongpu
6 {
7     namespace particles
8     {
9         namespace externalBeam
10        {
11            namespace initPhase
12            {
13                /** Calculate initial phase from the current time-step and the species
14                 * wavelength flag
15                 */
16                template<typename T_ParamClass, typename T_Species = bmpl::_1>
17                struct FromSpeciesWavelength;
18            } // namespace initPhase
19        } // namespace externalBeam
20    } // namespace particles

```

File 22. particles/externalBeam/phase/AssingPhase.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include <pmacc/traits/HasIdentifier.hpp>
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {

```

```

13 namespace externalBeam
14 {
15     namespace initPhase
16     {
17         /* Assign particle phase as the startPhase attribute
18         *
19         * @tparam T_Species species type
20         * @tparam usePhaseInsteadOfStartPhase switch between phase and startPhase
21         * attribute. Default: true when species has the phase attribute.
22         */
23     template<typename T_Species> struct AssignPhase
24     {
25         HDINLINE static void assign(T_Species& particle, float_X const& phase)
26         {
27             particle[startPhase_] = phase;
28         }
29     };
30 } // namespace initPhase
31 } // namespace externalBeam
32 } // namespace particles
33 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 23. particles/externalBeam/phase/FromPhotonMomentum.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  namespace picongpu
6  {
7      namespace particles
8      {
9          namespace externalBeam
10         {
11             namespace initPhase
12             {
13                 //! Calculate initial phase from the current time-step and the photon momentum
14
15                 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct FromPhotonMomentum;
16             } // namespace initPhase
17         } // namespace externalBeam
18     } // namespace particles
19 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 24. particles/externalBeam/phase/FromSpeciesWavelength.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2014-2020 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/PhotonFunctors.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/AssignPhase.hpp"
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace externalBeam
14         {
15             namespace initPhase
16             {
17                 template<typename T_ParamClass, typename T_Species>
18                 struct FromSpeciesWavelength
19                 {
20                     using SideCfg = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam::SideCfg;
21                     static constexpr float_64 phi0 = T_ParamClass::phi0;
22
23                     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
24                     {
25                         using type = FromSpeciesWavelength<T_ParamClass, T_SpeciesType>;
26                     };
27
28                     template<uint32_t idx>
29                     using BeamToPicIdx_t =
30                         typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template BeamToPicIdx<idx>::type;
31
32                     HDINLINE FromSpeciesWavelength(uint32_t currentStep)
33                     : curPhase(precisionCast<float_X>(
34                         GetPhaseByTimestep<T_Species>()(currentStep, phi0)))
35                     {
36                     }
37                     /* Set phase
38                     *
39                     * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
40                     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
41                     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
42                     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
43                     * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
44                     *
45                     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
46                     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
47                     * @param particle particle to be manipulated
48                     * @param ... unused particles
49                     */
50                 template<
51                     typename T_Acc,
52                     typename T_MetaData,

```

```

53     typename T_Particle,
54     typename... T_Args>
55     DINLINE void operator()(
56         T_Acc const& acc,
57         T_MetaData& meta,
58         T_Particle& particle,
59         T_Args&&...) const
60 {
61     static constexpr float_X cellSizeCT[3]
62         = {CELL_WIDTH, CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_DEPTH};
63     static constexpr float_X cellDepth{cellSizeCT[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value]};
64
65     /* this functor will be called only in the first cell (counting from the
66        boundary where the photon beam enters the simulation. So global position
67        along the propagation axis is just the in cell position. */
68     const floatD_X position = particle[position_];
69     // distance from the z_beam=0 plane (the simulation boundary) where the
70     // position contribution to the plane wave phase is 0.
71     const float_X distance{(axisSwap.rotate(position)).z() * cellDepth};
72     const float_X waveNumber{GetAngFrequency<T_Particle>() / SPEED_OF_LIGHT};
73     const float_X spatialContribution = waveNumber * distance;
74     const float_X phase = spatialContribution + curPhase;
75
76     AssignPhase<T_Particle>::assign(particle, phase);
77 }
78
79 /* Initialize this functor
80 *
81 * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
82 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
83 * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
84 *
85 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
86 */
87 template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
88 HDINLINE void init(T_MetaData const& meta)
89 {
90 }
91
92 private:
93 PMACC_ALIGN(curPhase, float_64);
94 PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap, typename SideCfg::AxisSwapRT);
95 };
96 } // namespace initPhase
97 } // namespace externalBeam
98 } // namespace particles
99 } // namespace picongpu

```

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/PhotonFuncctors.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/externalBeam/phase/AssingPhase.hpp"
9
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12     namespace particles
13     {
14         namespace externalBeam
15         {
16             namespace initPhase
17             {
18                 template<typename T_ParamClass> struct FromPhotonMomentum
19                 {
20                     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
21                     {
22                         using type = FromPhotonMomentum<T_ParamClass>;
23                     };
24                     static constexpr float_64 phi0 = T_ParamClass::phi0;
25
26                     using SideCfg = typename T_ParamClass::ProbingBeam::SideCfg;
27                     template<uint32_t idx>
28                     using BeamToPicIdx_t =
29                         typename SideCfg::AxisSwapCT::template BeamToPicIdx<idx>::type;
30
31                     HINLINE FromPhotonMomentum(uint32_t currentStep)
32                     {
33                     }
34                     /* Set phase
35                     *
36                     * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
37                     * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
38                     * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
39                     * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
40                     * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
41                     *
42                     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
43                     * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
44                     * @param particle particle to be manipulated
45                     * @param ... unused particles
46                     */
47                     template<
48                         typename T_Acc,
49                         typename T_MetaData,
50                         typename T_Particle,
51                         typename... T_Args>
52                     DINLINE void operator()(

```

File 25. particles/externalBeam/phase/FromPhotonMomentum.hpp

```

53     T_Acc const& acc,
54     T_MetaData& meta,
55     T_Particle& particle,
56     T_Args&&...) const
57 {
58     const uint32_t currentStep = meta.m_currentStep;
59     float_X phase = precisionCast<float_X>(
60         GetPhaseByTimestep<T_Particle>(currentStep, particle, phi0));
61
62     static constexpr float_X cellSizeCT[3]
63         = {CELL_WIDTH, CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_DEPTH};
64     static constexpr float_X cellDepth{cellSizeCT[BeamToPicIdx_t<2u>::value]};
65
66     /* this functor will be called only in the first cell (counting from the
67     boundary where the photon beam enters the simulation. So global position
68     along the propagation axis is just the in cell position. */
69     const floatD_X position = particle[position_];
70     // distance from the z_beam=0 plane (the simulation boundary) where the
71     // position contribution to the plane wave phase is 0.
72     const float_X distance{(axisSwap.rotate(position)).z() * cellDepth};
73     const float_X waveNumber{GetAngFrequency<T_Particle>() / SPEED_OF_LIGHT};
74     const float_X spatialContribution = waveNumber * distance;
75     phase += spatialContribution;
76
77     AssignPhase<T_Particle>::assign(particle, phase);
78 }
79
80 /* Empty initialization
81 *
82 * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
83 * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
84 * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
85 *
86 * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
87 */
88 template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
89 HDINLINE void init(T_MetaData const& meta)
90 {
91 }
92
93 private:
94 PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap, typename SideCfg::AxisSwapRT);
95 };
96 } // namespace initPhase
97 } // namespace externalBeam
98 } // namespace particles
99 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 26. particles/externalBeam/phase/NoPhase.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 namespace picongpu
8 {
9     namespace particles
10    {
11        namespace externalBeam
12        {
13            namespace initPhase
14            {
15                struct NoPhase
16                {
17                    template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
18                    {
19                        using type = NoPhase;
20                    };
21
22                    HINLINE NoPhase(uint32_t currentStep)
23                    {
24                    }
25                    /* Do Nothing
26                    *
27                    * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
28                    * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
29                    * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
30                    * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
31                    * @tparam T_Args pmacc::Particle, arbitrary number of particles types
32                    *
33                    * @param acc alpaka accelerator
34                    * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
35                    * @param particle particle to be manipulated
36                    * @param ... unused particles
37                    */
38                template<
39                    typename T_Acc,
40                    typename T_MetaData,
41                    typename T_Particle,
42                    typename... T_Args>
43                DINLINE void operator()(
44                    T_Acc const& acc,
45                    T_MetaData& meta,
46                    T_Particle& particle,
47                    T_Args&&...) const
48                {
49                }
50
51                /* Empty initialization
52                *

```

```

53  * @tparam T_Particle pmacc::Particle, particle type
54  * @tparam T_MetaData type of the low level functor used to call the
55  * StartAttributes functor which calls this functor.
56  *
57  * @param meta the instance of T_MetaData, provides domain info and the rng.
58  */
59  template<typename T_Particle, typename T_MetaData>
60  HDINLINE void init(T_MetaData const& meta)
61  {
62  }
63  };
64  } // namespace initPhase
65  } // namespace externalBeam
66  } // namespace particles
67  } // namespace picongpu

```

File 27. particles/externalBeam/phase/NoPhase.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  namespace picongpu
6  {
7  namespace particles
8  {
9  namespace externalBeam
10 {
11 namespace initPhase
12 {
13 /* Don't set particle phase
14  *
15  */
16 struct NoPhase;
17
18 } // namespace initPhase
19 } // namespace externalBeam
20 } // namespace particles
21 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 28. particles/scattering/scattering.kernel

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once

```

```

4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/fields/CellType.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/fields/FieldB.hpp"
9  #include "picongpu/particles/traits/GetInterpolation.hpp"
10
11 #include <pmacc/mappings/threads/ThreadCollective.hpp>
12 #include <pmacc/memory/boxes/CachedBox.hpp>
13 #include <pmacc/traits/GetFlagType.hpp>
14
15 namespace picongpu
16 {
17 namespace particles
18 {
19 namespace scattering
20 {
21 namespace acc
22 {
23 /* Sum over an arbitrary nuber of values.
24  *
25  * The nuber of values to sum is known at compile time.
26  * This uses recursion (hopefully optimized out) since using
27  * std::index_sequence and std::tuple is not possible in device code.
28  */
29 struct SumDensity
30 {
31     /* summation result
32     float_X sum{0.0_X};
33
34     /* Add value to the sum.
35     *
36     * This implementation is directly called when there is only one value left.
37     */
38     template<typename T_Arg> HDINLINE void operator()(T_Arg const& arg)
39     {
40         sum += arg;
41     }
42
43     /* Implementation called for more than one value.
44     template<typename T_Arg, typename... T_Args>
45     HDINLINE void operator()(T_Arg const& arg, T_Args const&... args)
46     {
47         (*this)(arg);
48         (*this)(args...);
49     }
50     /* Used when there are no density fields
51     HDINLINE void operator>()
52     {
53     }
54 };
55
56 /* Device Kernel for scattering particles.

```

```

57  *
58  * @param acc alpaka accelerator
59  * @param mapper mapping description
60  * @param particleBox device side particle data
61  * @param hostScattererFunctor the functor for creating a device side scatter
62  * functor
63  * @param fieldBoxes an arbitrary number of fieldBoxes containing scatterer
64  * densities. These will be summed before passing to the scatterer functor.
65  */
66  template<uint32_t T_numWorkers> struct ScatterParticlesKernel
67  {
68      template<
69          typename T_Acc,
70          typename T_Mapper,
71          typename T_ParticleBox,
72          typename T_HostScattererFunctor,
73          typename... T_FieldBoxes>
74      DINLINE void operator()(
75          T_Acc& acc,
76          T_Mapper const mapper,
77          T_ParticleBox particleBox,
78          T_HostScattererFunctor hostScattererFunctor,
79          T_FieldBoxes... fieldBoxes) const
80      {
81          // get block cell
82          // shift fields
83          // CtxArray with SumDensity
84          // Write sums into shared memory
85          constexpr uint32_t numWorkers = T_numWorkers;
86          uint32_t const workerIdx = cupla::threadIdx(acc).x;
87          constexpr uint32_t frameSize
88              = pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value;
89          constexpr uint32_t cellsPerSuperCell = frameSize;
90          DataSpace<simDim> const superCellIdx
91              = mapper.getSuperCellIndex(DataSpace<simDim>(cupla::blockIdx(acc)));
92          DataSpace<simDim> const blockCell{superCellIdx * SuperCellSize::toRT()};
93          auto& superCell = particleBox.getSuperCell(superCellIdx);
94          const uint32_t numParticlesInSupercell = superCell.getNumParticles();
95          DataSpace<simDim> const localSuperCellOffset(
96              superCellIdx - mapper.getGuardingSuperCells());
97
98          // an array for scatterer density in shared memory
99          PMACC_SMEM(acc, densityArray, memory::Array<float_X, frameSize>);
100
101          auto forEachCellInSuperCell
102              = lockstep::makeForEach<cellsPerSuperCell, numWorkers>(workerIdx);
103          auto forEachParticleInFrame
104              = lockstep::makeForEach<frameSize, numWorkers>(workerIdx);
105
106          // An array with SumDensity object for each virtual worker.
107          auto SumDensityCtx = forEachCellInSuperCell([&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
108              { return SumDensity(); });
109          // Summ over all the scatterer densities passed to the kernel and store the

```

```

110          // result for each cell in the shared memory.
111          forEachCellInSuperCell(
112              [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
113              {
114                  auto const idxInSuperCell
115                      = DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::template map<SuperCellSize>(idx);
116                  SumDensityCtx[idx](
117                      (fieldBoxes.shift(blockCell)) (idxInSuperCell)[0]...);
118                  densityArray[idx] = SumDensityCtx[idx].sum;
119              });
120          cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
121
122          // An array with a device side scatterer for each virtual worker.
123          auto accScatteringFunctorCtx = forEachParticleInFrame(
124              [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
125              {
126                  return hostScattererFunctor(
127                      acc,
128                      localSuperCellOffset,
129                      forEachParticleInFrame.getWorkerCfg());
130              });
131
132          // Loop over particles in the super cell. Call the scatterer functor for
133          // each particle.
134          auto frame = particleBox.getFirstFrame(superCellIdx);
135          for(uint32_t i = 0; i < numParticlesInSupercell; i += frameSize)
136          {
137              forEachParticleInFrame(
138                  [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
139                  {
140                      if(i + idx < numParticlesInSupercell)
141                      {
142                          auto particle = frame[idx];
143                          // get the scatterer density for the particle cell
144                          const float_X cellDensity = densityArray[particle[localCellIdx_]];
145                          accScatteringFunctorCtx[idx](acc, particle, cellDensity);
146                      }
147                  });
148              frame = particleBox.getNextFrame(frame);
149          }
150      }
151  };
152
153  template<uint32_t T_numWorkers, typename T_Species>
154  struct ScatterParticlesWithBFieldKernel
155  {
156      template<
157          typename T_Acc,
158          typename T_Mapper,
159          typename T_ParticleBox,
160          typename T_HostScattererFunctor,
161          typename T_BFieldBox,
162          typename... T_FieldBoxes>

```

```

163  DINLINE void operator()(
164      T_Acc& acc,
165      T_Mapper const mapper,
166      T_ParticleBox particleBox,
167      T_HostScattererFunctor hostScattererFunctor,
168      T_BFieldBox bFieldBox,
169      T_FieldBoxes... fieldBoxes) const
170  {
171      // get block cell
172      // shift fields
173      // CtxArray with SumDensity
174      // Write sums into shared memory
175      constexpr uint32_t numWorkers = T_numWorkers;
176      uint32_t const workerIdx = cupla::threadIdx(acc).x;
177      constexpr uint32_t frameSize
178          = pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value;
179      constexpr uint32_t cellsPerSuperCell = frameSize;
180      DataSpace<simDim> const superCellIdx
181          = mapper.getSuperCellIndex(DataSpace<simDim>(cupla::blockIdx(acc)));
182      DataSpace<simDim> const blockCell{superCellIdx * SuperCellSize::toRT()};
183      auto& superCell = particleBox.getSuperCell(superCellIdx);
184      const uint32_t numParticlesInSupercell = superCell.getNumParticles();
185      DataSpace<simDim> const localSuperCellOffset(
186          superCellIdx - mapper.getGuardingSuperCells());
187
188      PMACC_SMEM(acc, densityArray, memory::Array<float_X, frameSize>);
189
190      using LowerMargin = typename GetLowerMargin<
191          typename GetInterpolation<T_Species>::type>::type;
192      using UpperMargin = typename GetUpperMargin<
193          typename GetInterpolation<T_Species>::type>::type;
194      using InterpolationBlockArea = SuperCellDescription<
195          typename MappingDesc::SuperCellSize,
196          LowerMargin,
197          UpperMargin>;
198      auto cachedB = CachedBox::create<0, typename T_BFieldBox::ValueType>(
199          acc,
200          InterpolationBlockArea());
201      cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
202      pmacc::math::operation::Assign assign;
203      ThreadCollective<InterpolationBlockArea, numWorkers> collective{workerIdx};
204      auto bFieldBlock = bFieldBox.shift(blockCell);
205      collective(acc, assign, cachedB, bFieldBlock);
206      cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
207
208      using FrameType = typename T_ParticleBox::FrameType;
209      using InterpolationFunctor = typename pmacc::traits::Resolve<
210          typename GetFlagType<FrameType, interpolation<>>::type>::type;
211      InterpolationFunctor interpolationFunctor;
212      const picongpu::traits::FieldPosition<fields::CellType, FieldB> fieldPosB;
213
214      auto forEachCellInSuperCell
215          = lockstep::makeForEach<cellsPerSuperCell, numWorkers>(workerIdx);

```

```

216      auto forEachParticleInFrame
217          = lockstep::makeForEach<frameSize, numWorkers>(workerIdx);
218
219      auto SumDensityCtx = forEachCellInSuperCell([&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
220          { return SumDensity(); });
221
222      forEachCellInSuperCell(
223          [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
224          {
225              auto const idxInSuperCell
226                  = DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::template map<SuperCellSize>(idx);
227              SumDensityCtx[idx](
228                  (fieldBoxes.shift(blockCell))(idxInSuperCell)[0]...);
229              densityArray[idx] = SumDensityCtx[idx].sum;
230          });
231
232      auto accScatteringFunctorCtx = forEachParticleInFrame(
233          [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
234          {
235              return hostScattererFunctor(
236                  acc,
237                  localSuperCellOffset,
238                  forEachParticleInFrame.getWorkerCfg());
239          });
240
241      auto frame = particleBox.getFirstFrame(superCellIdx);
242      for(uint32_t i = 0; i < numParticlesInSupercell; i += frameSize)
243      {
244          forEachParticleInFrame(
245              [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
246              {
247                  if(i + idx < numParticlesInSupercell)
248                  {
249                      auto particle = frame[idx];
250                      auto const particleCellIdx = particle[localCellIdx_];
251                      const float_X cellDensity = densityArray[particleCellIdx];
252                      const DataSpace<simDim> localCell{
253                          DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::template map<SuperCellSize>(
254                              particleCellIdx)};
255                      const float3_X bField = interpolationFunctor(
256                          cachedB.shift(localCell).toCursor(),
257                          particle[position_],
258                          fieldPosB());
259
260                      accScatteringFunctorCtx[idx](acc, particle, bField, cellDensity);
261                  }
262              });
263          frame = particleBox.getNextFrame(frame);
264      }
265  };
266  } // namespace acc
267  } // namespace scattering
268  } // namespace particles

```

```
269 } // namespace picongpu
```

File 29. particles/scattering/FaradayRotationFunctor.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/scattering.kernel"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/traits/GetInterpolation.hpp"
9
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12     namespace particles
13     {
14         namespace scattering
15         {
16             namespace acc
17             {
18                 struct FaradayRotationFunctor
19                 {
20                     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
21                     HDINLINE void operator()(
22                         T_Acc const& acc,
23                         T_Particle& particle,
24                         float3_X const& bField,
25                         float_X const& density)
26                     {
27                         // electron charge is negative (we need e so -ELECTRON_CHARGE)
28                         constexpr float_X integrationConstant = -ELECTRON_CHARGE * ELECTRON_CHARGE
29                             * ELECTRON_CHARGE / ELECTRON_MASS / ELECTRON_MASS / SPEED_OF_LIGHT
30                             / 2.0_X / EPSO;
31                         constexpr float_X propDistance = DELTA_T * SPEED_OF_LIGHT;
32
33                         const float3_X photonMomentum = particle[momentum_];
34                         const float3_X dir = photonMomentum / math::abs(photonMomentum);
35
36                         const float_X bFieldDir = pmacc::math::dot(bField, dir);
37                         const float_X densityPICUnits
38                             = density * particles::TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE;
39                         const float_X omega = particles::GetAngFrequency<T_Particle>()(particle);
40                         const float_X angleChange = densityPICUnits * bFieldDir / (omega * omega)
41                             * integrationConstant * propDistance;
42                         float_X newAngle = particle[polarizationAngle_] + angleChange;
43                         // keep the angle in the (-PI, PI] range
44                         constexpr float_X doublePi{pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::doubleValue};
45                         newAngle = math::fmod(newAngle + pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value, doublePi)

```

```

46         - pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value;
47         particle[polarizationAngle_] = newAngle;
48     }
49 };
50 } // namespace acc
51
52 template<typename T_DensityFields, typename T_Species>
53 struct FaradayRotationFunctorImpl
54 {
55     static constexpr bool needsFillGaps = false;
56
57     using RequiredDerivedFields = T_DensityFields;
58     using RequiredNativeFields = MakeSeq_t<FieldB>;
59
60     template<uint32_t T_numWorkers>
61     using CallingKernel =
62         typename acc::ScatterParticlesWithBFieldKernel<T_numWorkers, T_Species>;
63
64     HDINLINE FaradayRotationFunctorImpl(uint32_t const& currentStep)
65     {
66     }
67
68     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_WorkerCfg>
69     HDINLINE auto operator()(
70         T_Acc const& acc,
71         DataSpace<simDim> const& localSupercellOffset,
72         T_WorkerCfg const& workerCfg) const
73     {
74         return acc::FaradayRotationFunctor();
75     }
76 };
77 template<typename T_DensityFields, typename T_Species>
78 constexpr bool
79     FaradayRotationFunctorImpl<T_DensityFields, T_Species>::needsFillGaps;
80
81 template<typename T_DensityFields> struct FaradayRotationFunctor
82 {
83     template<typename T_Species> struct apply
84     {
85         using type = FaradayRotationFunctorImpl<T_DensityFields, T_Species>;
86     };
87 };
88 } // namespace scattering
89 } // namespace particles
90 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 30. particles/scattering/ScatterFunctor.hpp

```
1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
```

```

2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/detail/AdvanceScatteringCounter.hpp"
8 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/scattering.kernel"
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             template<typename T_ReferenceDistance> struct HandleDistanceDependence
16             {
17                 static constexpr float_X refDist
18                     = static_cast<float_X>(T_ReferenceDistance::value / UNIT_LENGTH);
19                 /* Handle distance dependence in scattering
20                 *
21                 * When scattering amplitudons, one needs to account for the fact that the
22                 * amplitude falls with 1/r and not with 1/r. The amplitudon scattering cross
23                 * section is proportional to the distance to the point towards which the
24                 * particle is scattered. Since this is unknown at the scattering itself the
25                 * scattering cross section is set with some reference distance l_0 instead.
26                 * From the 2nd scattering on the particle weighting is corrected by r/l_0,
27                 * where r is the distance to the last scattering point.
28                 */
29                 HDINLINE HandleDistanceDependence(uint32_t const& currentStep)
30                     : currentStep_m(currentStep){};
31
32                 /* Operator implementation. Run only if the scattering is happening.
33                 template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
34                 DINLINE void operator()(T_Acc const& acc, T_Particle& particle)
35                 {
36                     // The max value is reserved for when there was no event (scattering) yet.
37                     if(particle[lastEventStep_] != std::numeric_limits<uint32_t>::max())
38                     {
39                         const float_X distance
40                             = (particle[lastEventStep_] - currentStep_m) * SPEED_OF_LIGHT;
41                         particle[weighting_] *= distance / refDist;
42                     }
43                     // Update the last event.
44                     particle[lastEventStep_] = currentStep_m;
45                 }
46
47                 private:
48                 PMACC_ALIGN(currentStep_m, uint32_t);
49             };
50
51             /* Disable distance handling when T_ReferenceDistance is void.
52             template<> struct HandleDistanceDependence<void>
53             {
54                 HDINLINE HandleDistanceDependence(uint32_t const& currentStep){};

```

```

55
56     /* Empty operator implementation.
57     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
58     DINLINE void operator()(T_Acc const& acc, T_Particle& particle)
59     {
60     }
61 };
62
63 namespace acc
64 {
65     /* Device side scattering functor
66     template<
67         typename T_AccConditionFuncor,
68         typename T_AccDirectionFuncor,
69         typename T_HandleDistanceDependence>
70     struct ScatterFuncor
71     {
72         /* Constructor
73         * @param accConditionFuncor device side condition functor
74         * @param accDirectionFuncor device side direction functor
75         */
76         HDINLINE ScatterFuncor(
77             T_AccConditionFuncor const& accConditionFuncor,
78             T_AccDirectionFuncor const& accDirectionFuncor,
79             T_HandleDistanceDependence const& handleDistanceDependence)
80             : accConditionFuncor_m(accConditionFuncor)
81             , accDirectionFuncor_m(accDirectionFuncor)
82             , handleDistanceDependence_m(handleDistanceDependence)
83         {
84         }
85
86         /* Functor implementation
87         *
88         * @param acc alpaka accelerator
89         * @param particle particle to scatter
90         * @param density local scatterer density
91         */
92         template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
93         DINLINE void operator()(
94             T_Acc const& acc,
95             T_Particle& particle,
96             float_X const& density)
97         {
98             const bool condition = accConditionFuncor_m(acc, particle, density);
99             if(condition)
100             {
101                 accDirectionFuncor_m(acc, particle);
102                 // 180 degree phase shift (thomson scattering)
103                 if constexpr(pmacc::traits::HasFlag<
104                     typename T_Particle::FrameType,
105                     startPhase>::type::value)
106                 {
107                     const float_X phase

```

```

108     = particle[startPhase_] + pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value;
109     constexpr float_X twoPi = pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::doubleValue;
110     particle[startPhase_] = math::fmod(phase, twoPi);
111 }
112 scattering::detail::AdvanceScatteringCounter()(particle);
113 handleDistanceDependence_m(acc, particle);
114 }
115 }
116
117 private:
118 PMACC_ALIGN(accConditionFuncor_m, T_AccConditionFuncor);
119 PMACC_ALIGN(accDirectionFuncor_m, T_AccDirectionFuncor);
120 PMACC_ALIGN(handleDistanceDependence_m, T_HandleDistanceDependence);
121 };
122 } // namespace acc
123
124 template<
125     typename T_DensityFields,
126     typename T_ConditionFuncor,
127     typename T_DirectionFuncor,
128     typename T_ReferenceDistance>
129 struct ScatterFuncor
130 : private T_ConditionFuncor
131 , private T_DirectionFuncor
132 {
133     template<typename T_Species> struct apply
134     {
135         using type = ScatterFuncor<
136             T_DensityFields,
137             T_ConditionFuncor,
138             T_DirectionFuncor,
139             T_ReferenceDistance>;
140     };
141
142     // A different scatterer functor may delete particles, if so one would need
143     // to call fillGaps after the scatterer kernel is called. Here it is not
144     // needed.
145     static constexpr bool needsFillGaps = false;
146
147     template<uint32_t T_numWorkers>
148     using CallingKernel = acc::ScatterParticlesKernel<T_numWorkers>;
149
150     using RequiredDerivedFields = T_DensityFields;
151     using RequiredNativeFields = MakeSeq_t<>;
152
153     HINLINE ScatterFuncor(uint32_t const& currentStep)
154     : T_ConditionFuncor(currentStep)
155     , T_DirectionFuncor(currentStep)
156     , handleDistanceDependence(currentStep)
157     {
158     }
159
160     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_WorkerCfg>

```

```

161     HDINLINE auto operator()(
162         T_Acc const& acc,
163         DataSpace<simDim> const& localSupercellOffset,
164         T_WorkerCfg const& workerCfg) const
165     {
166         return acc::ScatterFuncor<
167             typename T_ConditionFuncor::AccFuncorType,
168             typename T_DirectionFuncor::AccFuncorType,
169             HandleDistanceDependence<T_ReferenceDistance>>>(
170             T_ConditionFuncor::operator()(acc, localSupercellOffset, workerCfg),
171             T_DirectionFuncor::operator()(acc, localSupercellOffset, workerCfg),
172             handleDistanceDependence);
173     }
174
175     private:
176     PMACC_ALIGN(
177         handleDistanceDependence,
178         HandleDistanceDependence<T_ReferenceDistance>);
179 };
180 template<
181     typename T_DensityFields,
182     typename T_ConditionFuncor,
183     typename T_DirectionFuncor,
184     typename T_ReferenceDistance>
185 constexpr bool ScatterFuncor<
186     T_DensityFields,
187     T_ConditionFuncor,
188     T_DirectionFuncor,
189     T_ReferenceDistance>::needsFillGaps;
190 } // namespace scattering
191 } // namespace particles
192 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 31. particles/scattering/functors.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/FaradayRotationFuncor.def"
6 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/ScatterFuncor.def"
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/SplitScatterer.def"
8 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/Always.def"
9 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/FixedProbability.def"
10 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/ProbLinToDens.def"
11 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/RandomThompson.def"
12 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/Threshold.def"
13 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/direction/Random.def"
14 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/direction/RandomThompson.def"

```

```

15 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/splitCondition/Always.def"
16 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/splitCondition/GenerationLimit.def"

```

File 32. particles/scattering/direction/Random.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.hpp"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace direction
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     template<typename T_ParamClass> struct Random
20                     {
21                         private:
22                         static constexpr float_X maxPolar = T_ParamClass::maxPolarAngle;
23                         static constexpr float_X minPolar = T_ParamClass::minPolarAngle;
24                         // using -pi, +pi instead of 0, 2pi has something to do with precision and
25                         // fast math
26                         static constexpr float_X minAzimuth = -pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value;
27                         static constexpr float_X maxAzimuth = pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value;
28
29                         public:
30                         template<typename T_rng, typename T_Particle>
31                         DINLINE void operator()(T_rng& rng, T_Particle& particle) const
32                         {
33                             /* Azimuth angle is the angle around the x-axis [0,2PI] and polar angle is
34                              * the angle around the z-axis [0-PI] Note that compared to e.g. wikipedia
35                              * the z and x axis are swapped as our usual propagation direction is X
36                              * but it does not influence anything as the axis can be arbitrarily named
37                              */
38                             float_X azimuthAngle
39                                 = rng() * float_X(maxAzimuth - minAzimuth) + float_X(minAzimuth);
40                             // To get an even distribution on a unit sphere we need to modify the
41                             // distribution of the polar angle using arccos.
42                             float_X polarAngle;
43                             // TODO: Calculate max angle this is valid for
44                             if(

```

```

45         std::is_same<float_X, float_32>::value && minPolar == 0.
46         && maxPolar <= 1e-2)
47     {
48         // For float32 we don't get small angles as we'd need to calculate the
49         // arccos around 1 where the possible float values are sparse. For small
50         // angle we can approximate the density distribution and arccos around 0,
51         // else we need to use double precision
52         polarAngle = math::sqrt<sqrt_X>(rng()) * maxPolar;
53     }
54     else
55     {
56         // Optimization with compile-time evaluated ternary for common case
57         const float_64 minPolarCos
58             = (minPolar == 0.) ? float_64(1.) : math::cos(float_64(minPolar));
59         const float_64 maxPolarCos = math::cos(float_64(maxPolar));
60         // Note that cos(minPolar)>=cos(maxPolar) for minPolar<=maxPolar
61         polarAngle = math::acos<float_64>(
62             rng() * (minPolarCos - maxPolarCos) + maxPolarCos);
63     }
64     /* Now we have the azimuth and polar angles by which we want to change the
65     * current direction. So we need some rotations: Assume old direction = A,
66     * new direction = B, |A| = 1 There is a rotation matrix R_A so that A =
67     * R_A * e_X (with e_X = [1,0,0] ) It is also easy to generate a rotation
68     * Matrix R_B which transforms a point in Cartesian coordinates by the
69     * azimuth and polar angle So we can say B = R_A * R_B * R_A^T * A (rotate
70     * A back to e_X, rotate by R_B and rotate again to As coordinate system)
71     * This can be simplified as R_A^T * A = e_X and R_B' = R_B * e_X =
72     * [cos(polar), sin(polar)*sin(azimuth), sin(polar)*cos(azimuth)]
73     * --> B = R_A * R_B'
74     * To get R_A we need to find how to rotate e_X to A which means a rotation
75     * with cos(a) = A*e_X (dot product) around A x e_X (cross product) Formula
76     * for the general case is on wikipedia but can be simplified with cos(a) =
77     * A_x, A_y^2 + A_z^2 = 1 - A_x^2 = sin^2(a) = (1
78     * + A_x)(1 - A_x) So finally one gets B = {x,-y,-z},
79     * {y,x+z^2/(1+x),-y*z/(1+x)},{+z,-y*z/(1+x),x+y^2/(1+x)}}*cos(t),
80     * sin(t)sin(p),sin(t)cos(p)}
81     * With x,y,z=A_x,..., t=polar, p=azimuth. This solved by Wolfram Alpha
82     * results in the following formulas
83     */
84
85     // TODO: what about 2D?
86     trigo_X sinPolar, cosPolar, sinAzimuth, cosAzimuth;
87     pmacc::math::sincos<trigo_X>(polarAngle, sinPolar, cosPolar);
88     pmacc::math::sincos<trigo_X>(azimuthAngle, sinAzimuth, cosAzimuth);
89     const float3_X p = particle[momentum_];
90     float3_X dir = p / math::sqrt(pmacc::math::abs2(p));
91     const float_X x = dir.x();
92     const float_X y = dir.y();
93     const float_X z = dir.z();
94     if(math::abs(1 + x) <= std::numeric_limits<float_X>::min())
95     {
96         // Special case: x=-1 --> y=z=0 (unit vector), so avoid division by zero
97         dir.x() = -cosPolar;

```

```

98     dir.y() = -sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
99     dir.z() = -cosAzimuth * sinPolar;
100 }
101 else
102 {
103     dir.x()
104     = x * cosPolar - z * cosAzimuth * sinPolar - y * sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
105     dir.y() = y * cosPolar - y * z / (1 + x) * cosAzimuth * sinPolar
106     + (x + z * z / (1 + x)) * sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
107     dir.z() = z * cosPolar + (x + y * y / (1 + x)) * cosAzimuth * sinPolar
108     - y * z / (1 + x) * sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
109 }
110 particle[momentum_] = dir * math::sqrt(pmacc::math::abs2(p));
111 }
112 };
113 } // namespace acc
114 } // namespace direction
115 } // namespace scattering
116 } // namespace particles
117 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 33. particles/scattering/direction/Random.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.def"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace direction
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     /* Scatter particles in a random direction
20                     *
21                     * Particles are uniformly scattered in a cone defined by the minimal and
22                     * maximal polar angle.
23                     * @tparam T_ParamClass param class with the polar angle limits
24                     *     Example:
25                     *     struct DirectionParam
26                     *     {

```

```

27     *         // unit are radians
28     *         static constexpr float_64 maxPolarAngle = 0.05;
29     *         static constexpr float_64 minPolarAngle = 0.0;
30     *     };
31     */
32     template<typename T_ParamClass> struct Random;
33 } // namespace acc
34
35 // TODO make the distribution precision an option
36 template<typename T_ParamClass>
37 using Random = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::FreeRng<
38     acc::Random<T_ParamClass>,
39     pmacc::random::distributions::Uniform<float_X>>;
40 } // namespace direction
41 } // namespace scattering
42 } // namespace particles
43 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 34. particles/scattering/direction/RandomThompson.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.hpp"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace direction
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     // TODO: combine with random, reuse functions.
20                     template<typename T_Rng_precision> struct RandomThompson
21                     {
22                         using float_R = T_Rng_precision;
23
24                         template<typename T_rng, typename T_Particle>
25                         DINLINE void operator()(T_rng& rng, T_Particle& particle) const
26                         {
27                             // the probability is the photon path in on step over the free path
28                             // length(sigma * n)
29

```

```

30  /* Azimuth angle is the angle around the x-axis [0,2PI) and polar angle is
31  * the angle around the z-axis [0-PI) Note that compared to e.g. wikipedia
32  * the z and x axis are swapped as our usual propagation direction is X
33  * but it does not influence anything as the axis can be arbitrarily named
34  */
35  // azimuth in -pi to pi range (fast math optimization)
36  trigo_X azimuthAngle = static_cast<trigo_X>(
37  rng() * pmacc::math::Pi<float_R>::doubleValue
38  - pmacc::math::Pi<float_R>::value);
39
40  float_R polarAngleCosine;
41  if(rng() < static_cast<float_R>(3.0 / 4.0))
42  {
43  polarAngleCosine = rng();
44  }
45  else
46  {
47  polarAngleCosine
48  = pmacc::math::max(pmacc::math::max(rng(), rng()), rng());
49  }
50  if(rng() > 0.5)
51  polarAngleCosine *= static_cast<float_R>(-1.0);
52  trigo_X polarAngle
53  = static_cast<trigo_X>(math::acos<float_64>(polarAngleCosine));
54
55  /* Now we have the azimuth and polar angles by which we want to change the
56  * current direction. So we need some rotations: Assume old direction = A,
57  * new direction = B, |A| = 1 There is a rotation matrix R_A so that A =
58  * R_A * e_X (with e_X = [1,0,0] ) It is also easy to generate a rotation
59  * Matrix R_B which transforms a point in Cartesian coordinates by the
60  * azimuth and polar angle So we can say B = R_A * R_B * R_A^T * A (rotate
61  * A back to e_X, rotate by R_B and rotate again to As coordinate system)
62  * This can be simplified as R_A^T * A = e_X and R_B' = R_B * e_X =
63  * [cos(polar), sin(polar)*sin(azimuth), sin(polar)*cos(azimuth)]
64  * --> B = R_A * R_B'
65  * To get R_A we need to find how to rotate e_X to A which means a rotation
66  * with cos(a) = A*e_X (dot product) around A x e_X (cross product) Formula
67  * for the general case is on wikipedia but can be simplified with cos(a) =
68  * A_x, A_y^2 + A_z^2 = 1 - A_x^2 = sin^2(a) = (1
69  * + A_x)(1 - A_x) So finally one gets B = {x,-y,-z},
70  * {y,x+z^2/(1+x),-y*z/(1+x)}, {+z,-y*z/(1+x),x+y^2/(1+x)}*{cos(t),
71  * sin(t)sin(p),sin(t)cos(p)}
72  * With x,y,z=A_x,..., t=polar, p=azimuth. This solved by Wolfram Alpha
73  * results in the following formulas
74  */
75
76  // TODO: what about 2D?
77  trigo_X sinPolar, cosPolar, sinAzimuth, cosAzimuth;
78  pmacc::math::sincos<trigo_X>(polarAngle, sinPolar, cosPolar);
79  pmacc::math::sincos<trigo_X>(azimuthAngle, sinAzimuth, cosAzimuth);
80  const float3_X p = particle[momentum_];
81  float3_X dir = p / math::sqrt(pmacc::math::abs2(p));
82  const float_X x = dir.x();

```

```

83  const float_X y = dir.y();
84  const float_X z = dir.z();
85  if(math::abs(1 + x) <= std::numeric_limits<float_X>::min())
86  {
87  // Special case: x=-1 --> y=z=0 (unit vector), so avoid division by zero
88  dir.x() = -cosPolar;
89  dir.y() = -sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
90  dir.z() = -cosAzimuth * sinPolar;
91  }
92  else
93  {
94  dir.x()
95  = x * cosPolar - z * cosAzimuth * sinPolar - y * sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
96  dir.y() = y * cosPolar - y * z / (1 + x) * cosAzimuth * sinPolar
97  + (x + z * z / (1 + x)) * sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
98  dir.z() = z * cosPolar + (x + y * y / (1 + x)) * cosAzimuth * sinPolar
99  - y * z / (1 + x) * sinAzimuth * sinPolar;
100 }
101 particle[momentum_] = dir * math::sqrt(pmacc::math::abs2(p));
102 }
103 };
104 } // namespace acc
105 } // namespace direction
106 } // namespace scattering
107 } // namespace particles
108 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 35. particles/scattering/direction/RandomThompson.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.def"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace direction
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 /* Scatter particles in a random direction
20  *

```

```

21  * Particles are uniformly scattered in a cone defined by the minimal and
22  * maximal polar angle.
23  * @tparam T_ParamClass param class with the polar angle limits
24  * Example:
25  *     struct DirectionParam
26  *     {
27  *         // unit are radians
28  *         static constexpr float_64 maxPolarAngle = 0.05;
29  *         static constexpr float_64 minPolarAngle = 0.0;
30  *     };
31  * @tparam alwaysInLimits if true the inLimits method will always return true
32  * if false this method will return true with a probability equal to the total
33  * probability of being scattered within the limits defined in the param class
34  * (assuming the Thompson scattering angular distribution).
35  */
36 template<typename T_Rng_precision> struct RandomThompson;
37 } // namespace acc
38
39 // TODO make the distribution precision an option
40 template<typename T_Rng_precision = float_64>
41 using RandomThompson = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::FreeRng<
42     acc::RandomThompson<T_Rng_precision>,
43     pmacc::random::distributions::Uniform<T_Rng_precision>>;
44 } // namespace direction
45 } // namespace scattering
46 } // namespace particles
47 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 36. particles/scattering/FaradayRotationFunctor.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6  namespace picongpu
7  {
8  namespace particles
9  {
10 namespace scattering
11 {
12 template<typename T_DensityFields> struct FaradayRotationFunctor;
13 } // namespace scattering
14 } // namespace particles
15 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 37. particles/scattering/detail/CheckMaxScattering.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.hpp"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace detail
16 {
17 template<uint32_t maxScattering> struct CheckMaxScattering
18 {
19     template<typename T_Particle>
20     DINLINE static bool check(T_Particle const& particle)
21     {
22         return particle[timesScattered_] < maxScattering;
23     }
24 };
25
26 template<> struct CheckMaxScattering<0u>
27 {
28     template<typename T_Particle>
29     DINLINE static bool check(T_Particle const& particle)
30     {
31         return true;
32     }
33 };
34 } // namespace detail
35 } // namespace scattering
36 } // namespace particles
37 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 38. particles/scattering/detail/AdvanceScatteringCounter.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"

```

```

6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.hpp"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace detail
16 {
17 struct AdvanceScatteringCounter
18 {
19     template<typename T_Particle>
20     DINLINE void operator()(T_Particle& particle) const
21     {
22         if constexpr(pmacc::traits::HasIdentifier<
23             typename T_Particle::FrameType,
24             timesScattered>::type::value)
25         {
26             particle[timesScattered_] += 1u;
27         }
28     }
29 };
30 } // namespace detail
31 } // namespace scattering
32 } // namespace particles
33 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 39. particles/scattering/condition/Always.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.def"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace condition
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {

```

```

19 /* Scattering condition functor: particle is always scattered.
20 *
21 * Particles are scattered at each step regardless of the local scatterer
22 * density.
23 */
24 template<uint32_t maxScattering> struct Always;
25 } // namespace acc
26
27 template<uint32_t maxScattering = 0>
28
29 using Always
30 = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::Free<acc::Always<maxScattering>>;
31 } // namespace condition
32 } // namespace scattering
33 } // namespace particles
34 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 40. particles/scattering/condition/ProbLinToDens.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.def"
6
7 namespace picongpu
8 {
9 namespace particles
10 {
11 namespace scattering
12 {
13 namespace condition
14 {
15 namespace acc
16 {
17 /* Scattering probability linearly proportional to scatterer density.
18 *
19 *  $p = a * n$ , with  $p$  - probability,  $a$  - factor,  $n$  - number density in
20 * PICongGPU units;
21 * @tparam T_ParamClass param class with the proportionality factor
22 *     propFactor.
23 *     Example:
24 *     @code{c++}
25 *     struct Param
26 *     {
27 *         static constexpr float_X propFactor = 0.1_X;
28 *     };
29 *     @endcode
30 */

```



```

28  */
29  template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering>
30  struct FixedProbability;
31  } // namespace acc
32
33  template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering = 0>
34  using FixedProbability = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::FreeRng<
35  acc::FixedProbability<T_ParamClass, maxScattering>,
36  pmacc::random::distributions::Uniform<float_X>>;
37  } // namespace condition
38  } // namespace scattering
39  } // namespace particles
40  } // namespace picongpu

```

File 43. particles/scattering/condition/Threshold.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/detail/CheckMaxScattering.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.hpp"
9
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12 namespace particles
13 {
14 namespace scattering
15 {
16 namespace condition
17 {
18 namespace acc
19 {
20 template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering> struct Threshold
21 {
22     using ParamClass = T_ParamClass;
23     static constexpr float_X threshold
24     = ParamClass::threshold * UNIT_LENGTH * UNIT_LENGTH * UNIT_LENGTH;
25     using CheckMax = detail::CheckMaxScattering<maxScattering>;
26
27     /* decide if a particle should be scattered
28     *
29     * @tparam T_Particle species type
30     * @tparam T_rng random number generator type
31     *
32     * @param random number generator
33     * @param particle that could be scattered

```

```

34     * @param density local scatterer density (in terms of
35     * TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE)
36     */
37     template<typename T_Particle>
38     DINLINE bool operator()(T_Particle const& particle, float_X const& density)
39     const
40     {
41         if(!CheckMax::check(particle))
42             return false;
43         return (
44             density * particles::TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE
45             > threshold);
46     }
47 };
48 } // namespace acc
49 } // namespace condition
50 } // namespace scattering
51 } // namespace particles
52 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 44. particles/scattering/condition/Threshold.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.def"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace condition
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 /* Scatter particles if scatterer density is above a threshold
20 *
21 * @tparam T_ParamClass param class with the threshold value
22 * Example:
23 * @code{c++}
24 * struct Param
25 * {
26 *     static constexpr float_64 threshold = 1.e25;
27 * };

```

```

28  *      @endcode
29  *
30  */
31  template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering> struct Threshold;
32  } // namespace acc
33
34  template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering = 0>
35  using Threshold = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::Free<
36  acc::Threshold<T_ParamClass, maxScattering>>;
37  } // namespace condition
38  } // namespace scattering
39  } // namespace particles
40  } // namespace picongpu

```

File 45. particles/scattering/condition/Always.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/detail/CheckMaxScattering.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.hpp"
9
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12 namespace particles
13 {
14 namespace scattering
15 {
16 namespace condition
17 {
18 namespace acc
19 {
20 template<uint32_t maxScattering> struct Always
21 {
22     using CheckMax = detail::CheckMaxScattering<maxScattering>;
23
24     /* decide if a particle should be scattered
25     *
26     * @tparam T_Particle species type
27     *
28     * @param particle particle that could be scattered
29     * @param density local scatterer density (in terms of
30     * TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE)
31     */
32     template<typename T_Particle>
33     DINLINE bool operator()(T_Particle const& particle, float_X const& density)

```

```

34     const
35     {
36         if(!CheckMax::check(particle))
37             return false;
38         return true;
39     }
40 };
41 } // namespace acc
42 } // namespace condition
43 } // namespace scattering
44 } // namespace particles
45 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 46. particles/scattering/condition/FixedProbability.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/detail/CheckMaxScattering.hpp"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace condition
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering> struct FixedProbability
20 {
21     using CheckMax = detail::CheckMaxScattering<maxScattering>;
22
23     /* decide if a particle should be scattered
24     *
25     * @tparam T_Particle species type
26     * @tparam T_rng random number generator type
27     *
28     * @param random number generator
29     * @param particle particle that could be scattered
30     * @param density local scatterer density (in terms of
31     * TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE)
32     */
33     template<typename T_rng, typename T_Particle>
34     DINLINE bool operator()(

```

```

35     T_rng& rng,
36     T_Particle const& particle,
37     float_X const& density) const
38 {
39     if(!CheckMax::check(particle))
40         return false;
41     return (rng() < T_ParamClass::probability);
42 }
43 };
44 } // namespace acc
45 } // namespace condition
46 } // namespace scattering
47 } // namespace particles
48 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 47. particles/scattering/condition/RandomThompson.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/detail/CheckMaxScattering.hpp"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace condition
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering> struct RandomThompson
20                     {
21                         static constexpr float_X totalCrossSection = static_cast<float_X>(
22                             T_ParamClass::totalCrossSection_SI / UNIT_LENGTH / UNIT_LENGTH);
23                         using CheckMax = detail::CheckMaxScattering<maxScattering>;
24
25                         /* decide if a particle should be scattered
26                          *
27                          * @tparam T_Particle species type
28                          * @tparam T_rng random number generator type
29                          *
30                          * @param random number generator
31                          * @param particle particle that could be scattered
32                          * @param density local scatterer density (in terms of

```

```

33     * TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE)
34     */
35     template<typename T_rng, typename T_Particle>
36     DINLINE bool operator()(
37         T_rng& rng,
38         T_Particle const& particle,
39         float_X const& density) const
40     {
41         if(!CheckMax::check(particle))
42             return false;
43         const float_X probability{
44             DELTA_T * SPEED_OF_LIGHT * totalCrossSection * density
45             * particles::TYPICAL_NUM_PARTICLES_PER_MACROPARTICLE};
46         return (rng() < probability);
47     }
48 };
49 } // namespace acc
50 } // namespace condition
51 } // namespace scattering
52 } // namespace particles
53 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 48. particles/scattering/condition/RandomThompson.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.def"
6
7  namespace picongpu
8  {
9     namespace particles
10    {
11        namespace scattering
12        {
13            namespace condition
14            {
15                namespace acc
16                {
17                    /* Scattering probability from a total cross section
18                     *
19                     * The probability is the distance a particle travels in one step
20                     * over the free path length(sigma * n). Sigma is the total cross section.
21                     *
22                     * @tparam T_ParamClass param class providing the total cross section.
23                     * Example:
24                     * @code{c++}
25                     * struct Param

```

```

26 *      {
27 *          // Thompson scattering total cross section
28 *          // unit is m^{-2}
29 *          static constexpr float_64 totalCrossSection = 6.65e-29;
30 *      };
31 *
32 */
33 template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering> struct RandomThompson;
34 } // namespace acc
35
36 template<typename T_ParamClass, uint32_t maxScattering = 0>
37 using RandomThompson = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::FreeRng<
38     acc::RandomThompson<T_ParamClass, maxScattering>,
39     pmacc::random::distributions::Uniform<float_X>>;
40 } // namespace condition
41 } // namespace scattering
42 } // namespace particles
43 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 49. particles/scattering/ScatterFunctor.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6  namespace picongpu
7  {
8  namespace particles
9  {
10 namespace scattering
11 {
12 /* Host side scattering functor
13 *
14 * Creates the device side functor which scatters a particle if the conditions
15 * functor returns true. The scattering itself is done by the direction
16 * functor.
17 *
18 * @tparam T_ConditionFuncor
19 * @tparam T_DirectionFuncor
20 */
21 template<
22     typename T_DensityFields,
23     typename T_ConditionFuncor,
24     typename T_DirectionFuncor,
25     typename T_ReferenceDistance = void>
26 struct ScatterFunctor;
27 } // namespace scattering
28 } // namespace particles

```

```

29 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 50. particles/scattering/SplitScatterer.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6  namespace picongpu
7  {
8  namespace particles
9  {
10 namespace scattering
11 {
12 template<
13     typename T_DensityFields,
14     typename T_ConditionFuncor,
15     typename T_SplitConditionFuncor,
16     typename T_DirectionFuncor,
17     typename T_ReferenceDistance,
18     uint32_t maxNewParticlesOnSplit>
19 struct SplitScatterer;
20 } // namespace scattering
21 } // namespace particles
22 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 51. particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Rene Widera */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include <boost/mpl/integral_c.hpp>
8  #include <boost/mpl/placeholders.hpp>
9
10 namespace picongpu
11 {
12 namespace particles
13 {
14 namespace scattering
15 {

```

```

16 namespace generic
17 {
18 /** call simple free user defined functor and provide a random number generator
19 *
20 *
21 * @tparam T_Functor user defined unary functor
22 * @tparam T_Distribution pmacc::random::distributions, random number
23 * distribution
24 */
25 template<typename T_Functor, typename T_Distribution> struct FreeRng;
26
27 } // namespace generic
28 } // namespace scattering
29 } // namespace particles
30 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 52. particles/scattering/generic/Free.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2013-2021 Rene Widera, Axel Huebl */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/generic/Free.def"
8
9 #include <type_traits>
10 #include <utility>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14 namespace particles
15 {
16 namespace scattering
17 {
18 namespace generic
19 {
20 namespace acc
21 {
22 /** wrapper for the user functor on the accelerator
23 *
24 * @tparam T_Functor user defined functor
25 */
26 template<typename T_Functor> struct Free : private T_Functor
27 {
28 ///! type of the user functor
29 using Functor = T_Functor;
30
31 ///! store user functor instance

```

```

32 HDINLINE Free(Functor const& functor) : Functor(functor)
33 {
34 }
35
36 /** execute the user functor
37 *
38 * @tparam T_Args type of the arguments passed to the user functor
39 * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
40 *
41 * @param alpaka accelerator
42 * @param args arguments passed to the user functor
43 */
44 template<typename... T_Args, typename T_Acc>
45 HDINLINE auto operator()(T_Acc const&, T_Args&&... args)
46 {
47     return Functor::operator()(args...);
48 }
49 };
50 } // namespace acc
51
52 template<typename T_Functor> struct Free : protected T_Functor
53 {
54     using Functor = T_Functor;
55     using AccFunctorType = acc::Free<Functor>;
56
57     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
58     {
59         using type = Free;
60     };
61
62 /** constructor
63 *
64 * This constructor is only compiled if the user functor has
65 * a host side constructor with one (uint32_t) argument.
66 *
67 * @tparam DeferFunctor is used to defer the functor type evaluation to
68 * enable/disable the constructor
69 * @param currentStep current simulation time step
70 * @param is used to enable/disable the constructor (do not pass any value to
71 * this parameter)
72 */
73 template<typename DeferFunctor = Functor>
74 HDINLINE Free(
75     uint32_t currentStep,
76     typename std::enable_if<
77         std::is_constructible<DeferFunctor, uint32_t::value::type* = 0>
78         : Functor(currentStep)
79     {
80     }
81
82 /** constructor
83 *
84 * This constructor is only compiled if the user functor has a default

```

```

85  * constructor.
86  *
87  * @tparam DeferFuncor is used to defer the functor type evaluation to
88  * enable/disable the constructor
89  * @param current simulation time step
90  * @param is used to enable/disable the constructor (do not pass any value to
91  * this parameter)
92  */
93  template<typename DeferFuncor = Functor>
94  HDINLINE Free(
95      uint32_t,
96      typename std::enable_if<
97          std::is_constructible<DeferFuncor>::value::type* = 0)
98      : Functor()
99  {
100 }
101
102 /** create device functor
103  *
104  * @tparam T_WorkerCfg lockstep::Worker, configuration of the worker
105  * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
106  *
107  * @param alpaka accelerator
108  * @param offset (in supercells, without any guards) to the
109  * origin of the local domain
110  * @param configuration of the worker
111  */
112  template<typename T, typename T_WorkerCfg, typename T_Acc>
113  HDINLINE acc::Free<Funcor> operator()(
114      T_Acc const& acc,
115      T const&,
116      T_WorkerCfg const&) const
117  {
118      return acc::Free<Funcor>(*static_cast<Funcor const*>(this));
119  }
120 };
121
122 } // namespace generic
123 } // namespace scattering
124 } // namespace particles
125 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 53. particles/scattering/generic/Free.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Rene Widera */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  namespace picongpu

```

```

6  {
7  namespace particles
8  {
9  namespace scattering
10 {
11 namespace generic
12 {
13 /** call simple free user defined functor
14  *
15  * @tparam T_Functor user defined functor
16  * **optional**: can implement **one** host side constructor
17  * `T_Functor()` or `T_Functor(uint32_t currentTimeStep)`
18  */
19  template<typename T_Functor> struct Free;
20
21 } // namespace generic
22 } // namespace scattering
23 } // namespace particles
24 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 54. particles/scattering/generic/FreeRng.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Rene Widera, Alexander Grund */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/functor/misc/Rng.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/startPosition/generic/FreeRng.def"
9
10 #include <string>
11 #include <type_traits>
12 #include <utility>
13
14 namespace picongpu
15 {
16 namespace particles
17 {
18 namespace scattering
19 {
20 namespace generic
21 {
22 namespace acc
23 {
24 template<typename T_Functor, typename T_RngType>
25 struct FreeRng : private T_Functor
26 {
27     using Functor = T_Functor;

```

```

28 using RngType = T_RngType;
29
30 HDINLINE FreeRng(Funcor const& functor, RngType const& rng)
31 : T_Functor(functor)
32 , m_rng(rng)
33 {
34 }
35
36 /** call user functor
37 *
38 * The random number generator is initialized with the first call.
39 *
40 * @tparam T_Particle type of the particle to manipulate
41 * @tparam T_Args type of the arguments passed to the user functor
42 * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
43 *
44 * @param alpaka accelerator
45 * @param particle particle which is given to the user functor
46 * @return void is used to enable the operator if the user functor except two
47 * arguments
48 */
49 template<typename T_Particle, typename... T_Args, typename T_Acc>
50 HDINLINE auto operator()(
51     T_Acc const&,
52     T_Particle& particle,
53     T_Args&&... args)
54 {
55     return Functor::operator()(m_rng, particle, args...);
56 }
57
58 private:
59     RngType m_rng;
60 };
61 } // namespace acc
62
63 template<typename T_Functor, typename T_Distribution>
64 struct FreeRng
65 : protected T_Functor
66 , private picongpu::particles::functor::misc::Rng<T_Distribution>
67 {
68     template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct apply
69     {
70         using type = FreeRng;
71     };
72
73     using RngGenerator = picongpu::particles::functor::misc::Rng<T_Distribution>;
74     using RngType = typename RngGenerator::RandomGen;
75
76     using Functor = T_Functor;
77     using Distribution = T_Distribution;
78     using AccFuncorType = acc::FreeRng<Funcor, RngType>;
79
80 /** constructor

```

```

81 *
82 * This constructor is only compiled if the user functor has
83 * a host side constructor with one (uint32_t) argument.
84 *
85 * @tparam DeferFuncor is used to defer the functor type evaluation to
86 * enable/disable the constructor
87 * @param currentStep current simulation time step
88 * @param is used to enable/disable the constructor (do not pass any value to
89 * this parameter)
90 */
91 template<typename DeferFuncor = Funcor>
92 HDINLINE FreeRng(
93     uint32_t currentStep,
94     typename std::enable_if<
95         std::is_constructible<DeferFuncor, uint32_t::value::type* = 0>
96     > Funcor(currentStep)
97     , RngGenerator(currentStep)
98     {
99     }
100
101 /** constructor
102 *
103 * This constructor is only compiled if the user functor has a default
104 * constructor.
105 *
106 * @tparam DeferFuncor is used to defer the functor type evaluation to
107 * enable/disable the constructor
108 * @param currentStep simulation time step
109 * @param is used to enable/disable the constructor (do not pass any value to
110 * this parameter)
111 */
112 template<typename DeferFuncor = Funcor>
113 HDINLINE FreeRng(
114     uint32_t currentStep,
115     typename std::enable_if<
116         std::is_constructible<DeferFuncor>::value::type* = 0>
117     > Funcor()
118     , RngGenerator(currentStep)
119     {
120     }
121
122 /** create functor for the accelerator
123 *
124 * @tparam T_WorkerCfg lockstep::Worker, configuration of the worker
125 * @tparam T_Acc alpaka accelerator type
126 *
127 * @param alpaka accelerator
128 * @param localSupercellOffset offset (in superCells, without any guards)
129 * relative to the origin of the local domain
130 * @param workerCfg configuration of the worker
131 */
132 template<typename T_WorkerCfg, typename T_Acc>
133 HDINLINE auto operator()(

```

```

134     T_Acc const& acc,
135     DataSpace<simDim> const& localSupercellOffset,
136     T_WorkerCfg const& workerCfg) const -> acc::FreeRng<Funcor, RngType>
137 {
138     RngType const rng = (*static_cast<RngGenerator const*>(
139         this)) (acc, localSupercellOffset, workerCfg);
140
141     return acc::FreeRng<Funcor, RngType>(
142         *static_cast<Funcor const*>(this),
143         rng);
144 }
145
146 static HINLINE std::string getName()
147 {
148     return std::string("FreeRNG");
149 }
150 };
151
152 } // namespace generic
153 } // namespace scattering
154 } // namespace particles
155 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 55. particles/scattering/SplitScatterer.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/SplitAndScatterParticles.kernel"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/detail/AdvanceScatteringCounter.hpp"
9
10 #include <pmacc/particles/operations/Assign.hpp>
11 #include <pmacc/particles/operations/Deselect.hpp>
12
13 namespace picongpu
14 {
15     namespace particles
16     {
17         namespace scattering
18         {
19             namespace acc
20             {
21                 template<
22                     typename T_AccConditionFuncor,
23                     typename T_AccSplitConditionFuncor,
24                     typename T_AccDirectionFuncor,

```

```

25     typename T_HandleDistanceDependence,
26     uint32_t t_newParticlesOnSplit>
27     struct SplitScatterer
28     {
29         static constexpr uint32_t newParticlesOnSplit = t_newParticlesOnSplit;
30
31         HDINLINE SplitScatterer(
32             T_AccConditionFuncor const& accConditionFuncor,
33             T_AccSplitConditionFuncor const& accSplitConditionFuncor,
34             T_AccDirectionFuncor const& accDirectionFuncor,
35             T_HandleDistanceDependence const& handleDistanceDependence)
36             : accConditionFuncor_m(accConditionFuncor)
37             , accSplitConditionFuncor_m(accSplitConditionFuncor)
38             , accDirectionFuncor_m(accDirectionFuncor)
39             , handleDistanceDependence_m(handleDistanceDependence)
40         {
41         }
42
43         template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
44         DINLINE bool scatteringCondition(
45             T_Acc const& acc,
46             T_Particle& particle,
47             float_X const& density)
48         {
49             return accConditionFuncor_m(acc, particle, density);
50         }
51
52         template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
53         DINLINE bool splittingCondition(T_Acc const& acc, T_Particle& particle)
54         {
55             return accSplitConditionFuncor_m(acc, particle);
56         }
57
58         template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
59         DINLINE void scatterSingle(T_Acc const& acc, T_Particle& particle)
60         {
61             accDirectionFuncor_m(acc, particle);
62             if constexpr(pmacc::traits::HasFlag<
63                 typename T_Particle::FrameType,
64                 startPhase>::type::value)
65             {
66                 const float_X phase
67                     = particle[startPhase_] + pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value;
68                 constexpr float_X twoPi = pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::doubleValue;
69                 particle[startPhase_] = math::fmod(phase, twoPi);
70             }
71             scattering::detail::AdvanceScatteringCounter()(particle);
72             handleDistanceDependence_m(acc, particle);
73         }
74
75         template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
76         DINLINE void split(
77             T_Acc const& acc,

```

```

78     uint32_t id,
79     T_Particle& sourceParticle,
80     T_Particle& newParticle)
81
82 {
83     const float_X newWeighting
84         = sourceParticle[weighting_] / (newParticlesOnSplit + 1u);
85     using namespace pmacc::particles::operations;
86     assign(
87         newParticle,
88         deselect<bmpl::vector<particleId, multiMask>>(sourceParticle));
89     scatterSingle(acc, newParticle);
90     newParticle[multiMask_] = 1;
91     newParticle[weighting_] = newWeighting;
92     if constexpr(pmacc::traits::HasIdentifier<
93         typename T_Particle::FrameType,
94         generation>::type::value)
95     {
96         newParticle[generation_] += 1;
97     }
98 }
99
100 template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
101 DINLINE void afterSplit(T_Acc const& acc, T_Particle& sourceParticle)
102
103 {
104     const float_X newWeighting
105         = sourceParticle[weighting_] / (newParticlesOnSplit + 1u);
106     scatterSingle(acc, sourceParticle);
107     sourceParticle[weighting_] = newWeighting;
108 }
109
110 private:
111 PMACC_ALIGN(accConditionFunc_m, T_AccConditionFunc);
112 PMACC_ALIGN(accDirectionFunc_m, T_AccDirectionFunc);
113 PMACC_ALIGN(accSplitConditionFunc_m, T_AccSplitConditionFunc);
114 PMACC_ALIGN(handleDistanceDependence_m, T_HandleDistanceDependence);
115 };
116
117 } // namespace acc
118
119 template<
120     typename T_DensityFields,
121     typename T_ConditionFunc,
122     typename T_SplitConditionFunc,
123     typename T_DirectionFunc,
124     typename T_ReferenceDistance,
125     uint32_t t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>
126 struct SplitScatterer
127     : private T_ConditionFunc
128     , private T_DirectionFunc
129     , private T_SplitConditionFunc
130 {

```

```

131     template<typename T_Species> struct apply
132     {
133         using type = SplitScatterer<
134             T_DensityFields,
135             T_ConditionFunc,
136             T_SplitConditionFunc,
137             T_DirectionFunc,
138             T_ReferenceDistance,
139             t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>;
140     };
141     static constexpr bool needsFillGaps = true;
142     static constexpr uint32_t maxNewParticlesOnSplit = t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit;
143
144     using RequiredDerivedFields = T_DensityFields;
145     using RequiredNativeFields = MakeSeq_t<>;
146     template<uint32_t T_numWorkers>
147     using CallingKernel = acc::SplitAndScatterParticlesKernel<T_numWorkers>;
148
149     HINLINE SplitScatterer(uint32_t const& currentStep)
150         : T_ConditionFunc(currentStep)
151         , T_DirectionFunc(currentStep)
152         , T_SplitConditionFunc(currentStep)
153         , handleDistanceDependence(currentStep)
154     {
155     }
156
157     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_WorkerCfg>
158     HDINLINE auto operator()(
159         T_Acc const& acc,
160         DataSpace<simDim> const& localSupercellOffset,
161         T_WorkerCfg const& workerCfg) const
162     {
163         return acc::SplitScatterer<
164             typename T_ConditionFunc::AccFuncType,
165             typename T_SplitConditionFunc::AccFuncType,
166             typename T_DirectionFunc::AccFuncType,
167             HandleDistanceDependence<T_ReferenceDistance>,
168             t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>(
169             T_ConditionFunc::operator()(acc, localSupercellOffset, workerCfg),
170             T_SplitConditionFunc::operator()(
171                 acc,
172                 localSupercellOffset,
173                 workerCfg),
174             T_DirectionFunc::operator()(acc, localSupercellOffset, workerCfg),
175             handleDistanceDependence);
176     }
177
178     private:
179     PMACC_ALIGN(
180         handleDistanceDependence,
181         HandleDistanceDependence<T_ReferenceDistance>);
182 };
183

```

```

184 template<
185     typename T_DensityFields,
186     typename T_ConditionFuncor,
187     typename T_SplitConditionFuncor,
188     typename T_DirectionFuncor,
189     typename T_ReferenceDistance,
190     uint32_t t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>
191 constexpr bool SplitScatterer<
192     T_DensityFields,
193     T_ConditionFuncor,
194     T_SplitConditionFuncor,
195     T_DirectionFuncor,
196     T_ReferenceDistance,
197     t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>::needsFillGaps;
198
199 template<
200     typename T_DensityFields,
201     typename T_ConditionFuncor,
202     typename T_SplitConditionFuncor,
203     typename T_DirectionFuncor,
204     typename T_ReferenceDistance,
205     uint32_t t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>
206 constexpr uint32_t SplitScatterer<
207     T_DensityFields,
208     T_ConditionFuncor,
209     T_SplitConditionFuncor,
210     T_DirectionFuncor,
211     T_ReferenceDistance,
212     t_maxNewParticlesOnSplit>::maxNewParticlesOnSplit;
213
214 } // namespace scattering
215 } // namespace particles
216 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 56. particles/scattering/CallScatterer.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/SplitAndScatterParticles.kernel"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/scattering.kernel"
9
10 #include <pmacc/traits/GetFlagType.hpp>
11
12 #include <functional>
13 #include <tuple>

```

```

14 #include <utility>
15
16 namespace picongpu
17 {
18     namespace particles
19     {
20         namespace scattering
21         {
22             namespace detail
23             {
24                 /* Get a FieldTmp pointer
25                  *
26                  * @tparam i FieldTmp slot id
27                  */
28                 template<size_t i> struct GetFieldTmp
29                 {
30                     /* Functor implementation
31                      *
32                      * @param dc data connector
33                      */
34                     template<typename T_Dc>
35                     HINLINE std::shared_ptr<FieldTmp> operator()(T_Dc& dc) const
36                     {
37                         return dc.template get<FieldTmp>(FieldTmp::getUniqueId(i), true);
38                     }
39                 };
40
41                 template<typename T_NativeFields, size_t i> struct GetNativeField
42                 {
43                     using Field = typename bmpl::at_c<T_NativeFields, i>::type;
44                     template<typename T_Dc>
45                     HINLINE std::shared_ptr<Field> operator()(T_Dc& dc) const
46                     {
47                         return dc.template get<Field>(Field::getName(), true);
48                     }
49                 };
50
51                 template<typename T_NativeFields> struct GetNativeFieldsPointersTupleImpl
52                 {
53                     template<typename T_Dc, std::size_t... I>
54                     HINLINE auto operator()(T_Dc& dc, std::index_sequence<I...>) const
55                     {
56                         return std::make_tuple(GetNativeField<T_NativeFields, I>()(dc)...);
57                     }
58                 };
59
60                 template<typename T_Dc, std::size_t... I>
61                 HINLINE auto getTmpFieldPointersTuple(T_Dc& dc, std::index_sequence<I...>)
62                 {
63                     return std::make_tuple(GetFieldTmp<I>()(dc)...);
64                 }
65
66                 /* Get a std::tuple of device side data boxes

```

```

67  *
68  * @tparam T_Tuple field pointers tuple type
69  * @tparam I ids of the fields in the provided tuple for witch a databox should
70  * be included
71  *
72  * @param fieldPointers A tuple with field pointers
73  * @param the index sequence containing I
74  */
75  template<typename T_Tuple, std::size_t... I>
76  HINLINE auto getDataBoxTuple(T_Tuple& fieldPointers, std::index_sequence<I...>)
77  {
78      return std::make_tuple((std::get<I>(fieldPointers)
79                              ->getGridBuffer()
80                              .getDeviceBuffer()
81                              .getDataBox())...);
82  }
83
84  /* Compute field values for an element from a list of FieldTmp operations.
85  *
86  * @tparam T_FieldTmpOperations A list FieldTmp operations
87  * @tparam extraTmpSlot fieldTmp memory slot to use for intermediary results
88  * @tparam i The index in the operation list for which the computeValue should
89  * be called
90  */
91  template<typename T_FieldTmpOperations, uint32_t extraTmpSlot, size_t i>
92  struct ComputeFieldValuesImpl
93  {
94      using FieldTmpOp = typename bmpl::at_c<T_FieldTmpOperations, i>::type;
95      using Species = typename FieldTmpOp::Species;
96      using Solver = typename FieldTmpOp::Solver;
97      using Filter = typename FieldTmpOp::Filter;
98
99      /* Functor implementation
100     *
101     * @param dc data conector
102     * @param currentStep current simulation step
103     * @param fieldPointers a tuple of field pointers. The tmp operation is
104     * called for the i-th field in this tuple.
105     */
106     template<typename T_Dc, typename T_Tuple>
107     HINLINE auto operator()(
108         uint32_t const& currentStep,
109         T_Dc& dc,
110         T_Tuple& fieldPointers) const
111     {
112         return particles::particleToGrid::
113             ComputeFieldValue<CORE + BORDER, Solver, Species, Filter>()
114             *(std::get<i>(fieldPointers)),
115             currentStep,
116             extraTmpSlot);
117     }
118 };
119

```

```

120  template<template<size_t> class T_Functor> struct CallComputeFieldValues
121  {
122      template<typename T_Dc, typename T_Tuple, std::size_t... I>
123      HINLINE auto operator()(
124          std::index_sequence<I...>,
125          uint32_t const& currentStep,
126          T_Dc& dc,
127          T_Tuple& fieldPointers) const
128      {
129          return std::make_tuple(T_Functor<I>()(currentStep, dc, fieldPointers)...);
130      }
131  };
132
133  template<size_t i> struct SetTransactionEvent
134  {
135      template<typename T_Tuple>
136      HINLINE void operator()(T_Tuple& eventPointers) const
137      {
138          auto eventPtr = std::get<i>(eventPointers);
139          if(eventPtr.has_value())
140          {
141              __setTransactionEvent(*eventPtr);
142          }
143      }
144  };
145
146  template<template<size_t> class T_Functor> struct CallSetTransactionEvent
147  {
148      template<typename T_Tuple, std::size_t... I>
149      HINLINE void operator()(std::index_sequence<I...>, T_Tuple& eventPointers)
150          const
151      {
152          [[maybe_unused]] int t[] = {(void) T_Functor<I>()(eventPointers), 1)...};
153      }
154  };
155
156  template<typename T_ScatterKernel> struct CallKernel
157  {
158      template<
159          typename T_Mapper,
160          typename T_ParticleBox,
161          typename T_HostScattererFunctor,
162          typename... T_FieldBoxes>
163      HINLINE void operator()(
164          T_Mapper const& mapper,
165          T_ParticleBox& particleBox,
166          T_HostScattererFunctor& hostScattererFunctor,
167          T_FieldBoxes&... fieldBoxes)
168      {
169          constexpr uint32_t numWorkers = pmacc::traits::GetNumWorkers<
170              pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value>::value;
171          PMACC_KERNEL(T_ScatterKernel){}
172          (mapper.getGridDim(),

```

```

173     numWorkers)(mapper, particleBox, hostScattererFunc, fieldBoxes...);
174 }
175 };
176
177 template<
178     typename T_Func,
179     typename... T_values,
180     std::size_t... I,
181     typename... T_Args>
182 HINLINE void callWithTuple(
183     T_Func func,
184     const std::tuple<T_values...>& tuple,
185     std::index_sequence<I...>,
186     T_Args&&... args)
187 {
188     func(args..., std::get<I>(tuple)...);
189 }
190
191 } // namespace detail
192
193 template<typename T_SpeciesType> struct CallScatterer
194 {
195     using SpeciesType = pmacc::particles::meta::
196         FindByNameOrType_t<VectorAllSpecies, T_SpeciesType>;
197     using FrameType = typename SpeciesType::FrameType;
198
199     // For now each species can have just one scatterer. One could implement
200     // multiple scatterers per species the same way we call multiple ionizers per
201     // species.
202     using ScattererUnspecialized = typename pmacc::traits::Resolve<
203         typename GetFlagType<FrameType, scatterer<>>::type>::type;
204     using Scatterer =
205         typename ScattererUnspecialized::template apply<T_SpeciesType>::type;
206
207     static constexpr uint32_t numWorkers = pmacc::traits::GetNumWorkers<
208         pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value>::value;
209     using Kernel = typename Scatterer::template CallingKernel<numWorkers>;
210
211     /* List of fields that are required by the functor.
212     *
213     * The Scatterer provides a list of required derived fields, i.e. density or
214     * temperature of some species. This is an mpl sequence of already
215     * specialized FieldTmpOperations.
216     */
217     using RequiredDerivedFields = typename pmacc::traits::Resolve<
218         typename Scatterer::RequiredDerivedFields>::type;
219     static constexpr size_t numTmpFields
220         = bmpl::size<RequiredDerivedFields>::type::value;
221     template<size_t i>
222     using ComputeFieldValues
223         = detail::ComputeFieldValuesImpl<RequiredDerivedFields, numTmpFields, i>;
224     using RequiredNativeFields = typename pmacc::traits::Resolve<
225         typename Scatterer::RequiredNativeFields>::type;

```

```

226     using GetNativeFieldsPointersTuple
227         = detail::GetNativeFieldsPointersTupleImpl<RequiredNativeFields>;
228
229     template<typename T_FieldTmpOperation> struct GetExtraSlots
230     {
231         using Solver = typename T_FieldTmpOperation::Solver;
232         using type = bmpl::int_<
233             particles::particleToGrid::RequiredExtraSlots<Solver>::type::value>;
234     };
235
236     using ListExtraSlots = typename bmpl::
237         transform<RequiredDerivedFields, GetExtraSlots<bmpl::_1>::type>;
238
239     using RequiredExtraTmpSlots = typename bmpl::accumulate<
240         ListExtraSlots,
241         bmpl::int_<0>,
242         bmpl::max<bmpl::_1, bmpl::_2>>::type;
243     static constexpr uint32_t requiredExtraTmpSlots
244         = RequiredExtraTmpSlots::value;
245
246     /** Functor implementation
247     *
248     * @tparam T_CellDescription contains the number of blocks and blocksize
249     *         that is later passed to the kernel
250     * @param cellDesc logical block information like dimension and cell sizes
251     * @param currentStep The current time step
252     */
253     HINLINE void operator()(const uint32_t currentStep) const
254     {
255         using RequiredSlots = bmpl::int_<requiredExtraTmpSlots>;
256         PMACC_CASSERT_MSG_TYPE(
257             // this line braking bellow wo't work, it is just for latex
258             _please_allocate_at_least_as_many_FieldTmp_slots_in_memory_param_as_
259             fields_required_for_scattering_plus_1_if_combined_atrributes_are_required,
260             ListExtraSlots,
261             fieldTmpNumSlots >= numTmpFields + requiredExtraTmpSlots);
262         DataConnector& dc = Environment<>::get().DataConnector();
263         // Use an index sequence (C++11 feature) to iterate over the fields with
264         // compile time loops.
265         std::make_index_sequence<numTmpFields> indexTmpFields{};
266         // Get an empty TmpField slot for each field. Store the shared field
267         // pointers in an std::tuple.
268         auto tmpFieldPointers
269             = detail::getTmpFieldPointersTuple(dc, indexTmpFields);
270
271         auto eventTaskPointers
272             = detail::CallComputeFieldValues<ComputeFieldValues>()(
273             indexTmpFields,
274             currentStep,
275             dc,
276             tmpFieldPointers);
277         auto tmpDataBoxes
278             = detail::getDataBoxTuple(tmpFieldPointers, indexTmpFields);

```

```

279 // TODO:: Add support for field modifiers. We need to do 1/gamma^2 for
280 // Faraday.
281
282 // get native fields
283 constexpr size_t numNativeFields
284 = bmpl::size<RequiredNativeFields>::type::value;
285 std::make_index_sequence<numNativeFields> indexNativeFields{};
286 auto nativeFieldPointers
287 = GetNativeFieldsPointersTuple()(dc, indexNativeFields);
288 auto nativeDataBoxes
289 = detail::getDataBoxTuple(nativeFieldPointers, indexNativeFields);
290
291 // combine all fields
292 auto dataBoxes = std::tuple_cat(nativeDataBoxes, tmpDataBoxes);
293 std::make_index_sequence<numNativeFields + numTmpFields> indexAllFields{};
294
295 // Get particle data.
296 auto species = dc.get<SpeciesType>(FrameType::getName(), true);
297 // Mapping descripton for the kernel call.
298 AreaMapping<CORE + BORDER, picongpu::MappingDesc> mapper(
299     species->getCellDescription());
300
301 detail::CallSetTransactionEvent<detail::SetTransactionEvent>()(
302     indexTmpFields,
303     eventTaskPointers);
304 // Call the scattering kernel and pass the field databoxes.
305 detail::callWithTuple(
306     detail::CallKernel<Kernel>(),
307     dataBoxes,
308     indexAllFields,
309     mapper,
310     species->getDeviceParticlesBox(),
311     Scatterer(currentStep));
312 // When the scatterer removes particles fill gaps needs to be called
313 // afterwards. Should be turned into a constexpr if after switching to
314 // c++17.
315 if constexpr(Scatterer::needsFillGaps)
316 {
317     // fill Gaps only in CORE + BORDER?
318     species->fillAllGaps();
319 }
320 };
321 };
322 } // namespace scattering
323 } // namespace particles
324 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 57. particles/scattering/functors.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/FaradayRotationFunctor.hpp"
6 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/ScatterFunctor.hpp"
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/SplitScatterer.hpp"
8 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/Always.hpp"
9 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/FixedProbability.hpp"
10 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/ProbLinToDens.hpp"
11 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/RandomThompson.hpp"
12 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/condition/Threshold.hpp"
13 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/direction/Random.hpp"
14 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/direction/RandomThompson.hpp"
15 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/splitCondition/Always.hpp"
16 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/splitCondition/GenerationLimit.hpp"

```

File 58. particles/scattering/SplitAndScatterParticles.kernel

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/scattering.kernel"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace acc
16             {
17                 namespace detail
18                 {
19                     // TODO: define this outside and use with collisions.
20                     template<typename T_ParBox, typename T_FramePtr>
21                     INLINE auto getParticle(
22                         T_ParBox& parBox,
23                         T_FramePtr frame,
24                         uint32_t particleId) -> typename T_FramePtr::type::ParticleType
25                     {
26                         constexpr uint32_t frameSize = pmacc::math::CT::volume<
27                             typename T_FramePtr::type::SuperCellSize>::type::value;
28                         uint32_t const skipFrames = particleId / frameSize;
29                         for(uint32_t i = 0; i < skipFrames; ++i)

```

```

30     frame = parBox.getNextFrame(frame);
31     PMACC_DEVICE_ASSERT_MSG(
32     frame.isValid(),
33     "frame in get Particle was invalid. particleIdWas: %u",
34     particleId);
35     return frame[particleId % frameSize];
36 }
37 } // namespace detail
38
39 template<uint32_t T_numWorkers> struct SplitAndScatterParticlesKernel
40 {
41     template<
42     typename T_Acc,
43     typename T_Mapper,
44     typename T_ParticleBox,
45     typename T_HostScattererFunctor,
46     typename... T_FieldBoxes>
47     INLINE void operator()(
48     T_Acc& acc,
49     T_Mapper const mapper,
50     T_ParticleBox particleBox,
51     T_HostScattererFunctor hostScattererFunctor,
52     T_FieldBoxes... fieldBoxes) const
53     {
54     using FrameType = typename T_ParticleBox::FrameType;
55     using FramePtr = typename T_ParticleBox::FramePtr;
56
57     DataSpace<simDim> const superCellIdx
58     = mapper.getSuperCellIndex(DataSpace<simDim>(cupla::blockIdx(acc)));
59
60     auto const firstFrame = particleBox.getFirstFrame(superCellIdx);
61     auto sourceFrame = firstFrame;
62     auto const lastSourceFrame = particleBox.getLastFrame(superCellIdx);
63
64     // cover the case when there are no particles at all
65     if(!sourceFrame.isValid())
66         return;
67
68     // get block cell
69     // shift fields
70     // CtxArray with SumDensity
71     // Write sums into shared memory
72     constexpr uint32_t numWorkers = T_numWorkers;
73     uint32_t const workerIdx = cupla::threadIdx(acc).x;
74     constexpr uint32_t frameSize
75     = pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value;
76     constexpr uint32_t cellsPerSuperCell = frameSize;
77
78     DataSpace<simDim> const blockCell{superCellIdx * SuperCellSize::toRT()};
79     auto& superCell = particleBox.getSuperCell(superCellIdx);
80     const uint32_t numParticlesInSupercell = superCell.getNumParticles();
81     DataSpace<simDim> const localSuperCellOffset(
82     superCellIdx - mapper.getGuardingSuperCells());

```

```

83
84     PMACC_SMEM(acc, densityArray, memory::Array<float_X, frameSize>);
85
86     auto forEachCellInSuperCell
87     = lockstep::makeForEach<cellsPerSuperCell, numWorkers>(workerIdx);
88     auto forEachParticleInFrame
89     = lockstep::makeForEach<frameSize, numWorkers>(workerIdx);
90     auto onlyMaster = lockstep::makeMaster(workerIdx);
91
92     auto SumDensityCtx = forEachCellInSuperCell([&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
93     { return SumDensity(); });
94
95     forEachCellInSuperCell(
96     [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
97     {
98     auto const idxInSuperCell
99     = DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::template map<SuperCellSize>(idx);
100     SumDensityCtx[idx](
101     (fieldBoxes.shift(blockCell)) (idxInSuperCell)[0]...);
102     densityArray[idx] = SumDensityCtx[idx].sum;
103     });
104
105     auto accScatteringFunctorCtx = forEachParticleInFrame(
106     [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
107     {
108     return hostScattererFunctor(
109     acc,
110     localSuperCellOffset,
111     forEachParticleInFrame.getWorkerCfg());
112     });
113
114     const uint32_t fillLastSourceFrame = superCell.getSizeLastFrame();
115     constexpr uint32_t maxNewParticlesOnSplit
116     = T_HostScattererFunctor::maxNewParticlesOnSplit;
117
118     PMACC_SMEM(acc, particlesToSplit, uint32_t);
119     PMACC_SMEM(acc, countSplittedParticles, uint32_t);
120     onlyMaster(
121     [&]()
122     {
123     particlesToSplit = 0u;
124     countSplittedParticles = 0u;
125     });
126     // sync after setting counters to 0 and after filling the densityArray
127     cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
128
129     uint32_t particlesToSplitThread{0};
130
131     for(uint32_t i = 0; i < numParticlesInSupercell; i += frameSize)
132     {
133     forEachParticleInFrame(
134     [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
135     {
136     if(i + idx < numParticlesInSupercell)

```

```

136     {
137         auto particle = sourceFrame[idx];
138         const float_X cellDensity = densityArray[particle[localCellIdx_]];
139         if(accScatteringFuncCtx[idx]
140             .scatteringCondition(acc, particle, cellDensity))
141         {
142             if(accScatteringFuncCtx[idx].splittingCondition(
143                 acc,
144                 particle))
145             {
146                 particlesToSplitThread++;
147                 particle[multiMask_] = 50;
148             }
149             else
150             {
151                 accScatteringFuncCtx[idx].scatterSingle(acc, particle);
152             }
153         }
154     }
155     });
156     sourceFrame = particleBox.getNextFrame(sourceFrame);
157 }
158
159 cupla::atomicAdd(
160     acc,
161     &particlesToSplit,
162     particlesToSplitThread,
163     ::alpaka::hierarchy::Threads{});
164 cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
165
166 if(particlesToSplit > 0u)
167 {
168     onlyMaster(
169         [&]()
170         {
171             if(
172                 particlesToSplit * maxNewParticlesOnSplit
173                 > (frameSize - fillLastSourceFrame))
174             {
175                 const uint32_t requiredNewSlots
176                     = particlesToSplit * maxNewParticlesOnSplit
177                     - (frameSize - fillLastSourceFrame);
178
179                 uint32_t numNewFrames = requiredNewSlots / frameSize;
180                 uint32_t newParticlesInLastFrame = requiredNewSlots % frameSize;
181                 if(newParticlesInLastFrame > 0u)
182                     numNewFrames++;
183
184                 for(uint32_t ii = 0; ii < numNewFrames; ii++)
185                 {
186                     auto newFrame = particleBox.getEmptyFrame(acc);
187                     particleBox.setAsLastFrame(acc, newFrame, superCellIdx);
188                 }

```

```

189             }
190         });
191     cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
192
193     const auto firstDestinationFrame = lastSourceFrame;
194     sourceFrame = firstFrame;
195
196     for(uint32_t i = 0; i < numParticlesInSupercell; i += frameSize)
197     {
198         forEachParticleInFrame(
199             [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
200             {
201                 if(i + idx < numParticlesInSupercell)
202                 {
203                     auto particle = sourceFrame[idx];
204                     if(particle[multiMask_] == 50)
205                     {
206                         particle[multiMask_] = 1;
207                         const uint32_t memoryDestinationBlock
208                             = cupla::atomicAdd(
209                                 acc,
210                                 &countSplittedParticles,
211                                 1u,
212                                 ::alpaka::hierarchy::Threads{}
213                                 * maxNewParticlesOnSplit);
214
215                         for(uint32_t ii = 0; ii < maxNewParticlesOnSplit; ii++)
216                         {
217                             const uint32_t newParticleIdx
218                                 = fillLastSourceFrame + memoryDestinationBlock + ii;
219                             /* TODO: do sth better than this. We shouldn't be going over
220                                * all of this frames over and over again.
221                                */
222                             auto newParticle = detail::getParticle(
223                                 particleBox,
224                                 firstDestinationFrame,
225                                 newParticleIdx);
226                             accScatteringFuncCtx[idx]
227                                 .split(acc, ii, particle, newParticle);
228                         }
229                         accScatteringFuncCtx[idx].afterSplit(acc, particle);
230                     }
231                 }
232             });
233     }
234     sourceFrame = particleBox.getNextFrame(sourceFrame);
235 }
236
237 #ifndef NDEBUG
238     // syncthreads before the assertion
239     cupla::_syncthreads(acc);
240 #endif
241
242 #ifdef PMACC_DEVICE_ASSERT_MSG
243     countSplittedParticles == particlesToSplit,
244     "[Split and Scatter particles]: CountSplittedParticles (%u) was not "

```

```

242     "equal to "
243     "particlesToSplit (%u)",
244     countSplittedParticles,
245     particlesToSplit);
246 }
247 }
248 };
249 } // namespace acc
250 } // namespace scattering
251 } // namespace particles
252 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 59. particles/scattering/splitCondition/Always.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.def"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace splitCondition
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     ///! Splitting condition functor: particle is always splited.
20                     struct Always;
21                 } // namespace acc
22
23                 using Always = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::Free<acc::Always>;
24             } // namespace splitCondition
25         } // namespace scattering
26     } // namespace particles
27 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 60. particles/scattering/splitCondition/GenerationLimit.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */

```

```

2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.hpp"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace particles
12     {
13         namespace scattering
14         {
15             namespace splitCondition
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     template<uint32_t maxGenToSplit> struct GenerationLimit
20                     {
21                         /* decide if a particle should be splitted */
22                         *
23                         * @tparam T_Particle species type
24                         *
25                         * @param particle particle that could be splitted
26                         */
27                         template<typename T_Particle>
28                         DINLINE bool operator()(T_Particle const& particle) const
29                         {
30                             return (particle[generation_] <= maxGenToSplit);
31                         }
32                     };
33                 } // namespace acc
34             } // namespace splitCondition
35         } // namespace scattering
36     } // namespace particles
37 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 61. particles/scattering/splitCondition/GenerationLimit.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.def"
8
9  namespace picongpu

```

```

10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace splitCondition
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 ///! Splitting condition functor: particle is splitted if it's not older than x
20 ///! generations.
21 template<uint32_t maxGenToSplit> struct GenerationLimit;
22 } // namespace acc
23
24 template<uint32_t maxGenToSplit>
25 using GenerationLimit = picongpu::particles::scattering::generic::Free<
26     acc::GenerationLimit<maxGenToSplit>>;
27 } // namespace splitCondition
28 } // namespace scattering
29 } // namespace particles
30 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 62. particles/scattering/splitCondition/Always.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/generic/Free.hpp"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace particles
12 {
13 namespace scattering
14 {
15 namespace splitCondition
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 struct Always
20 {
21     /* decide if a particle should be splitted
22     *
23     * @tparam T_Particle species type
24     *
25     * @param particle particle that could be splitted

```

```

26 */
27 template<typename T_Particle>
28 inline bool operator()(T_Particle const& particle) const
29 {
30     return true;
31 }
32 };
33 } // namespace acc
34 } // namespace splitCondition
35 } // namespace scattering
36 } // namespace particles
37 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 63. simulation/stage/Scattering.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2019-2021 Rene Widera */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/particles/scattering/CallScatterer.hpp"
8
9 #include <pmacc/Environment.hpp>
10 #include <pmacc/dataManagement/DataConnector.hpp>
11 #include <pmacc/meta/ForEach.hpp>
12 #include <pmacc/particles/traits/FilterByFlag.hpp>
13 #include <pmacc/type/Area.hpp>
14
15 #include <cstdlib>
16
17 namespace picongpu
18 {
19 namespace simulation
20 {
21 namespace stage
22 {
23 ///! Functor for the stage of the PIC loop performing particle scattering
24 class Scattering
25 {
26     public:
27     /** Perform particle scattering
28     *
29     * @param step index of time iteration
30     */
31     void operator()(uint32_t const step) const
32     {
33         using pmacc::particles::traits::FilterByFlag;
34         using SpeciesWithScatterers =

```

```

35     typename FilterByFlag<VectorAllSpecies, scatterer<>>::type;
36     pmacc::meta::ForEach<
37     SpeciesWithScatterers,
38     particles::scattering::CallScatterer<bmpl::_1>>
39     particleScattering;
40     particleScattering(step);
41 }
42
43 private:
44 };
45
46 } // namespace stage
47 } // namespace simulation
48 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 64. plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetector.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/param/photonDetector.param"
8  #include "picongpu/particles/traits/SpeciesEligibleForSolver.hpp"
9  #include "picongpu/plugins/common/GetOpenPMDStoredType.hpp"
10 #include "picongpu/plugins/multi/multi.hpp"
11 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectParticles.kernel"
12 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
13 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetectorImpl.hpp"
14 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetectorWriter.hpp"
15 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/accumulationPolicies.def"
16
17 #include <pmacc/math/operation.hpp>
18 #include <pmacc/mpl/MPIReduce.hpp>
19 #include <pmacc/mpl/reduceMethods/Reduce.hpp>
20 #include <pmacc/pluginSystem/INotify.hpp>
21 #include <pmacc/traits/HasFlag.hpp>
22 #include <pmacc/traits/HasIdentifiers.hpp>
23
24 #include <algorithm>
25 #include <cstdio>
26 #include <map>
27 #include <memory>
28 #include <stdexcept>
29 #include <string>
30 #include <vector>
31
32 namespace picongpu

```

```

33 {
34 namespace plugins
35 {
36 namespace photonDetector
37 {
38 /** PhotonDetector plugin
39 *
40 * A planar detector for outgoing particles
41 *
42 * @tparam T_DetectorConfig compile time parameters, see photonDetector.param
43 * @tparam T_Species particle species to detect
44 */
45 template<typename T_DetectorConfig, typename T_Species>
46 class PhotonDetector : public plugins::multi::IInstance
47 {
48 public:
49 /** Slave instance description and command line options
50 struct Help : public plugins::multi::IHelp
51 {
52 /** creates a PhotonDetector slave plugin instance
53 *
54 * @param help plugin defined help
55 * @param id index of the plugin, range: [0;help->getNumPlugins())
56 * @param cellDescription
57 *
58 * @returns shared pointer to the slave instance with the IInstance
59 * interface
60 */
61 std::shared_ptr<IInstance> create(
62     std::shared_ptr<IHelp>& help,
63     size_t const id,
64     MappingDesc* cellDescription) override
65 {
66     return std::shared_ptr<IInstance>(<
67         new PhotonDetector<T_DetectorConfig, T_Species>(<
68             help,
69             id,
70             cellDescription));
71     }
72
73 /** Plugin command line options:
74 plugins::multi::Option<std::string> notifyPeriod
75     = {"period", "notify period"};
76 plugins::multi::Option<int32_t> detectorSizeX = {
77     "size.x",
78     "detector size, in cells, in x direction (detector coordinate system)."};
79 plugins::multi::Option<int32_t> detectorSizeY = {
80     "size.y",
81     "detector size, in cells, in y direction (detector coordinate system)."};
82 plugins::multi::Option<std::string> placement = {
83     "placement",
84     "Placement of the detector. Simulation box side behind which the "
85     "detector is "

```

```

86     "placed. "
87     "Arbitrary angles are not supported so a detector is always placed on "
88     "one of the "
89     "simulation axes. Valid values are: `x-`, `x+`, `y-`, `y+`, `z-`, `z+`. "
90     "The "
91     "letter is the "
92     "axis on which the detector is positioned. `` means in front of the "
93     "simulation "
94     "box `+` "
95     "means behind the simulation box. So for example `x+`(`x-`) would mean "
96     "that "
97     "particles"
98     "going into the positive (negative) x direction are moving towards the "
99     "detector. ";
100    plugins::multi::Option<std::string> outputDir = {
101        "dir",
102        "Directory inside simOutput where the output files are stored.",
103        "photonDetector"};
104    plugins::multi::Option<std::string> fileName = {
105        "fileName",
106        "Output file name base. Complete file name will be: "
107        "<fileName><infix>.<ext> ",
108        T_Species::FrameType::getName() + "_" + "photonDetectorData");
109    plugins::multi::Option<std::string> fileInfix = {
110        "infix",
111        "openPMD filename infix (use to pick file- or group-based "
112        "layout in openPMD)\nSet to NULL to keep empty (e.g. to pick"
113        " group-based iteration layout). Parameter will be ignored"
114        " if a streaming backend is detected in 'ext' parameter and"
115        " an empty string will be assumed instead. "
116        "Complete file name will be: <fileName><infix>.<ext>",
117        "%06T"};
118    plugins::multi::Option<std::string> fileExtension = {
119        "ext",
120        "openPMD filename extension (this controls the"
121        " backend picked by the openPMD API)",
122        "bp"};
123    plugins::multi::Option<std::string> jsonConfig = {
124        "json",
125        "advanced (backend) configuration for openPMD in JSON format",
126        "{}"};
127
128    ///! method used by plugin controller to get --help description
129    void registerHelp(
130        boost::program_options::options_description& desc,
131        std::string const& masterPrefix = std::string{}) override
132    {
133        notifyPeriod.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
134        detectorSizeX.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
135        detectorSizeY.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
136        placement.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
137        fileExtension.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
138        jsonConfig.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);

```

```

139        fileInfix.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
140        fileName.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
141        outputDir.registerHelp(desc, masterPrefix + prefix);
142    }
143
144    void expandHelp(
145        boost::program_options::options_description& desc,
146        std::string const& masterPrefix = std::string{}) override
147    {
148    }
149
150    void validateOptions() override
151    {
152        if(notifyPeriod.size() != detectorSizeX.size())
153            throw std::runtime_error(
154                name
155                + ": parameter detectorSizeX and period are not used the same "
156                "number of "
157                "times");
158        if(notifyPeriod.size() != detectorSizeY.size())
159            throw std::runtime_error(
160                name
161                + ": parameter detectorSizeY and period are not used the same "
162                "number of "
163                "times");
164        if(notifyPeriod.size() != placement.size())
165            throw std::runtime_error(
166                name
167                + ": parameter placement and period are not used the same number of "
168                "times");
169
170        // check if user passed placements are valid
171        for(auto const& placementStr : placement)
172        {
173            std::vector<std::string>
174                supportedPlacements{"x-", "x+", "y-", "y+", "z-", "z+"};
175            if(
176                std::find(
177                    supportedPlacements.begin(),
178                    supportedPlacements.end(),
179                    placementStr)
180                == supportedPlacements.end())
181            {
182                throw std::runtime_error(
183                    name + ": invalid detector placement '" + placementStr + "'");
184            }
185        }
186    }
187
188    size_t getNumPlugins() const override
189    {
190        return notifyPeriod.size();
191    }

```

```

192
193     std::string getDescription() const override
194     {
195         return description;
196     }
197
198     std::string getOptionPrefix() const
199     {
200         return prefix;
201     }
202
203     std::string getName() const override
204     {
205         return name;
206     }
207
208     std::string const name = "photonDetector";
209     //! short description of the plugin
210     std::string const description
211         = "Propagate particles leaving the simulation to a planar detector.";
212     //! prefix used for command line arguments
213     std::string const prefix = T_Species::FrameType::getName() + "_"
214         + T_DetectorConfig::getName() + "_" + std::string("photonDetector");
215 };
216
217 private:
218 using AccumulationPolicy =
219     typename T_DetectorConfig::AccumulationPolicy::template apply<
220         T_Species>::type;
221 using StoredType = typename AccumulationPolicy::Type;
222
223 //! OpenPMD API doesn't fully support vectors.
224 //! Instead we create a separate mesh for each vector component.
225 //! Here we extract the type stored in a vector.
226 //! This is only really needed when the accumulation policy uses vectors to
227 //! store data.
228 using SingleValueType = typename StoredType::type;
229
230 using OpenPMDStoredType =
231     typename openPMD::GetOpenPMDStoredType<SingleValueType>::type;
232 using ParticleFilter =
233     typename T_DetectorConfig::ParticleFilter::template apply<T_Species>::type;
234 static constexpr uint32_t storedVectorSize
235     = static_cast<uint32_t>(StoredType::dim);
236
237 //! plugin help description storing command line parameters
238 std::shared_ptr<Help> help_m;
239 //! id of the slave plugin instance
240 size_t id_m;
241 //! pointer to a detector instance (detects particles, stores output,
242 //! provides extra description)
243 std::unique_ptr<PhotonDetectorImpl<T_DetectorConfig, T_Species>> detector;
244 //! pointer to a writer for writing output

```

```

245     std::unique_ptr<PhotonDetectorWriter<OpenPMDStoredType>> writer;
246     using BufferMaster = std::vector<StoredType>;
247     BufferMaster detectorBufferMaster;
248
249     MappingDesc cellDescription_m;
250     //! the short name of the species (prefix) processed by this instance
251     std::string const speciesName;
252     //! defines time steps at which the output is written
253     std::string notifyPeriod;
254
255     //! For collecting detector values from multiple devices on master:
256     pmacc::mpi::MPIReduce reduce;
257     using ReduceMethod = pmacc::mpi::reduceMethods::Reduce;
258
259     //! exchange direction in which the detector is placed.
260     DetectorPlacement placement;
261     //! the size of the detector in cells
262     DataSpace<DIM2> detectorSize;
263     //! Is this instance running on the master (rank 0)?
264     const bool isMaster;
265
266 public:
267     /** PhotonDetector object initializer.
268     *
269     * @param help plugin defined help
270     * @param id index of the plugin, range: [0;help_m->getNumPlugins())
271     * @param cellDescription
272     */
273     HINLINE PhotonDetector(
274         std::shared_ptr<plugins::multi::IHelp>& help,
275         size_t const id,
276         MappingDesc* cellDescription)
277         : help_m(std::static_pointer_cast<Help>(help))
278         , id_m(id)
279         , cellDescription_m(*cellDescription)
280         , speciesName(T_Species::FrameType::getName())
281         , isMaster(reduce.hasResult(ReduceMethod()))
282     {
283         //! Register this slave plugin instance for calling notify on each step
284         Environment<>::get().PluginConnector().setNotificationPeriod(
285             this,
286             help_m->notifyPeriod.get(id));
287
288         detectorSize
289             = {help_m->detectorSizeX.get(id), help_m->detectorSizeY.get(id)};
290         notifyPeriod = help_m->notifyPeriod.get(id);
291
292         std::map<std::string, DetectorPlacement> placementMap{
293             {"x-", DetectorPlacement::XFront},
294             {"x+", DetectorPlacement::X Rear},
295             {"y-", DetectorPlacement::YFront},
296             {"y+", DetectorPlacement::Y Rear},
297             {"z-", DetectorPlacement::ZFront},

```

```

298     {"z+", DetectorPlacement::ZRear},
299 };
300 try
301 {
302     placement = placementMap.at(help_m->placement.get(id));
303 }
304 catch(std::out_of_range const& e)
305 {
306     throw PluginException(
307         "[Plugin] [" + help_m->getOptionPrefix()
308         + "] placement must be 'x-', 'x+', 'y-', 'y+', 'z-', or 'z+'");
309 }
310
311 using DetectorImplType = PhotonDetectorImpl<T_DetectorConfig, T_Species>;
312 detector = std::make_unique<DetectorImplType>(detectorSize, placement);
313
314 // Set up the writer object for IO:
315 // Make sure file based iteration layout is not used with a streaming
316 // backend
317 std::string fileInfix = help_m->fileInfix.get(id);
318 std::string fileExtension = help_m->fileExtension.get(id);
319 if(fileInfix == "NULL" || fileExtension == "sst")
320 {
321     fileInfix = "";
322 }
323 std::string fileName = help_m->fileName.get(id);
324 std::string outputDir = help_m->outputDir.get(id);
325 std::string meshName = AccumulationPolicy::getOpenPMDMeshName();
326
327 writer = std::make_unique<PhotonDetectorWriter<OpenPMDStoredType>>(
328     isMaster,
329     fileName,
330     fileInfix,
331     fileExtension,
332     outputDir,
333     meshName,
334     precisionCast<uint64_t>(detectorSize),
335     float2_X{
336         T_DetectorConfig::cellHeight / UNIT_LENGTH,
337         T_DetectorConfig::cellWidth / UNIT_LENGTH},
338     detector->accumHostFuncitor.getUnit(),
339     detector->accumHostFuncitor.getUnitDimension(),
340     detector->accumHostFuncitor.getName(),
341     help_m->placement.get(id),
342     T_DetectorConfig::distance);
343
344 // Create a buffer that is only on host side and only on master for
345 // intermediate output storage
346 if(isMaster)
347 {
348     detectorBufferMaster.assign(
349         detectorSize.x() * detectorSize.y(),
350         AccumulationPolicy().initValue);

```

```

351     }
352 }
353
354 //! get plugin help description
355 static std::shared_ptr<plugins::multi::IHelp> getHelp()
356 {
357     return std::shared_ptr<plugins::multi::IHelp>(new Help{});
358 }
359
360 //! PhotonDetector object destructor
361 ~PhotonDetector() override
362 {
363 }
364
365 //! restart the plugin from a checkpoint
366 HINLINE void restart(
367     uint32_t restartStep,
368     std::string const& restartDirectory) override
369 {
370     // can be left empty
371 }
372
373 private:
374 HINLINE void reduceDataOnMaster()
375 {
376     detector->deviceToHost();
377     __getTransactionEvent().waitForFinished();
378
379     reduce(
380         pmacc::math::operation::Add(),
381         isMaster ? detectorBufferMaster.data() : nullptr,
382         detector->getHostDataBox().getPointer(),
383         detectorSize.productOfComponents(),
384         ReduceMethod());
385 }
386
387 HINLINE void writeOutputScalar(uint32_t currentStep)
388 {
389     reduceDataOnMaster();
390
391     if(isMaster)
392     {
393         writer->openIteration(currentStep);
394         (*writer)(
395             currentStep,
396             reinterpret_cast<OpenPMDStoredType*>(detectorBufferMaster.data()),
397             detector->accumHostFuncitor.getOpenPMDMeshSuffix(0));
398         writer->flush();
399         writer->closeIteration();
400         detectorBufferMaster.assign(
401             detectorSize.x() * detectorSize.y(),
402             AccumulationPolicy().initValue);
403     }

```

```

404 // Zero the detector.
405 detector->resetDeviceBuffer();
406 }
407
408 HINLINE void writeOutputVector(uint32_t currentStep)
409 {
410     reduceDataOnMaster();
411
412     if(isMaster)
413     {
414         writer->openIteration(currentStep);
415
416         const auto size = detectorBufferMaster.size();
417         std::vector<SingleValueType> component2d(size);
418
419         for(uint32_t component = 0; component < storedVectorSize; component++)
420         {
421             for(uint32_t ii = 0; ii < size; ii++)
422             {
423                 component2d[ii] = detectorBufferMaster[ii][component];
424             }
425             (*writer)(
426                 currentStep,
427                 reinterpret_cast<OpenPMDStoredType*>(component2d.data()),
428                 detector->accumHostFunctor.getOpenPMDMeshSuffix(component));
429
430             writer->flush();
431         }
432         writer->closeIteration();
433         detectorBufferMaster.assign(
434             detectorSize.x() * detectorSize.y(),
435             AccumulationPolicy().initValue);
436     }
437     // Zero the detector.
438     detector->resetDeviceBuffer();
439 }
440
441 HINLINE void writeOutput(uint32_t currentStep)
442 {
443     // TODO: (c++17) make it constexpr if
444     if(storedVectorSize > 1u)
445         writeOutputVector(currentStep);
446     else
447         writeOutputScalar(currentStep);
448 }
449
450 public:
451 //! create a check point for the plugin
452 HINLINE void checkpoint(
453     uint32_t currentStep,
454     std::string const& checkpointDirectory) override
455 {
456     /* Force output on checkpoint.
457
458     * This is the easiest way to avoid loosing data on checkpoint.
459     * An alternative would be to collect data on master and store it in the
460     * checkpoint directory. This would be loaded on restart and later on added
461     * to the next output.
462     */
463     writeOutput(currentStep);
464 }
465
466 /** Actions performed on every step included in the notify period
467 *
468 * @param currentStep
469 */
470 HINLINE void notify(uint32_t currentStep) override
471 {
472     writeOutput(currentStep);
473 }
474
475 /** Handle particles leaving the simulation box
476 *
477 * Check if the detector is placed behind this exchange direction. If so call
478 * the DetectParticles kernel to detect outgoing particles.
479 *
480 * @param speciesName_p name of the species leaving the simulation
481 * @param direction_p direction in which the species are leaving. See
482 * pmacc::type::ExchangeType for definition.
483 */
484 HINLINE void onParticleLeave(
485     std::string const& speciesName_p,
486     int32_t const direction) override
487 {
488     // no need to collect particles if the plugin is not active
489     if(this->notifyPeriod.empty())
490         return;
491     // collect only particles from the species handled by this plugin
492     if(speciesName_p != speciesName)
493         return;
494
495     DataConnector& dc = Environment<simDim>::get().DataConnector();
496     auto particles = dc.get<T_Species>(speciesName, true);
497
498     constexpr uint32_t numWorkers = pmacc::traits::GetNumWorkers<
499         pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value>::value;
500
501     auto mapperFactory
502         = particles::boundary::getMapperFactory(*particles, direction);
503     auto const mapper = mapperFactory(this->cellDescription_m);
504     const DataSpace<simDim> localOffset
505         = Environment<simDim>::get().SubGrid().getLocalDomain().offset;
506
507     /* Here we only process the particles that just crossed the boundary,
508     * so the active area for the kernel is the outside area wrt the boundary
509     */
510     pmacc::DataSpace<simDim> beginExternalCellsTotal, endExternalCellsTotal;

```

```

510 particles::boundary::getExternalCellsTotal(
511     *particles,
512     direction,
513     &beginExternalCellsTotal,
514     &endExternalCellsTotal);
515 SubGrid<simDim> const& subGrid = Environment<simDim>::get().SubGrid();
516 pmacc::DataSpace<simDim> shiftTotalToLocal
517     = subGrid.getGlobalDomain().offset + subGrid.getLocalDomain().offset;
518 auto const beginExternalCellsLocal
519     = beginExternalCellsTotal - shiftTotalToLocal;
520 auto const endExternalCellsLocal
521     = endExternalCellsTotal - shiftTotalToLocal;
522 const uint32_t currentStep
523     = Environment<>::get().SimulationDescription().getCurrentStep();
524 // unary particle functor used to detect particles
525 const auto detectParticle = detector->getDetectParticle(currentStep);
526
527 PMACC_KERNEL(DetectParticles<numWorkers>{ })
528 (mapper.getGridDim(), numWorkers)(
529     particles->getDeviceParticlesBox(),
530     localOffset,
531     detectParticle,
532     detector->getDeviceDataBox(),
533     mapper,
534     beginExternalCellsLocal,
535     endExternalCellsLocal,
536     particles::filter::Unary<ParticleFilter>{currentStep});
537 }
538 };
539
540 } // namespace photonDetector
541 } // namespace plugins
542 namespace particles
543 {
544     namespace traits
545     {
546         ///! Check if a species class has the attributes and flags required for
547         ///! detection
548         template<
549             typename T_DetectorConfig,
550             typename T_Species,
551             typename T_UnspecifiedSpecies>
552         struct SpeciesEligibleForSolver<
553             T_Species,
554             plugins::photonDetector::
555             PhotonDetector<T_DetectorConfig, T_UnspecifiedSpecies>
556         {
557             using FrameType = typename T_Species::FrameType;
558             using AccumulationPolicy = typename T_DetectorConfig::AccumulationPolicy;
559             using Filter = typename T_DetectorConfig::ParticleFilter;
560
561             /// This plugin needs at least the position and weighting for raytracing
562             using RequiredIdentifiers = MakeSeq_t<position<>, momentum>;

```

```

563         using SpeciesHasIdentifiers = typename pmacc::traits::
564             HasIdentifiers<FrameType, RequiredIdentifiers>::type;
565         using EligibleForRayTracing = SpeciesHasIdentifiers;
566
567         using EligibleForFilter = typename particles::traits::
568             SpeciesEligibleForSolver<T_Species, Filter>::type;
569
570         /// Check the prerequisites for accumulating the values stored on detector
571         using EligibleForAccumulation = typename particles::traits::
572             SpeciesEligibleForSolver<T_Species, AccumulationPolicy>::type;
573         using type = typename bmpl::and_<
574             typename bmpl::and_<EligibleForRayTracing, EligibleForAccumulation>,
575             EligibleForFilter>;
576     };
577 } // namespace traits
578 } // namespace particles
579 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 65. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountMacroParticles.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/traits/SpeciesEligibleForSolver.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
9
10 #include <pmacc/traits/HasIdentifiers.hpp>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14     namespace plugins
15     {
16         namespace photonDetector
17         {
18             namespace accumulation
19             {
20                 namespace acc
21                 {
22                     template<typename T_Species> struct CountMacroParticles;
23                 } // namespace acc
24
25                 /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the CountMacroParticles device
26                 * accumulation functor
27                 *
28                 * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
29                 */

```

```

30 template<typename T_Species> struct CountMacroParticles;
31 } // namespace accumulation
32 namespace particleHandlers
33 {
34 /** Simply count macro particles hitting a detector cell.
35  *
36  * A particle accumulation policy for a particle detector.
37  */
38 struct CountMacroParticles
39 {
40     /** Get a functor factory type for a give particle species type
41     template<typename T_Species> struct apply
42     {
43         using type
44         = picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::accumulation::CountMacroParticles<
45         T_Species>;
46     };
47 };
48 } // namespace particleHandlers
49 } // namespace photonDetector
50 } // namespace plugins
51 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 66. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/accumulationPolicies.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AddWaveParticles.def"
6  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AmplitudeWithPolarization.def"
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountMacroParticles.def"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.def"

```

File 67. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/traits/SpeciesEligibleForSolver.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
9

```

```

10 #include <pmacc/traits/HasIdentifiers.hpp>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14     namespace plugins
15     {
16         namespace photonDetector
17         {
18             namespace accumulation
19             {
20                 namespace acc
21                 {
22                     template<typename T_Species> struct CountParticles;
23                 } // namespace acc
24
25                 /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the CountParticles device
26                 * accumulation functor
27                 *
28                 * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
29                 */
30                 template<typename T_Species> struct CountParticles;
31             } // namespace accumulation
32         namespace particleHandlers
33         {
34             /** Simply count real particles hitting a detector cell.
35             *
36             * A particle accumulation policy for a particle detector.
37             */
38             struct CountParticles
39             {
40                 /** Get a functor factory type for a give particle species type
41                 template<typename T_Species> struct apply
42                 {
43                     using type
44                     = picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::accumulation::CountParticles<
45                     T_Species>;
46                 };
47             };
48         } // namespace particleHandlers
49     } // namespace photonDetector
50 } // namespace plugins
51
52 namespace particles
53 {
54     namespace traits
55     {
56         /** Check if a particle species has all the required identifiers and flags for
57         /** the CountParticles policy
58         template<typename T_Species>
59         struct SpeciesEligibleForSolver<
60             T_Species,
61             picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::particleHandlers::CountParticles>
62         {

```

```

63 using FrameType = typename T_Species::FrameType;
64 using RequiredIdentifiers = MakeSeq_t<weighting>;
65 using type = typename pmacc::traits::
66   HasIdentifiers<FrameType, RequiredIdentifiers>::type;
67 };
68 } // namespace traits
69 } // namespace particles
70 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 68. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/accumulationPolicies.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AddWaveParticles.hpp"
6  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AmplitudeWithPolarization.hpp"
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountMacroParticles.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.hpp"

```

File 69. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AddWaveParticles.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/particles/PhotonFunctors.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/AxisSwap.hpp"
9  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
10 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetectorUtilities.hpp"
11 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AddWaveParticles.def"
12
13 #include <pmacc/math/Complex.hpp>
14
15 namespace picongpu
16 {
17 namespace plugins
18 {
19 namespace photonDetector
20 {
21 namespace accumulation
22 {
23 namespace acc

```

```

24 {
25 namespace detail
26 {
27 /* This types are used to mock the constexpr if functionality from c++17.
28  * And they should be refactored out once static if becomes available. */
29
30 /** Get particle phase
31  *
32  * The particle phase can consist either of
33  * 1. A constant starting phase that can be different for each particle and a
34  * value that is common for all particles in the species which is calculated
35  * from the simulation time and the species wavelength flag.
36  * 2. An individual particle attribute phase that can be updated by e.g. the
37  * PhotonPhase pusher.
38  *
39  * Approach 1 is used when the particle doesn't have the phase attribute. In
40  * that case the species must have the wavelength flag and the startPhase
41  * attribute. Approach 2 is used when the particle has the phase attribute.
42  *
43  * @tparam T_Species species type
44  * @tparam hasPhase true if the T_Species has the phase attribute
45  */
46 template<
47   typename T_Species,
48   bool hasWavelength = pmacc::traits::
49     HasFlag<typename T_Species::FrameType, wavelength<>>::type::value>
50 struct GetPhase
51
52 {
53   /** Get the species wide contribution to particle phase at the give time step
54   HINLINE float_X getCurPhase(uint32_t const& currentStep) const
55   {
56     return 0.0_X;
57   }
58   /** Get the contribution to particle phase that can be different for each
59   /** particle
60   template<typename T_Particle>
61   HINLINE float_X getParticlePhase(
62     uint32_t const& currentStep,
63     T_Particle const& particle) const
64   {
65     const float_X curPhase = -1.
66       * particles::GetPhaseByTimestep<T_Species>()(currentStep + 1, particle)
67       + 2. * PI;
68     return particle[startPhase_] + curPhase;
69   }
70 };
71
72 template<typename T_Species> struct GetPhase<T_Species, true>
73 {
74   HINLINE float_X getCurPhase(uint32_t const& currentStep) const
75   {
76     return -1. * particles::GetPhaseByTimestep<T_Species>()(currentStep + 1)

```

```

77     + 2. * PI;
78 }
79
80 template<typename T_Particle>
81 HDINLINE float_X getParticlePhase(
82     uint32_t const& currentStep,
83     T_Particle const& particle) const
84 {
85     return particle[startPhase_];
86 }
87 }; // namespace accumulation
88 } // namespace detail
89
90 /** Accumulation device functor for particles with wave properties (amplitude
91     * and phase summation)
92     *
93     * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
94     */
95 template<typename T_Species> struct AddWaveParticles
96 {
97     private:
98     using Species = T_Species;
99     using FrameType = typename Species::FrameType;
100
101     public:
102     using FloatType = float_64;
103     /*! type used to store detector cell values
104     using Type = pmacc::math::Complex<FloatType>;
105
106     private:
107     PMACC_ALIGN(detector_m, const DetectorParams);
108     PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap_m, const externalBeam::AxisSwap);
109     PMACC_ALIGN(simSize_m, const DataSpace<simDim>);
110     /** Common phase contribution at current time step
111     *
112     * Used only when all the particles of the species has the same wavelength
113     * (wavelength flag is defined).
114     * value range is [0, 2*PI)
115     */
116     PMACC_ALIGN(curPhase_m, const float_X);
117     PMACC_ALIGN(currentStep_m, const uint32_t);
118
119     public:
120     /** AddWaveParticles device functor constructor
121     *
122     * @param currentStep current simulation time step
123     * @param detector detector description
124     * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
125     */
126     HDINLINE AddWaveParticles(
127         uint32_t currentStep,
128         const DetectorParams detector,
129         DataSpace<simDim> simSize,

```

```

130     externalBeam::AxisSwap axisSwap)
131     : detector_m(detector)
132     , simSize_m(simSize)
133     , curPhase_m(detail::GetPhase<T_Species>().getCurPhase(currentStep))
134     , axisSwap_m(axisSwap)
135     , currentStep_m(currentStep)
136     {
137     }
138
139     /** accumulate particle on a detector cell
140     *
141     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
142     * @param detectorBox detector data box
143     * @param targetCellIdx the index of the detector cell hit by the particle
144     * @param particle particle to accumulate
145     * @param globalCellIdx the index of the cell from which the particle has
146     * left the simulation box (the cell in GUARD where the particle will be
147     * deleted). In the detector coordinate system.
148     */
149     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_DetectorBox, typename T_Particle>
150     HDINLINE void operator()(
151         T_Acc const& acc,
152         T_DetectorBox detectorBox,
153         const DataSpace<DIM2>& targetCellIdx,
154         const T_Particle& particle,
155         const DataSpace<simDim>& globalCellIdx) const
156     {
157         using namespace pmacc;
158         /** Get the dimensions of a picongpu cell in the detector coordinate system
159         const float_X CELL_LENGTH_DET_X_DIR
160             = std::get<0>(getCellLengths(detector_m.detectorPlacement));
161         const float_X CELL_LENGTH_DET_Y_DIR
162             = std::get<1>(getCellLengths(detector_m.detectorPlacement));
163         const float_X CELL_LENGTH_DET_Z_DIR
164             = std::get<2>(getCellLengths(detector_m.detectorPlacement));
165         Type& oldVal = detectorBox(targetCellIdx)[0];
166
167         /** Phase is:  $k \cdot dn + w \cdot t + \phi_0$  with  $dn$ ...distance to detector,
168         *  $k$ ...wavenumber,  $\phi_0$ ...start phase  $w \cdot t$  is the same for all particles so
169         * we pre-calculate it (reduce to  $2 \cdot \pi$ ) in high precision  $dn$  must be exact
170         * compared to  $\lambda$  which is hard. We would also need to calculate  $dn$  to
171         * a fixed point for all photons in the detector-cell (e.g.) middle for
172         * proper interference In the end, only the phase difference matters. We
173         * take the ray from the cell (0,0) from the exiting plane as a reference
174         * and calculate the phase difference to this. It is the projection of the
175         * vector from the reference point to the particles position on the
176         * reference ray, whose vector is given by the particles direction (for
177         * large distances all rays to a given detector cell are parallel)
178         */
179
180         float_X phase;
181         /** Combine the common and individual phase contributions.
182         /** See detail::GetPhase for more detailed explanation.

```

```

183 phase
184   = detail::GetPhase<T_Species>().getParticlePhase(currentStep_m, particle)
185   + curPhase_m;
186 constexpr float_X twoPi = pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::doubleValue;
187 phase = math::fmod(phase, twoPi);
188
189 // This has something to do with fast math.
190 if(phase > pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value)
191   phase -= twoPi;
192
193 PMACC_DEVICE_ASSERT_MSG(
194   phase >= -pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value
195   && phase <= pmacc::math::Pi<float_X>::value,
196   "phase was %e",
197   phase);
198 /* The projection is k * (dir * pos)//dir| (dot product)
199 * We need the direction to a fixed point on the detector. As it is hard to
200 * calculate that exactly for the particle due to the large distance, we
201 * use the direction of the reference ray based on the observation that for
202 * "large" distances the angle is the same For better precision summands
203 * are reduced mod 2*PI
204 */
205 const pmacc::math::Vector<float_X, 2> detectorAngles
206   = precisionCast<float_X>(targetCellIdx - detector_m.size / 2)
207   * detector_m.anglePerCell;
208 const pmacc::math::Vector<float_X, 3> dir(
209   math::tan<trigo_X>(detectorAngles.x()),
210   math::tan<trigo_X>(detectorAngles.y()),
211   1.0_X);
212 const float_X dirLen = math::abs(dir);
213 const float_X omega = particles::GetAngFrequency<T_Species>(particle);
214 const float_X k = omega / SPEED_OF_LIGHT;
215
216 // Reference is the middle of the end of the volume
217 DataSpace<simDim> globalCellOffset = globalCellIdx - simSize_m / 2;
218 globalCellOffset.z() = globalCellIdx.z() - simSize_m.z();
219 // Add the negated dot product (reduced by 2*PI), negated as the difference
220 // to the reference ray gets smaller with increasing index Add x,y parts
221 // first as those are much smaller than z
222 const float_X distDiffG
223   = globalCellOffset.z() * CELL_LENGTH_DET_Z_DIR * dir.z()
224   + (globalCellOffset.x() * CELL_LENGTH_DET_X_DIR * dir.x()
225     + globalCellOffset.y() * CELL_LENGTH_DET_Y_DIR * dir.y());
226 phase += math::fmod(-distDiffG / dirLen * k, twoPi);
227
228 // Now add the negated dot product for the remaining in-cell position
229
230 float3_X inCellPosition;
231 switch(simDim)
232 {
233 case DIM2:
234   inCellPosition = axisSwap_m.rotate(
235     float3_X{particle[position_].x(), particle[position_].y(), 0.0_X});

```

```

236   break;
237 case DIM3:
238   inCellPosition = axisSwap_m.rotate(particle[position_]);
239   break;
240 }
241 // quick and dirty fix:
242 // just rotating the in cell position will give negative values if an axis
243 // is reversed but we need the distance from the cell origin. (rotated + 1)
244 // % 1 should be correct.
245 for(int d = 0; d < 3u; d++)
246 {
247   inCellPosition[d] = math::fmod(inCellPosition[d] + 1.0_X, 1.0_X);
248 }
249
250 const float_X distDiffI
251   = float_X(inCellPosition.z()) * CELL_LENGTH_DET_Z_DIR * dir.z()
252   + float_X(inCellPosition.x()) * CELL_LENGTH_DET_X_DIR * dir.x()
253   + float_X(inCellPosition.y()) * CELL_LENGTH_DET_Y_DIR * dir.y();
254 phase += math::fmod(-distDiffI / dirLen * k, twoPi);
255
256 /*if(dir.z() > 1e-6)
257 {
258   printf("Dir: %g, %g, %g\n", dir.x(), dir.y(), dir.z());
259   printf("%i,%i -> %g+%g+%g=%g -> %g\n", globalCellIdx.y(),
260     globalCellIdx.z(), particle[startPhase_], curPhase_, -distDiffG * k,
261     -distDiffI * k, particle[startPhase_] + curPhase_, phase+2*PI);
262 }*/
263
264 trigo_X sinPhase, cosPhase;
265 pmacc::math::sincos<trigo_X>(phase, sinPhase, cosPhase);
266 const trigo_X amplitude{particle[weighting_]};
267 alpaka::atomicAdd(
268   acc,
269   &oldVal.get_real(),
270   static_cast<FloatType>(amplitude * cosPhase),
271   alpaka::hierarchy::Blocks{});
272 alpaka::atomicAdd(
273   acc,
274   &oldVal.get_imag(),
275   static_cast<FloatType>(amplitude * sinPhase),
276   alpaka::hierarchy::Blocks{});
277 }
278 };
279 } // namespace acc
280 /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the AddWaveParticles device
281 * accumulation functor
282 *
283 * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
284 */
285 template<typename T_Species> struct AddWaveParticles
286 {
287   private:
288   using Species = T_Species;

```

```

289 using FrameType = typename Species::FrameType;
290
291 public:
292 using AccFunctorType = acc::AddWaveParticles<T_Species>;
293 using FloatType = float_64;
294 //! type used to store detector cell values
295 using ComponentType = typename pmacc::math::Complex<FloatType>;
296 using Type = typename pmacc::math::Vector<ComponentType, DIM1>;
297
298 //! the value used to initialize (reset) detector storage
299 const Type initialValue = Type::create(0.0);
300
301 //! Get unit dimension of the values accumulated on the detector
302 HINLINE std::vector<float_64> getUnitDimension()
303 {
304     /*
305     */
306     std::vector<float_64> unitDimension(7, 0.0);
307     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::length) = 0.0;
308     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::mass) = 0.0;
309     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::time) = -0.0;
310     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::electricCurrent) = 0.0;
311     return unitDimension;
312 }
313
314 //! Get the SI unit conversion for the values accumulated on the detector
315 HDINLINE float_64 getUnit()
316 {
317     return 1.0;
318 }
319
320 //! Get a descriptive name of this accumulation policy
321 HINLINE static std::string getName()
322 {
323     return "AddWaveParticles";
324 }
325
326 //! Get a descriptive name for the openPMD mesh storing detector output
327 HINLINE static std::string getOpenPMDMeshName()
328 {
329     return "amplitude";
330 }
331
332 HINLINE std::string getOpenPMDMeshSuffix(uint32_t component) const
333 {
334     return "";
335 }
336
337 /** Create a device side particle accumulation functor for the
338  * AddWaveParticles policy
339  *
340  * @param currentStep current simulation step
341  * @param detector detector description

```

```

342      * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
343      * @return device side functor
344     */
345 HINLINE acc::AddWaveParticles<T_Species> operator()(
346     uint32_t const& currentStep,
347     DetectorParams const& detector,
348     DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize,
349     externalBeam::AxisSwap const& axisSwap) const
350 {
351     return acc::AddWaveParticles<T_Species>(
352     currentStep,
353     detector,
354     simSize,
355     axisSwap);
356 }
357 };
358 } // namespace accumulation
359 } // namespace photonDetector
360 } // namespace plugins
361 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 70. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AmplitudeWithPolarization.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.def"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace plugins
12 {
13 namespace photonDetector
14 {
15 namespace accumulation
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 /** Accumulation device functor for simple particle counting
20  *
21  * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
22  */
23 template<typename T_Species> struct AmplitudeWithPolarization
24 {
25     public:
26     using ValueType = float_64;

```

```

27  ///! type used to store detector cell values
28  using Type = pmacc::math::Vector<ValueType, DIM2>;
29
30  /** CountParticles device functor constructor
31   *
32   * @param currentStep current simulation time step
33   * @param detector detector description
34   * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
35   */
36  HDINLINE AmplitudeWithPolarization(
37      uint32_t const currentStep,
38      DetectorParams const detector,
39      DataSpace<simDim> const simSize)
40      : detector_m(detector)
41        , simSize_m(simSize)
42  {
43  }
44
45  /** accumulate particle on a detector cell
46   *
47   * @param acc alpaka accelerator
48   * @param detectorBox detector data box
49   * @param targetCellIdx the index of the detector cell hit by the particle
50   * @param particle particle to accumulate
51   * @param globalCellIdx the index of the cell from which the particle has
52   * left the simulation box (the cell in GUARD where the particle will be
53   * deleted). In the detector coordinate system.
54   */
55  template<typename T_Acc, typename T_DetectorBox, typename T_Particle>
56  DINLINE void operator()(
57      T_Acc const& acc,
58      T_DetectorBox detectorBox,
59      const DataSpace<DIM2>& targetCellIdx,
60      const T_Particle& particle,
61      const DataSpace<simDim>& globalCellIdx) const
62  {
63      const ValueType weight = precisionCast<ValueType>(particle[weighting_]);
64      const float_X particleAngle = particle[polarizationAngle_];
65
66      /// TODO: global polarization angle definition
67
68      /* Detector coordinate system viewed from the simulation:
69       *
70       * |-----|
71       * |      x| |
72       * |      z(x) ---> |
73       * |              y |
74       * |-----|
75       *
76       */
77
78      const ValueType valX = weight * math::sin(particleAngle);
79      const ValueType valY = weight * math::cos(particleAngle);

```

```

80
81      cupla::atomicAdd(
82          acc,
83          &((detectorBox(targetCellIdx))[0]),
84          valX,
85          alpaka::hierarchy::Blocks{});
86      cupla::atomicAdd(
87          acc,
88          &((detectorBox(targetCellIdx))[1]),
89          valY,
90          alpaka::hierarchy::Blocks{});
91  }
92
93  private:
94      PMACC_ALIGN(detector_m, const DetectorParams);
95      PMACC_ALIGN(simSize_m, const DataSpace<simDim>);
96  };
97  } /// namespace acc
98  /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the CountParticles device
99   * accumulation functor
100  *
101  * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
102  */
103  template<typename T_Species> struct AmplitudeWithPolarization
104  {
105  public:
106      ///! type used to store detector cell values
107      using Type = pmacc::math::Vector<float_64, DIM2>;
108      ///! the value used to initialize (reset) detector storage
109      const Type initValue = Type::create(0.0);
110      using AccFuncType = acc::AmplitudeWithPolarization<T_Species>;
111
112      ///! Get unit dimension of the values accumulated on the detector
113      HDINLINE std::vector<float_64> getUnitDimension()
114      {
115          /*
116           */
117          std::vector<float_64> unitDimension(7, 0.0);
118          unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::length) = 0.0;
119          unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::mass) = 0.0;
120          unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::time) = -0.0;
121          unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::electricCurrent) = 0.0;
122          return unitDimension;
123      }
124
125      ///! Get the SI unit conversion for the values accumulated on the detector
126      HDINLINE float_64 getUnit()
127      {
128          return 1.0;
129      }
130
131      ///! Get a descriptive name for the openPMD mesh storing detector output
132      HDINLINE static std::string getOpenPMDMeshName()

```

```

133 {
134     return "amplitude";
135 }
136
137 HINLINE std::string getOpenPMDMeshSuffix(uint32_t component) const
138 {
139     if(component == 0u)
140         return "_X";
141     else
142         return "_Y";
143 }
144
145 ///! Get a descriptive name of this accumulation policy
146 HINLINE static std::string getName()
147 {
148     return "AmplitudeWithPolarization";
149 }
150
151 /** Create a device side particle accumulation functor for the CountParticles
152  * policy
153  * @param currentStep current simulation step
154  * @param detector detector description
155  * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
156  * @return device side functor
157  */
158 HINLINE AccFunctorType operator()(
159     uint32_t const& currentStep,
160     DetectorParams const& detector,
161     DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize,
162     externalBeam::AxisSwap const& axisSwap) const
163 {
164     return AccFunctorType(currentStep, detector, simSize);
165 }
166 };
167
168
169 } // namespace accumulation
170 } // namespace photonDetector
171 } // namespace plugins
172 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 71. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AmplitudeWithPolarization.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6

```

```

7 #include "picongpu/particles/traits/SpeciesEligibleForSolver.hpp"
8 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
9
10 #include <pmacc/traits/HasIdentifiers.hpp>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14     namespace plugins
15     {
16         namespace photonDetector
17         {
18             namespace accumulation
19             {
20                 namespace acc
21                 {
22                     template<typename T_Species> struct AmplitudeWithPolarization;
23                 } // namespace acc
24
25                 /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the CountParticles device
26                  * accumulation functor
27                  * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
28                  */
29                 template<typename T_Species> struct AmplitudeWithPolarization;
30             } // namespace accumulation
31         } namespace particleHandlers
32         {
33             /** Simply count real particles hitting a detector cell.
34              * A particle accumulation policy for a particle detector.
35              */
36             struct AmplitudeWithPolarization
37             {
38                 ///! Get a functor factory type for a give particle species type
39                 template<typename T_Species> struct apply
40                 {
41                     using type = picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::accumulation::
42                         AmplitudeWithPolarization<T_Species>;
43                 };
44             };
45         } // namespace particleHandlers
46     } // namespace photonDetector
47 } // namespace plugins
48
49 namespace particles
50 {
51     namespace traits
52     {
53         ///! Check if a particle species has all the required identifiers and flags for
54         ///! the CountParticles policy
55         template<typename T_Species>
56         struct SpeciesEligibleForSolver<
57             T_Species,

```

```

60     picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::particleHandlers::
61     AmplitudeWithPolarization>
62 {
63     using FrameType = typename T_Species::FrameType;
64     using RequiredIdentifiers = MakeSeq_t<weighting, polarizationAngle>;
65     using type = typename pmacc::traits::
66     HasIdentifiers<FrameType, RequiredIdentifiers>::type;
67 };
68 } // namespace traits
69 } // namespace particles
70 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 72. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountMacroParticles.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.def"
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace plugins
12     {
13         namespace photonDetector
14         {
15             namespace accumulation
16             {
17                 namespace acc
18                 {
19                     /** Accumulation device functor for simple particle counting
20                      *
21                      * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
22                      */
23                     template<typename T_Species> struct CountMacroParticles
24                     {
25                         public:
26                             /** type used to store detector cell values
27                              */
28                             using Type = float_64;
29
30                             /** CountParticles device functor constructor
31                              *
32                              * @param currentStep current simulation time step
33                              * @param detector detector description
34                              * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
35                              */
36                             HDINLINE CountMacroParticles(

```

```

36         uint32_t const& currentStep,
37         DetectorParams const& detector,
38         DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize)
39         : detector_m(detector)
40         , simSize_m(simSize)
41         {
42     }
43
44     /** accumulate particle on a detector cell
45     *
46     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
47     * @param detectorBox detector data box
48     * @param targetCellIdx the index of the detector cell hit by the particle
49     * @param particle particle to accumulate
50     * @param globalCellIdx the index of the cell from which the particle has
51     * left the simulation box (the cell in GUARD where the particle will be
52     * deleted). In the detector coordinate system.
53     */
54     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_DetectorBox, typename T_Particle>
55     HDINLINE void operator()(
56         T_Acc const& acc,
57         T_DetectorBox detectorBox,
58         const DataSpace<DIM2>& targetCellIdx,
59         const T_Particle& particle,
60         const DataSpace<simDim>& globalCellIdx) const
61     {
62         cupla::atomicAdd(
63             acc,
64             &(detectorBox(targetCellIdx)[0]),
65             1.0,
66             alpaka::hierarchy::Blocks{});
67     }
68
69     private:
70         PMACC_ALIGN(detector_m, const DetectorParams);
71         PMACC_ALIGN(simSize_m, const DataSpace<simDim>);
72     };
73 } // namespace acc
74 /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the CountParticles device
75  * accumulation functor
76  *
77  * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
78  */
79     template<typename T_Species> struct CountMacroParticles
80     {
81     public:
82         /** type used to store detector cell values
83          *
84          * TODO: switch to uint (MPI reduce needs a new specialization)
85          */
86         using ComponentType = float_64;
87         using Type = pmacc::math::Vector<ComponentType, DIM1>;
88         /** the value used to initialize (reset) detector storage
89          */
90         const Type initValue = Type::create(0.0);
91         using AccFunctorType = acc::CountMacroParticles<T_Species>;

```

```

89
90 //! Get unit dimension of the values accumulated on the detector
91 HINLINE std::vector<float_64> getUnitDimension()
92 {
93     /*
94     */
95     std::vector<float_64> unitDimension(7, 0.0);
96     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::length) = 0.0;
97     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::mass) = 0.0;
98     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::time) = -0.0;
99     unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::electricCurrent) = 0.0;
100     return unitDimension;
101 }
102
103 //! Get the SI unit conversion for the values accumulated on the detector
104 HDINLINE float_64 getUnit()
105 {
106     return 1.0;
107 }
108
109 //! Get a descriptive name for the openPMD mesh storing detector output
110 HINLINE static std::string getOpenPMDMeshName()
111 {
112     return "macroParticleCount";
113 }
114
115 //! Get a descriptive name of this accumulation policy
116 HINLINE static std::string getName()
117 {
118     return "CountMacroParticles";
119 }
120
121 HINLINE std::string getOpenPMDMeshSuffix(uint32_t component) const
122 {
123     return "";
124 }
125
126 /** Create a device side particle accumulation functor for the CountParticles
127  * policy
128  *
129  * @param currentStep current simulation step
130  * @param detector detector description
131  * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
132  * @return device side functor
133  */
134 HINLINE acc::CountMacroParticles<T_Species> operator()(
135     uint32_t const& currentStep,
136     DetectorParams const& detector,
137     DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize,
138     externalBeam::AxisSwap const& axisSwap) const
139 {
140     return acc::CountMacroParticles<T_Species>(currentStep, detector, simSize);
141 }

```

```

142 };
143 } // namespace accumulation
144 } // namespace photonDetector
145 } // namespace plugins
146 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 73. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/AddWaveParticles.def

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
5
6 #include "picongpu/particles/traits/SpeciesEligibleForSolver.hpp"
7 #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/AxisSwap.def"
8 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
9
10 #include <pmacc/math/Complex.hpp>
11 #include <pmacc/traits/HasFlag.hpp>
12 #include <pmacc/traits/HasIdentifiers.hpp>
13
14 #include <boost/mpl/and.hpp>
15 #include <boost/mpl/or.hpp>
16
17 #include <complex>
18 namespace picongpu
19 {
20     namespace plugins
21     {
22         namespace photonDetector
23         {
24             namespace accumulation
25             {
26                 namespace acc
27                 {
28                     template<typename T_Species> struct AddWaveParticles;
29                 } // namespace acc
30
31                 template<typename T_Species> struct AddWaveParticles;
32             } // namespace accumulation
33             namespace particleHandlers
34             {
35                 /** Sum amplitude and phase of wave like particles hitting a detector cell
36                  *
37                  * A particle accumulation policy for a particle detector.
38                  */
39                 struct AddWaveParticles
40                 {
41                     //! Get a functor factory type for a give particle species type

```

```

42 template<typename T_Species> struct apply
43 {
44     using type
45     = picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::accumulation::AddWaveParticles<
46     T_Species>;
47 };
48 };
49 } // namespace particleHandlers
50
51 } // namespace photonDetector
52 } // namespace plugins
53
54 namespace particles
55 {
56 namespace traits
57 {
58     ///! Check if a particle species has all the required identifiers and flags for
59     ///! the AddWaveParticles policy
60     template<typename T_Species>
61     struct SpeciesEligibleForSolver<
62     T_Species,
63     picongpu::plugins::photonDetector::particleHandlers::AddWaveParticles>
64     {
65     using FrameType = typename T_Species::FrameType;
66
67     /// This accumulations strategy always needs position and weighting.
68     using AlwaysRequiredIdentifiers
69     = MakeSeq_t<position<>, weighting, startPhase>;
70     /// Particles has the phase attribute. This should be updated by pusher on
71     /// each time step. Wavelength is calculated per particle from particle
72     /// momentum.
73     using DynamicWavelengthScenarioAttributes = MakeSeq_t<momentum>;
74
75     using SpeciesHasBaseIdentifiers = typename pmacc::traits::
76     HasIdentifiers<FrameType, AlwaysRequiredIdentifiers>::type;
77
78     using SpeciesHasConstScenarioIdentifiers =
79     typename pmacc::traits::HasFlag<FrameType, wavelength<>>::type;
80
81     using SpeciesHasDynamicScenarioIdentifiers = typename pmacc::traits::
82     HasIdentifiers<FrameType, DynamicWavelengthScenarioAttributes>::type;
83
84     using type = typename bml::and_<
85     SpeciesHasBaseIdentifiers,
86     typename bml::or_<
87     SpeciesHasConstScenarioIdentifiers,
88     SpeciesHasDynamicScenarioIdentifiers>::type>::type;
89 };
90 } // namespace traits
91 } // namespace particles
92 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 74. plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.hpp

```

1 /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/CountParticles.def"
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace plugins
12 {
13 namespace photonDetector
14 {
15 namespace accumulation
16 {
17 namespace acc
18 {
19 /** Accumulation device functor for simple particle counting
20 *
21 * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
22 */
23 template<typename T_Species> struct CountParticles
24 {
25     public:
26     ///! type used to store detector cell values
27     using Type = float_64;
28
29     /** CountParticles device functor constructor
30     *
31     * @param currentStep current simulation time step
32     * @param detector detector description
33     * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
34     */
35     HDINLINE CountParticles(
36     uint32_t const& currentStep,
37     DetectorParams const& detector,
38     DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize)
39     : detector_m(detector)
40     , simSize_m(simSize)
41     {
42     }
43
44     /** accumulate particle on a detector cell
45     *
46     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
47     * @param detectorBox detector data box
48     * @param targetCellIdx the index of the detector cell hit by the particle

```

```

49  * @param particle particle to accumulate
50  * @param globalCellIdx the index of the cell from which the particle has
51  * left the simulation box (the cell in GUARD where the particle will be
52  * deleted). In the detector coordinate system.
53  */
54  template<typename T_Acc, typename T_DetectorBox, typename T_Particle>
55  DINLINE void operator()(
56      T_Acc const& acc,
57      T_DetectorBox detectorBox,
58      const DataSpace<DIM2>& targetCellIdx,
59      const T_Particle& particle,
60      const DataSpace<simDim>& globalCellIdx) const
61  {
62      const Type amplitude = precisionCast<Type>(particle[weighting_]);
63      cupla::atomicAdd(
64          acc,
65          &(detectorBox(targetCellIdx)[0]),
66          amplitude,
67          alpaka::hierarchy::Blocks{});
68  }
69
70  private:
71  PMACC_ALIGN(detector_m, const DetectorParams);
72  PMACC_ALIGN(simSize_m, const DataSpace<simDim>);
73  };
74  } // namespace acc
75  /** Functor factory (host side functor) for the CountParticles device
76   * accumulation functor
77   *
78   * @tparam T_Species type of the particle species accumulated on the detector
79   */
80  template<typename T_Species> struct CountParticles
81  {
82  public:
83      /** type used to store detector cell values
84       using ComponentType = float_64;
85       using Type = pmacc::math::Vector<ComponentType, DIM1>;
86       /** the value used to initialize (reset) detector storage
87       const Type initValue = Type::create(0.0);
88       using AccFuncType = acc::CountParticles<T_Species>;
89
90       /** Get unit dimension of the values accumulated on the detector
91       HINLINE std::vector<float_64> getUnitDimension()
92       {
93           /*
94            */
95           std::vector<float_64> unitDimension(7, 0.0);
96           unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::length) = 0.0;
97           unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::mass) = 0.0;
98           unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::time) = -0.0;
99           unitDimension.at(SIBaseUnits::electricCurrent) = 0.0;
100          return unitDimension;
101      }

```

```

102
103  /** Get the SI unit conversion for the values accumulated on the detector
104  HINLINE float_64 getUnit()
105  {
106      return 1.0;
107  }
108
109  /** Get a descriptive name for the openPMD mesh storing detector output
110  HINLINE static std::string getOpenPMDMeshName()
111  {
112      return "particleCount";
113  }
114
115  /** Get a descriptive name of this accumulation policy
116  HINLINE static std::string getName()
117  {
118      return "CountParticles";
119  }
120
121  HINLINE std::string getOpenPMDMeshSuffix(uint32_t component) const
122  {
123      return "";
124  }
125
126  /** Create a device side particle accumulation functor for the CountParticles
127   * policy
128   *
129   * @param currentStep current simulation step
130   * @param detector detector description
131   * @param simSize simulation size (in the detector coordinate system)
132   * @return device side functor
133   */
134  HINLINE acc::CountParticles<T_Species> operator()(
135      uint32_t const& currentStep,
136      DetectorParams const& detector,
137      DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize,
138      externalBeam::AxisSwap const& axisSwap) const
139  {
140      return acc::CountParticles<T_Species>(currentStep, detector, simSize);
141  }
142  };
143  } // namespace accumulation
144  } // namespace photonDetector
145  } // namespace plugins
146  } // namespace picongpu

```

File 75. plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.hpp

1 /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */

```

2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
8
9 #include <pmacc/math/Vector.hpp>
10
11 namespace picongpu
12 {
13 namespace plugins
14 {
15 namespace photonDetector
16 {
17 DetectorParams::DetectorParams(
18     const DataSpace<DIM2>& size,
19     const pmacc::math::Vector<float_X, DIM2>& anglePerCell,
20     const DetectorPlacement& detectorPlacement)
21     : size(size)
22     , anglePerCell(anglePerCell)
23     , detectorPlacement(detectorPlacement)
24 {
25 }
26 } // namespace photonDetector
27 } // namespace plugins
28 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 76. plugins/photonDetector/DetectParticles.kernel

```

1 /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3 #pragma once
4
5 #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7 #include <pmacc/lockstep.hpp>
8
9 namespace picongpu
10 {
11 namespace plugins
12 {
13 namespace photonDetector
14 {
15 /** Detects particles
16  *
17  * @tparam T_numWorkers number of virtual workers
18  * @param acc alpaka accelerator
19  * @param particleBox data box with particles

```

```

20 * @param localOffset offset of the current rank
21 * @param detectParticle unary particle functor with the signature:
22 * void(acc, particle, superCellPosition, detectorBox)
23 * @param detector device side detector box
24 * @param mapper kernel instance to super cell mapping
25 */
26 template<uint32_t T_numWorkers> struct DetectParticles
27 {
28     template<
29         typename T_Acc,
30         typename T_ParticleBox,
31         typename T_DetectParticle,
32         typename T_DetectorBox,
33         typename T_Mapping,
34         typename T_Filter>
35     DINLINE void operator()(
36         T_Acc const& acc,
37         T_ParticleBox const particleBox,
38         DataSpace<simDim> const localOffset,
39         T_DetectParticle const detectParticle,
40         T_DetectorBox detectorBox,
41         T_Mapping const mapper,
42         pmacc::DataSpace<simDim> beginCellIdxLocal,
43         pmacc::DataSpace<simDim> endCellIdxLocal,
44         T_Filter filter) const
45     {
46         typedef T_ParticleBox ParticleBox;
47         using FramePtr = typename T_ParticleBox::FramePtr;
48
49         const DataSpace<simDim> superCellIdx
50             = mapper.getSuperCellIndex(DataSpace<simDim>(cupla::blockIdx(acc)));
51         auto const blockStartCellLocal
52             = (superCellIdx - mapper.getGuardingSuperCells())
53             * SuperCellSize::toRT();
54         const DataSpace<simDim> superCellPosition
55             = blockStartCellLocal + localOffset;
56         uint32_t const workerIdx = cupla::threadIdx(acc).x;
57
58         FramePtr frame = particleBox.getFirstFrame(superCellIdx);
59         auto& superCell = particleBox.getSuperCell(superCellIdx);
60         uint32_t const numParticlesInSupercell = superCell.getNumParticles();
61         uint32_t const frameSize
62             = pmacc::math::CT::volume<SuperCellSize>::type::value;
63
64         auto forEachFrameElem
65             = lockstep::makeForEach<frameSize, T_numWorkers>(workerIdx);
66
67         auto accFilter = filter(
68             acc,
69             (superCellIdx - mapper.getGuardingSuperCells()),
70             lockstep::Worker<T_numWorkers>{workerIdx});
71
72         // go over all frames containing particles

```

```

73 for(uint32_t i = 0; i < numParticlesInSuperCell; i += frameSize)
74 {
75     // Each virtual worker calls the detectParticle functor for one particle
76     // in the current frame
77     forEachFrameElem(
78         [&](lockstep::Idx const idx)
79         {
80             if(i + idx < numParticlesInSuperCell)
81             {
82                 // TODO make detectoParticle into a pmacc::Filtered functor
83                 auto particle = frame[idx];
84                 if(accFilter(acc, particle))
85                 {
86                     // Check if it fits the external cells range
87                     auto const cellInSuperCell
88                         = DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::template map<SuperCellSize>(
89                             particle[localCellIdx_]);
90                     auto const localCell = blockStartCellLocal + cellInSuperCell;
91                     for(uint32_t d = 0; d < simDim; d++)
92                     {
93                         (localCell[d] < beginCellIdxLocal[d])
94                         || (localCell[d] > endCellIdxLocal[d])
95                         return;
96                     }
97                     detectParticle(acc, particle, superCellPosition, detectorBox);
98                 }
99             }
100         });
101     frame = particleBox.getNextFrame(frame);
102 }
103 }
104 };
105 } // namespace photonDetector
106 } // namespace plugins
107 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 77. plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetectorImpl.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/AxisSwap.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.hpp"
9  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/accumulation/accumulationPolicies.hpp"
10
11 #include <pmacc/algorithms/math.hpp>

```

```

12 #include <pmacc/dataManagement/ISimulationData.hpp>
13 #include <pmacc/debug/VerboseLog.hpp>
14 #include <pmacc/math/Vector.hpp>
15 #include <pmacc/memory/buffers/HostDeviceBuffer.hpp>
16
17 #include <cmath>
18
19 namespace picongpu
20 {
21     namespace plugins
22     {
23         namespace photonDetector
24         {
25             namespace detail
26             {
27                 // TODO move this to pmacc::math
28                 //! Round a floating point value towards zero
29                 template<typename T> HDINLINE int roundTowardsZero(T const& val);
30
31                 template<> HDINLINE int roundTowardsZero<float>(float const& val)
32                 {
33                     #if(CUDA_DEVICE_COMPILE == 1) // we are on gpu
34                         return ::_float2int_rz(val);
35                     #endif
36                     int ceilVal = math::ceil(math::abs(val));
37                     return val < 0 ? -1 * ceilVal : ceilVal;
38                 }
39                 template<> HDINLINE int roundTowardsZero(double const& val)
40                 {
41                     #if(CUDA_DEVICE_COMPILE == 1) // we are on gpu
42                         return ::_double2int_rz(val);
43                     #endif
44                     int ceilVal = math::ceil(math::abs(val));
45                     return val < 0 ? -1 * ceilVal : ceilVal;
46                 }
47             }
48
49             /**
50              * Calculates the cell index on the detector that a photon reaches when it
51              * continues with the current speed
52              *
53              * @tparam T_Config detector configuration from photonDetector.param
54              */
55             template<typename T_Config> struct GetTargetCellIdx
56             {
57                 using Config = T_Config;
58                 static constexpr float_X cellWidth
59                     = float_X(Config::cellWidth / UNIT_LENGTH);
60                 static constexpr float_X cellHeight
61                     = float_X(Config::cellHeight / UNIT_LENGTH);
62
63                 /** GetTargetCellIdx constructor
64                  *
65                  * @param detectorParams detector parameters (see DetectorParams.def)

```

```

65  * @param simSize simulation size (shape) in cells (in the detector
66  * coordinate system)
67  * @param axisSwap used to switch between the PIconGPU and the detector
68  * coordinate system
69  */
70  HDINLINE GetTargetCellIdx(
71  DetectorParams const& detectorParams,
72  DataSpace<simDim> const& simSize,
73  externalBeam::AxisSwap const& axisSwap)
74  : detector_m(detectorParams)
75  , simSize_m(simSize)
76  , axisSwap_m(axisSwap)
77  {
78  }
79
80  /**
81  * Calculates the index on the detector and the time of impact
82  * Returns true, if the detector was hit, false otherwise.
83  * On false \ref targetIdx and \ref dt are undefined
84  *
85  * @param particle particle to detect
86  * @param globalIdx the global index of the particle cell (in the detector
87  * coordinate system)
88  * @param targetIdx a reference to a variable storing the result (index on
89  * the detector)
90  */
91  template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle>
92  DINLINE bool operator()(
93  T_Acc const& acc,
94  T_Particle const& particle,
95  DataSpace<DIM3> const& globalIdx,
96  DataSpace<DIM2>& targetIdx) const
97  {
98  /* Detector coordinate system viewed from the simulation:
99  *
100  *      |-----|
101  *      |         |
102  *      |      x|  |
103  *      |      z(x) ---> |
104  *      |         y   |
105  *      |-----|
106  */
107
108  // Get the dimensions of a picongpu cell in the detector coordinate system
109  // (only axes parallel to the detector plane)
110  float_X const CELL_LENGTH_DET_X_DIR
111  = std::get<0>(getCellLengths(detector_m.detectorPlacement));
112  float_X const CELL_LENGTH_DET_Y_DIR
113  = std::get<1>(getCellLengths(detector_m.detectorPlacement));
114  // get the direction in which the particle is moving fro its momentum
115  float3_X momentum = particle[momentum_];
116  float3_X dirPicSystem(momentum / math::abs(momentum));
117  // switch to the detector coordinate system

```

```

118  float3_X dir = axisSwap_m.rotate(dirPicSystem);
119
120  // Not flying towards detector? -> exit
121  if(dir.z() <= 0)
122  return false;
123
124  /* Notice:
125  * `parataxis` was using `float2int_rd` so it was rounding down.
126  * I think we should be rounding towards zero instead but maybe I'm
127  * wrong.
128  */
129
130  #if SIMDIM == DIM2
131  const float3_X inCellPosition3D = axisSwap_m.rotate(
132  float3_X{particle[position_].x(), particle[position_].y(), 0.0_X});
133  #else
134  const float3_X inCellPosition3D = axisSwap_m.rotate(particle[position_]);
135  #endif
136  const float2_X inCellPosition{
137  math::fmod(inCellPosition3D.x() + 1.0_X, 1.0_X),
138  math::fmod(inCellPosition3D.y() + 1.0_X, 1.0_X)};
139
140  // Calculate angle in "up" dimension (when viewed from front) ->
141  // X-dimension of detector Notice: the z axis is the axis perpendicular to
142  // the detector
143  float_X angleBack = math::atan2<trigo_X>(dir.x(), dir.z());
144  // Calculate cell index on detector by angle (histogram-like binning)
145  float_X cellIdxX = angleBack / detector_m.anglePerCell.x();
146  targetIdx.x() = roundTowardsZero(cellIdxX);
147  // The angles are taken from the center of the volume. If the volume is
148  // larger than 1 detector cell particles from the outside of the volume
149  // might hit another detector cell. So add this additional distance from
150  // the volume center Note: Offset is really small compared to index. So
151  // adding directly might produce slightly inaccurate results as e.g.
152  // 512(half size) + 1e-5(1 simcell offset) is still 512 for float32 Hence
153  // we strip off the large (integer) part, use the remainder and then put
154  // integers together again (see Kahan summation)
155  cellIdxX -= targetIdx.x();
156  cellIdxX += (globalIdx.x() - simSize_m.x() / 2 + inCellPosition.x())
157  * CELL_LENGTH_DET_X_DIR / cellHeight;
158  targetIdx.x() += pmacc::math::float2int_rd(cellIdxX);
159
160  // Same for "right" dimension -> Y-dimension of detector
161  float_X angleDown = math::atan2<trigo_X>(dir.y(), dir.z());
162  float_X cellIdxY = angleDown / detector_m.anglePerCell.y();
163
164  targetIdx.y() = roundTowardsZero(cellIdxY);
165  cellIdxY -= targetIdx.y();
166  cellIdxY += (globalIdx.y() - simSize_m.y() / 2 + inCellPosition.y())
167  * CELL_LENGTH_DET_Y_DIR / cellWidth;
168  targetIdx.y() += pmacc::math::float2int_rd(cellIdxY);
169
170  // Shift the origin to the center of the detector

```

```

171     targetIdx += detector_m.size / 2;
172
173     // Check bounds
174     return targetIdx.x() >= 0 && targetIdx.x() < detector_m.size.x()
175         && targetIdx.y() >= 0 && targetIdx.y() < detector_m.size.y();
176 }
177
178 private:
179 PMACC_ALIGN(detector_m, const DetectorParams);
180 PMACC_ALIGN(simSize_m, const DataSpace<simDim>);
181 PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap_m, const externalBeam::AxisSwap);
182 };
183
184 ///! Unary particle functor for particle detection.
185 template<typename T_GetTargetCellIdx, typename T_AccumFuncor>
186 struct DetectParticle
187 {
188     public:
189     /** DetectParticle constructor
190     *
191     * @param getTargetCellIdx unary particle functor used to determine the
192     * detector cell
193     * @param accumFuncor unary particle functor used for detector value
194     * accumulation
195     * @param axisSwap used to switch between the PIconGPU and the detector
196     * coordinate system
197     */
198     HDINLINE DetectParticle(
199         T_GetTargetCellIdx const& getTargetCellIdx,
200         T_AccumFuncor const& accumFuncor,
201         externalBeam::AxisSwap const& axisSwap)
202         : getTargetCellIdx_m(getTargetCellIdx)
203         , accumFuncor_m(accumFuncor)
204         , axisSwap_m(axisSwap)
205     {
206     }
207
208     /** detect particle
209     *
210     * Check if/where the particle lands on the detector if so call the
211     * accumulation functor.
212     *
213     * @param acc alpaka accelerator
214     * @param particle particle to detect
215     * @param superCellPosition the position of the super cell with the particle
216     * in the global domain
217     * @param detectorBox detector buffer data box
218     */
219     template<typename T_Acc, typename T_Particle, typename T_DetectorBox>
220     HDINLINE void operator()(
221         T_Acc const& acc,
222         T_Particle const& particle,
223         DataSpace<simDim> const& superCellPosition,

```

```

224     T_DetectorBox& detectorBox) const
225     {
226         // calculate global cell index
227         DataSpace<simDim> const localCell(
228             pmacc::DataSpaceOperations<simDim>::map<SuperCellSize>(
229                 particle[localCellIdx_]);
230         DataSpace<simDim> const globalCellIdx = superCellPosition + localCell;
231         // transform into the detector coordinate system
232         DataSpace<DIM3> const globalCellIdxDet
233             = axisSwap_m.transformCellIdx(globalCellIdx);
234         // particle position on the detector, getTargetCellIdx_m writes here
235         DataSpace<DIM2> targetIdx;
236         // Get index on detector, if none found -> go out
237         if(getTargetCellIdx_m(acc, particle, globalCellIdxDet, targetIdx))
238             accumFuncor_m(acc, detectorBox, targetIdx, particle, globalCellIdxDet);
239     }
240
241     private:
242     PMACC_ALIGN(getTargetCellIdx_m, const T_GetTargetCellIdx);
243     PMACC_ALIGN(accumFuncor_m, const T_AccumFuncor);
244     PMACC_ALIGN(axisSwap_m, const externalBeam::AxisSwap);
245 };
246
247 } // namespace detail
248
249 /**
250  * Planar detector for particles that will accumulate incoming photons with the
251  * given policy
252  * @tparam T_Config:
253  *     policy AccumulationPolicy Defines how the detected particles change a
254  *     value at a detector cell. This type should define a meta function `apply`
255  *     which takes a species type as a template parameter and returns the
256  *     specialized type of a host side accumulation functor (device functor
257  *     factory). See ./accumulation for examples. float_64 distance distance from
258  *     the volume in meters float_64 cellWidth detector cell width float_64
259  *     cellHeight detector cell height
260  *
261  */
262 template<typename T_Config, typename T_Species> struct PhotonDetectorImpl
263 {
264     using Config = T_Config;
265     using Species = T_Species;
266     using AccumPolicy =
267         typename Config::AccumulationPolicy::template apply<Species>::type;
268     AccumPolicy accumHostFuncor;
269
270     ///! distance of the detector from the simulation box
271     static constexpr float_64 distance
272         = float_64(Config::distance / UNIT_LENGTH);
273     // detector cell dimensions
274     static constexpr float_64 cellWidth
275         = float_64(Config::cellWidth / UNIT_LENGTH);
276     static constexpr float_64 cellHeight

```

```

277     = float_64(Config::cellHeight / UNIT_LENGTH);
278     ///! type used to store detector cell values
279     using Type = typename AccumPolicy::Type;
280
281     private:
282     using Buffer = pmacc::HostDeviceBuffer<Type, 2>;
283     ///! A memory Buffer on both device and host used to store detector data
284     std::unique_ptr<Buffer> buffer;
285     ///! angle range covered by 1 cell
286     pmacc::math::Vector<float_64, 2> anglePerCell_m;
287     DetectorPlacement const detectorPlacement_m;
288
289     public:
290     ///! type of the particle functor used to detect particles
291     using DetectParticle = detail::DetectParticle<
292         detail::GetTargetCellIdx<Config>,
293         typename AccumPolicy::AccFunctorType>;
294
295     /** detector implementation constructor
296     *
297     * @param size the detector size (shape)
298     * @param detectorPlacement specifies the side of the simulation box against
299     * which the detector is placed
300     */
301     HINLINE PhotonDetectorImpl(
302         DataSpace<DIM2> const& size,
303         DetectorPlacement const detectorPlacement)
304         : detectorPlacement_m(detectorPlacement)
305         , accumHostFunctor(AccumPolicy())
306     {
307         buffer = std::make_unique<Buffer>(DataSpace<DIM2>(size));
308         /// initialize the device buffer with the initial value defined by the
309         /// accumulation policy (usually 0)
310         buffer->getDeviceBuffer().setValue(accumHostFunctor.initValue);
311         anglePerCell_m.x() = atan(cellHeight / distance);
312         anglePerCell_m.y() = atan(cellWidth / distance);
313     }
314     t
315     /** clear detector
316     *
317     * Resets all detector cells with the initial value defined by the
318     * accumulation policy (usually 0).
319     */
320     HINLINE void
321     resetDeviceBuffer()
322     {
323         buffer->getDeviceBuffer().setValue(AccumPolicy().initValue);
324     }
325
326     HINLINE typename Buffer::DataBoxType getHostDataBox()
327     {
328         return buffer->getHostBuffer().getDataBox();
329     };

```

```

330     }
331
332     HINLINE typename Buffer::DataBoxType getDeviceDataBox()
333     {
334         return buffer->getDeviceBuffer().getDataBox();
335     }
336
337     HINLINE void hostToDevice()
338     {
339         buffer->hostToDevice();
340     }
341
342     HINLINE void deviceToHost()
343     {
344         buffer->deviceToHost();
345     }
346
347     ///! Get detector size (shape)
348     HINLINE DataSpace<DIM2> getSize() const
349     {
350         return buffer->getHostBuffer().getDataSpace();
351     }
352
353     ///! Create a particle functor for detection in the DetectParticles kernel
354     HINLINE DetectParticle getDetectParticle(uint32_t currentStep) const
355     {
356         DataSpace<simDim> const simSize(
357             Environment<simDim>::get().SubGrid().getTotalDomain().size);
358         /* The simulation size has to be a 3D vector so that it can be transformed
359         into the detector coordinate system. */
360         DataSpace<DIM3> simSize3D;
361         switch(simDim)
362         {
363             case DIM2:
364                 simSize3D = DataSpace<DIM3>{simSize.x(), simSize.y(), 1};
365                 break;
366             case DIM3:
367                 simSize3D = simSize;
368                 break;
369         }
370         /// Object used to switch between simulation and detector coordinate systems
371         externalBeam::AxisSwap const axisSwap = getAxisSwap(detectorPlacement_m);
372         /// transform into detector system
373         DataSpace<DIM3> simSizeDet(axisSwap.rotate(simSize3D, true));
374         /// additional detector description for the device functors
375         DetectorParams detParams(
376             getSize(),
377             precisionCast<float_X>(anglePerCell_m),
378             detectorPlacement_m);
379         return DetectParticle(
380             detail::GetTargetCellIdx<Config>(detParams, simSizeDet, axisSwap),
381             accumHostFunctor(currentStep, detParams, simSizeDet, axisSwap),
382             axisSwap);

```

```

383 }
384
385 // TODO: add sth like validateConstraints from parataxis
386 };
387
388 } // namespace photonDetector
389 } // namespace plugins
390 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 78. plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetectorUtilities.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/externalBeam/Side.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def"
9
10 #include <experimental/optional>
11
12 namespace picongpu
13 {
14 namespace plugins
15 {
16 namespace photonDetector
17 {
18 //! Get the coordinate transform between simulation and detector systems based
19 //! on a detector placement
20 HINLINE externalBeam::AxisSwap getAxisSwap(
21     DetectorPlacement const& detectorPlacement)
22 {
23     switch(detectorPlacement)
24     {
25     case DetectorPlacement::XFront:
26         return externalBeam::ProbingSideCfg<externalBeam::XRSide>().getAxisSwap();
27     case DetectorPlacement::XRear:
28         return externalBeam::ProbingSideCfg<externalBeam::XSide>().getAxisSwap();
29     case DetectorPlacement::YFront:
30         return externalBeam::ProbingSideCfg<externalBeam::YRSide>().getAxisSwap();
31     case DetectorPlacement::YRear:
32         return externalBeam::ProbingSideCfg<externalBeam::YSide>().getAxisSwap();
33     case DetectorPlacement::ZFront:
34         return externalBeam::ProbingSideCfg<externalBeam::ZRSide>().getAxisSwap();
35     // case DetectorPlacement::ZRear:
36     default:
37         return externalBeam::ProbingSideCfg<externalBeam::ZSide>().getAxisSwap();
38     }

```

```

39 }
40
41 //! Get the pic cell dimensions along the detector coordinate system axes based
42 //! on a detector placement
43 HDINLINE constexpr auto getCellLengths(
44     DetectorPlacement const& detectorPlacement)
45 {
46     using ReturnT = std::tuple<float_X, float_X, float_X>;
47     switch(detectorPlacement)
48     {
49     case DetectorPlacement::XFront:
50         // SideXR: x_det is z_pic , y_det is y_pic
51         return ReturnT{CELL_DEPTH, CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_WIDTH};
52     case DetectorPlacement::XRear:
53         // SideX: x_det is z_pic , y_det is y_pic
54         return ReturnT{CELL_DEPTH, CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_WIDTH};
55     case DetectorPlacement::YFront:
56         // SideYR: x_det is z_pic , y_det is x_pic
57         return ReturnT{CELL_DEPTH, CELL_WIDTH, CELL_HEIGHT};
58     case DetectorPlacement::YRear:
59         // SideY: x_det is y_pic , y_det is x_pic
60         return ReturnT{CELL_DEPTH, CELL_WIDTH, CELL_HEIGHT};
61     case DetectorPlacement::ZFront:
62         // SideZR: x_det is y_pic , y_det is x_pic
63         return ReturnT{CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_WIDTH, CELL_DEPTH};
64     // case DetectorPlacement::ZRear:
65     default:
66         return ReturnT{CELL_HEIGHT, CELL_WIDTH, CELL_DEPTH};
67     }
68     // TODO it would be probably better to use case DetectorPlacement::ZRear: and
69     // handle default extra
70 }
71 } // namespace photonDetector
72 } // namespace plugins
73 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 79. plugins/photonDetector/PhotonDetectorWriter.hpp

```

1  /* Copyright 2021 Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include "picongpu/plugins/common/asStandardVector.hpp"
8  #include "picongpu/plugins/common/openPMDVersion.def"
9  #include "picongpu/plugins/common/openPMDWriteMeta.hpp"
10
11 #include <pmacc/assert.hpp>

```

```

12 #include <pmacc/dataManagement/DataConnector.hpp>
13 #include <pmacc/mappings/simulation/GridController.hpp>
14 #include <pmacc/math/Vector.hpp>
15 #include <pmacc/static_assert.hpp>
16
17 #include <cstdlib>
18 #include <string>
19 #include <vector>
20
21 #include <openPMD/openPMD.hpp>
22
23 namespace picongpu
24 {
25     namespace plugins
26     {
27         namespace photonDetector
28         {
29             /** Output writer for the photonDetector plugin.
30              *
31              * Data is written in serial mode.
32              * @tparam T_ValueType Type of the values stored in the output.
33              */
34             template<typename T_ValueType> struct PhotonDetectorWriter
35             {
36             private:
37                 /** a pointer to an openPMD API Series object
38                 std::unique_ptr<::openPMD::Series> openPMDSeries_m;
39                 /** strings defining the path to the series
40                 std::string const fileName_m, fileExtension_m, dir_m, fileInfix_m;
41                 /** backend specific configuration
42                 std::string const jsonConfig_m;
43                 /** detector size
44                 pmacc::math::UInt64<DIM2> const globalExtent_m;
45                 /** OpenPMD type specifier for the ValueType
46                 ::openPMD::Datatype datatype_m;
47                 /** output SI unit
48                 const float_64 unit_m;
49                 /** detector cell size
50                 float2_X const gridSpacing_m;
51                 /** unit dimension of the stored values
52                 std::map<::openPMD::UnitDimension, double> const unitMap_m;
53                 std::string const accumulationPolicyName_m;
54                 std::string const detectorPlacement_m;
55                 float_64 const detectorDistance_m;
56                 std::unique_ptr<::openPMD::Iteration> iteration_m;
57
58                 /** openPMD series iteration encoding
59                 * openPMD api can store iterations:
60                 * - in separate files (file based encoding)
61                 * - in the same file (group based encoding)
62                 * - send iterations via streaming api (value based encoding)
63                 */
64                 /** ::openPMD::IterationEncoding iterationEncoding_m;

```

```

65     bool const isMaster_m;
66     std::string meshName_m;
67
68     public:
69         /** Initializes a PhotonDetectorWriter object.
70         *
71         * @param fileName output file name, without the extensions.
72         * @param fileInfix openPMD filename infix (use to pick iteration encoding)
73         * @param fileExtension file extension, specifies the API backend.
74         * @param dir directory in simOutput where the output files are stored
75         * @param meshName mesh name for the stored data
76         * @param globalExtent detector size
77         * @param gridSpacing detector cell size
78         * @param unit output SI unit
79         * @param unitDimension unit dimension of the stored values
80         */
81         HINLINE PhotonDetectorWriter(
82             bool const& isMaster,
83             std::string const& fileName,
84             std::string const& fileInfix,
85             std::string const& fileExtension,
86             std::string const& dir,
87             std::string const& meshName,
88             pmacc::math::UInt64<DIM2> const& globalExtent,
89             float2_X const& gridSpacing,
90             float_64 const& unit,
91             std::vector<float_64> const& unitDimension,
92             std::string const& accumulationPolicyName,
93             std::string const& detectorPlacement,
94             float_64 const& detectorDistance)
95             : isMaster_m(isMaster)
96             , fileName_m(fileName)
97             , fileInfix_m(fileInfix)
98             , dir_m(dir)
99             , meshName_m(meshName)
100             , fileExtension_m(fileExtension)
101             , globalExtent_m(globalExtent)
102             , gridSpacing_m(gridSpacing)
103             , unit_m(unit)
104             , unitMap_m(openPMD::convertToUnitDimension(unitDimension))
105             , accumulationPolicyName_m(accumulationPolicyName)
106             , detectorPlacement_m(detectorPlacement)
107             , detectorDistance_m(detectorDistance)
108         {
109             datatype_m = ::openPMD::determineDatatype<T_ValueType>();
110
111             /** Create output directory and set permissions
112             pmacc::Filesystem<simDim>& fs = Environment<simDim>::get().Filesystem();
113             if(isMaster_m)
114             {
115                 fs.createDirectory(dir_m);
116                 fs.setDirectoryPermissions(dir_m);
117             }

```

```

118     openSeries(::openPMD::Access::CREATE);
119 }
120 }
121 -PhotonDetectorWriter()
122 {
123     closeSeries();
124 }
125
126 private:
127 /** Opens the openPMD series.
128  *
129  * @param at openPMD API access type.
130  */
131 HINLINE void openSeries(::openPMD::Access at)
132 {
133     if(!openPMDSeries_m)
134     {
135         std::string fullName
136             = dir_m + '/' + fileName_m + fileInfix_m + "." + fileExtension_m;
137         log<picLog::INPUT_OUTPUT>("PhotonDetectorWriter: Opening file: %1%"
138             % fullName);
139
140         // Open a series for a serial write.
141         openPMDSeries_m = std::make_unique<::openPMD::Series>(fullName, at);
142
143         log<picLog::INPUT_OUTPUT>(
144             "PhotonDetectorWriter: Successfully opened file: %1%"
145             % fullName);
146     }
147     else
148     {
149         throw std::runtime_error(
150             "PhotonDetectorWriter: Tried opening a Series while old "
151             "Series was still active.");
152     }
153 }
154
155 /** Closes the openPMD series
156 HINLINE void closeSeries()
157 {
158     if(openPMDSeries_m)
159     {
160         log<picLog::INPUT_OUTPUT>("PhotonDetectorWriter: Closing "
161             "openPMDSeries: %1%"
162             % (fileName_m + fileInfix_m + "." + fileExtension_m);
163         openPMDSeries_m.reset();
164         log<picLog::INPUT_OUTPUT>(
165             "PhotonDetectorWriter: successfully closed openPMD series: %1%"
166             % (fileName_m + fileInfix_m + "." + fileExtension_m);
167     }
168     else
169     {
170         throw std::runtime_error(

```

```

171         "PhotonDetectorWriter: Tried closing a Series that was not"
172         " active.");
173     }
174 }
175
176 /** Prepare an openPMD mesh for storage
177  *
178  * @param iteration
179  */
180 HINLINE ::openPMD::Mesh prepareMesh(std::string const& meshSuffix)
181 {
182     ::openPMD::Mesh mesh = iteration_m->meshes[meshName_m + meshSuffix];
183
184     mesh.setGridSpacing(openPMD::asStandardVector(gridSpacing_m));
185     mesh.setAxisLabels(std::vector<std::string>{"y", "x"});
186     mesh.setGridGlobalOffset(std::vector<float_64>{0.0, 0.0});
187     mesh.setGeometry(::openPMD::Mesh::Geometry::cartesian);
188     mesh.setDataOrder(::openPMD::Mesh::DataOrder::C);
189     mesh.setTimeOffset(0.0_X);
190     mesh.setGridUnitSI(UNIT_LENGTH);
191     mesh.setUnitDimension(unitMap_m);
192     mesh.setAttribute("accumulationPolicy", accumulationPolicyName_m);
193     mesh.setAttribute("detectorPlacement", detectorPlacement_m);
194     mesh.setAttribute("detectorDistanceInMeters", detectorDistance_m);
195     return mesh;
196 }
197
198 /** Prepare an openPMD mesh record component for storage
199  *
200  * @param mesh
201  */
202 HINLINE ::openPMD::MeshRecordComponent prepareMRC(::openPMD::Mesh& mesh)
203 {
204     ::openPMD::MeshRecordComponent mrc
205         = mesh[:openPMD::MeshRecordComponent::SCALAR];
206
207     std::vector<uint64_t> shape = openPMD::asStandardVector(globalExtent_m);
208     ::openPMD::Dataset dataset{datatype_m, std::move(shape)};
209     mrc.resetDataset(std::move(dataset));
210     mrc.setPosition(std::vector<float_X>{0.5_X, 0.5_X});
211     mrc.setUnitSI(unit_m);
212     return mrc;
213 }
214
215 public:
216 HINLINE void openIteration(uint32_t const currentStep)
217 {
218     iteration_m = std::make_unique<::openPMD::Iteration>(
219         openPMDSeries_m->writeIterations()[currentStep]);
220     // Write simulation meta data
221     openPMD::WriteMeta>(*openPMDSeries_m, *iteration_m, currentStep);
222 }
223

```

```

224 HINLINE void flush()
225 {
226     // Avoid deadlock between not finished pmacc tasks and mpi calls in
227     // openPMD.
228     __getTransactionEvent().waitForFinished();
229     openPMDSeries_m->flush();
230 }
231 HINLINE void closeIteration()
232 {
233     // Avoid deadlock between not finished pmacc tasks and mpi calls in
234     // openPMD.
235     __getTransactionEvent().waitForFinished();
236     iteration_m->close();
237 }
238
239 /** Write data to the output array
240  *
241  * @param currentStep current simulation step
242  * @param pointer base pointer to the data that should be written
243  */
244 HINLINE void operator()(
245     uint32_t const currentStep,
246     T_ValueType* pointer,
247     std::string const& meshSuffix = "")
248 {
249     //           // read & write access type is not possible when the
250     //           iterations are stored in separate files
251     //           switch(iterationEncoding_m)
252     //           {
253     //           case ::openPMD::IterationEncoding::fileBased:
254     //               openSeries(::openPMD::Access::CREATE);
255     //               break;
256     //           case ::openPMD::IterationEncoding::groupBased:
257     //               openSeries(::openPMD::Access::READ_WRITE);
258     //               break;
259     //           // there is also variableBased encoding on the API's
260     //           // dev branch, not sure what it is and when
261     //           // would it appear in a release
262     //           default:
263     //               throw std::runtime_error(
264     //                   "PhotonDetectorWriter: Internal error.
265     //                   Unrecognized iteration encoding.");
266     //           }
267
268     ::openPMD::Mesh mesh = prepareMesh(meshSuffix);
269     ::openPMD::MeshRecordComponent mrc = prepareMRC(mesh);
270
271     mrc.storeChunk<T_ValueType>(
272         ::openPMD::shareRaw(pointer),
273         ::openPMD::Offset(DIM2, 0u),
274         openPMD::asStandardVector(globalExtent_m));
275 }
276 };

```

```

277 } // namespace photonDetector
278 } // namespace plugins
279 } // namespace picongpu

```

File 80. plugins/photonDetector/DetectorParams.def

```

1  /* Copyright 2015-2021 Alexander Grund, Pawel Ordyna */
2
3  #pragma once
4
5  #include "picongpu/simulation_defines.hpp"
6
7  #include <pmacc/math/Vector.hpp>
8
9  namespace picongpu
10 {
11     namespace plugins
12     {
13         namespace photonDetector
14         {
15             /** Placement of the detector relative to the simulation box
16              *
17              * XFront means the detector is placed parallel to the yz plane on a negative z
18              * coordinate (to the left of the simulation using the definitions from
19              * ExchangeType) XRear means the detector is placed parallel to the yz plane on
20              * a positive z coordinate (to the right of the simulation using the
21              * definitions from ExchangeType) Similarly for Y and Z;
22              */
23             enum class DetectorPlacement
24             {
25                 XFront,
26                 XRear,
27                 YFront,
28                 YRear,
29                 ZFront,
30                 ZRear
31             };
32
33             /** Detector description
34              */
35             struct DetectorParams
36             {
37                 const DataSpace<DIM2> size;
38                 const pmacc::math::Vector<float_X, DIM2> anglePerCell;
39                 const DetectorPlacement detectorPlacement;
40
41                 /** DetectorParams constructor
42                  *
43                  * @param size detector size (shape)
44                  * @param anglePerCell angle range covered by 1 cell

```

```
44  * @param detectorPlacement detector placement relative to the simulation box
45  */
46  DetectorParams(
47      const DataSpace<DIM2>& size,
48      const pmacc::math::Vector<float_X, DIM2>& anglePerCell,
49      const DetectorPlacement& detectorPlacement);
50  };
51
52  } // namespace photonDetector
53  } // namespace plugins
54  } // namespace picongpu
```
